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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D6.3 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 2

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EP	European Parliament
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IEP	Individual Exploitation Plan
Mx	Month x
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The communication, dissemination and exploitation communication activities of the FIERCE project have been a central component of its overall strategy, playing a key role in promoting the project's goals, scope and contributions to its diverse target audiences. From the outset, FIERCE adopted a multifaceted and carefully planned approach to:

- Raise awareness about the project and the theoretical and practical tools developed during its implementation
- Increase engagement and foster the active involvement of target groups in project activities
- Promote the long-term exploitation and sustainability of these tools, practices, and results beyond the project's lifetime.

This deliverable outlines the progress made and provides detailed statistics and insights on dissemination and communication activities – both online and offline – from February 2024 to August 2025 (M18–M36). It reflects the results of actions undertaken by Consortium Members during this period and includes an overview of the project's communication, dissemination, exploitation and sustainability efforts.

As the third and final report on **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities** (following reports submitted in M6 and M18), this deliverable consolidates the outreach efforts across the full duration of the project.

The following chapters present data and insights on the FIERCE website and social media channels, partner networking efforts, and all additional initiatives undertaken to promote the project and its messages, including press releases, newsletters, videos, podcasts, blog articles, and campaigns.

Finally, this deliverable also outlines the overall **Sustainability, Exploitation, and Replication Strategy** of the FIERCE project, ensuring its key results continue to generate impact beyond the Horizon Europe funding period.

1. Introduction

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE (Feminist movements revitalizing democracy in Europe) is a Horizon Europe-funded project that set out to bridge feminist research, activism, and policymaking in an era of growing social inequalities, political disaffection, and the rise of anti-gender movements across Europe.

The project aimed to generate both theoretical insights and practical tools to support alliances between feminist movements, civil society, and decision-makers – revitalizing democratic practices through inclusive and gender-equal perspectives.

Adopting an interdisciplinary, multi-level, and participatory research approach, FIERCE explored the dynamics between feminist and anti-gender actors and their influence on institutional politics and public discourse. The research focused on the period 2010 – 2023 and examined five key areas where gender-based controversies have emerged:

- Labour market and care
- Health and reproductive rights
- LGBTQ+ rights
- Migration
- Gender-based violence

Through interviews, Critical Frame Analysis, and Discourse Network Analysis, the project investigated how feminist movements mobilise and respond to threats – while also highlighting their role as democratic innovators.

FIERCE conducted eight case studies across Europe and its neighborhood – France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, and Spain – capturing diverse socio-political, geographical, and welfare contexts. Beyond national comparisons, the project adopted a cross-cutting lens to understand how gender-related controversies influence policymaking across borders.

Additionally, in close collaboration with feminist organisations, the project developed co-creation activities and pilot actions that demonstrate how feminist knowledge and practices can shape more inclusive and resilient democracies. This bottom-up, impact-driven approach lies at the heart of FIERCE's ambition to turn research into action, and to leave a lasting legacy in policy, activism and public debate.

1.2. WP6 - Objectives

Work Package 6: Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation was designed to amplify the reach and impact of FIERCE, ensuring that the project's results and approaches are widely known, accessible, and durable beyond the project's lifetime. The core objectives of WP6 are to:

- Raise awareness and maximise the visibility of FIERCE's results among key target groups
- Facilitate effective knowledge-sharing and coordination among consortium partners
- Design and implement a strategic, multi-channel approach for communication, dissemination, and exploitation
- Assess the exploitation potential and added value of FIERCE outcomes both during and after the project's implementation
- Build and actively engage a community of stakeholders around the project's themes and results
- Foster synergies and collaborations with relevant EU-funded projects, clusters, networks, and initiatives.

1.3. The Deliverable 6.3

1.3.1. Purpose and Scope

Deliverable **D6.3 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Progress Report 2”** presents the final report of WP6, primarily covering the period from February 2024 (M19) to August 2025 (M36). In some cases, it also reports on activities spanning the entire project duration to provide a complete picture of FIERCE’s communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts.

The report offers an overview of all activities carried out, along with reflections on lessons learned, stakeholder engagement, and the project’s final exploitation and sustainability strategy. It builds on the foundation established in previous reports (D6.1 – Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan; D6.2 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1) and consolidates the full range of tools, channels, and actions deployed to promote FIERCE’s work across Europe and beyond.

1.3.2. Target Audience

The main audiences for this report are both internal and external:

- **Internal:** consortium partners, for whom the report serves as a resource to support the refinement of future actions, the legacy of FIERCE’s communication, dissemination, and impact strategies, as well as the exploitation of its results.
- **External:** EU project reviewers, communication and dissemination professionals, and other Horizon Europe project teams interested in adopting or learning from FIERCE’s approach. It may also serve as a practical guide and inspiration for organisations advancing gender equality, inclusive innovation, and democratic participation through research and advocacy, as well as for feminist activists, civil society groups, and social movements who can draw on the project’s results and the Transferability Guidebook to replicate and adapt FIERCE’s practices.

1.3.3. Relation to other WPs and Deliverables

The activities outlined in this deliverable are closely interlinked with the overall implementation of the project and contribute to the visibility and impact of FIERCE across all Work Packages. In particular, the dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts have been directly connected to WP4 and WP5, supporting the outreach and engagement of key audiences – especially feminist organisations, collectives, and activists – in the project’s co-creation processes.

1.3.4. Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured into the following sections:

- Chapter 1 introduces the project scope, the WP6 objectives, the document’s target audience, the relationship to the other work packages and the structure.
- Chapter 2 presents an overview of the reported communication and dissemination activities implemented throughout the addressed period.
- Chapter 3 presents updates on the project’s exploitation and sustainability plan, transferability and replication guidebook and the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network.
- Chapter 4 completes the report with a conclusion that comments on the overall actions.
- The Annex section

2. Reporting of the Communication and Dissemination activities

This section presents the strategic communication and dissemination activities carried out mainly during the second reporting period of the FIERCE project (M18 - M36). These actions have been central to promoting the project's objectives, engaging diverse audiences, and ensuring wide visibility of its outcomes. Through a combination of **digital platforms, targeted campaigns, events, and outreach activities**, FIERCE has worked to strengthen its presence, share knowledge, and foster dialogue on feminist democratic innovation. The following subsections provide a detailed account of each channel and tool used during this period, highlighting both reach and impact.

2.1. FIERCE Website

The [FIERCE website](#) is one of the project's core communication and dissemination tools. It was launched in October 2022 (M2), successfully achieving Milestone 11. Since then, it has served as a central hub for sharing updates, resources, and results with the public, stakeholders, and the broader research and policy community.

Throughout the project, the website functioned as a dynamic platform, continuously updated to reflect the full range of FIERCE activities. It showcased the project's research outcomes and gave visibility to the co-creation work carried out through the [FIERCE National Labs](#), [Transnational Labs and the FIERCE campaign](#) and the [FIERCE Actions](#), developed in close collaboration with feminist organisations and activists across Europe.

The website also highlights one of the project's most significant milestones – the [FIERCE Final Conference](#), held in June 2025. This event marked a high point for the project, bringing together a diverse and multisectoral audience to reflect on FIERCE's achievements and envision its legacy. With over 60 onsite participants and 135 online attendees, the conference welcomed researchers, activists, policymakers, and representatives from feminist and human rights organisations across Europe featuring diverse voices from across the consortium and beyond.

Several new sections and updates were introduced to enhance accessibility and visibility:

- The [Resources](#) subpage – dedicated to making FIERCE's work publicly available – was regularly updated with:
 - [FIERCE's brand identity and Promotional materials](#) in English and partner languages
 - [Blog posts](#) documenting the project's progress, opinions and findings
 - [Newsletters](#), [press releases](#), [podcasts](#), and project publications
 - All [public deliverables](#), which will be uploaded upon approval by the European Commission
- The [Clustering](#) subpage features four Horizon Europe projects funded under the same call as FIERCE. Through direct communication with their representatives, a summary of each project, accompanied by their logos and website links was presented. This section reflects FIERCE's commitment to fostering clustering synergies and knowledge exchange with sister projects and similar activities.
- The [News](#) section was regularly updated throughout the project's lifetime with key announcements, project milestones, meetings, updates and partner achievements to keep the wider public and stakeholders informed about ongoing activities.

The website will continue its restructuring after the project's end to ensure a high uptake of the project results from FIERCE's target audience.

Website Analytics

Using the “Google Analytics 4” tool, we have access to a detailed overview of traffic to the FIERCE website. This tool enables tracking not only visitor numbers but also other relevant quantitative information for users who visit the project website.

The following figures showcase online metrics for the project website for the period between February 2024 (M18) and August 2025 (M36).

According to the figure below, over **5,300 users** reached at least one of the pages on our website during the reporting period. According to information extracted from the official [Help Center](#) of the Analytics tool, by the term “Users”, we refer to the number of people who engaged with our site within the specified date range. In particular, these users performed over **67,000 actions** on the website with an average session duration of over **4 minutes**.

Figure 1: Website Analytics M18-M36

Demographic details: Country

According to the figure below, a list of the countries that most users come from is depicted. It is evident that traffic comes to our website not only from our partners’ countries but also from countries around the world, showing the outreach of the website beyond the countries of the directly involved parties.

Figure 2: Demographic analytics M18-M36

Most visited Pages and Screens

The figure below illustrates not only the broad visibility of the FIERCE project (as shown by homepage views) but also **the strong engagement of users exploring pages dedicated to key project activities – demonstrating genuine interest rather than random browsing.**

Page path and screen class	↓ Views	Active users	Views per active user
Total	21,112 100% of total	5,303 100% of total	3.98 Avg 0%
1 /	6,762 (32.03%)	3,301 (62.25%)	2.05
2 /final-conference/	1,358 (6.43%)	550 (10.37%)	2.47
3 /national-labs/	1,106 (5.24%)	582 (10.97%)	1.90
4 /about-1/	763 (3.61%)	514 (9.69%)	1.48
5 /news/	734 (3.48%)	257 (4.85%)	2.86
6 /consortium/	621 (2.94%)	450 (8.49%)	1.38
7 /public-deliverables/	573 (2.71%)	284 (5.36%)	2.02
8 /project-vision/	537 (2.54%)	337 (6.35%)	1.59
9 /open-call-for-fierce-actions-empowering-feminist-movements-in-europe/	523 (2.48%)	327 (6.17%)	1.60
10 /fierce-actions/	456 (2.16%)	166 (3.13%)	2.75

Figure 3: Most visited Pages and Screens M18-M36

Traffic acquisition sources

The figure below shows the main sources directing users to the FIERCE website. Notably, the vast majority of visitors access the site by typing the address <https://fierce-project.eu/> directly (shown as *Direct* in the figure), highlighting both the **project’s visibility and the strong awareness generated through our communication efforts.** Other traffic sources include: *Organic Search* – visits from non-paid Google search results; *Referral* – users arriving via links from other websites; *Organic Social* – traffic driven by the project’s social media profiles; and *Unassigned* – visits where the source could not be identified.

Figure 4: Most visited Pages and Screens

2.2. Social Media and online channels

Social media has played a central role in the communication and dissemination strategy of FIERCE, serving as a vital tool to **engage diverse audiences, promote project results, and contribute to wider conversations around gender equality, democracy, and feminist action in Europe**. These platforms have enabled real-time communication and broad visibility for project developments, while supporting interaction with stakeholders, partners and the general public.

From the outset of the project, dedicated FIERCE accounts were created on major platforms to share key content, including:

- Project news, milestones and deliverables
- Blog posts, press releases and newsletters
- Scientific publications and open-access resources
- Videos, podcasts, and campaign materials
- Activities and achievements of consortium partners

In addition to project-generated content, the FIERCE social media presence has actively engaged with relevant international days, awareness campaigns, and institutional initiatives – such as **International Women’s Day (March 8)** and the **International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (November 25)** – through both original posts and curated shares from reputable sources including the **European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)**, **UN Women**, and the **European Parliament**.

A collaborative approach has been maintained throughout the project’s online presence:

- Partners’ organisational accounts are tagged to amplify reach and visibility
- Relevant external stakeholders and EU entities – such as the **European Research Executive Agency (REA)** - are mentioned in targeted posts
- Regular interactions and mutual promotion have been established with FIERCE sister projects, supporting cross-project engagement and knowledge exchange

All posts are accompanied by visual assets – such as tailored graphics or banners – featuring the **FIERCE logo** and the **EU disclaimer**, enhancing the visual identity and recognisability of the project across platforms.

To monitor performance and inform content planning, a dedicated monitoring log has been maintained, tracking monthly social media metrics using each platform’s native analytics tools. These insights have supported continuous improvement of the project's online engagement strategy.

As of the reporting period, the FIERCE social media accounts have reached **1,800 followers** across all platforms, with a steady growth rate observed over the reporting period.

The subsections below provide a detailed overview of the performance and engagement levels across each platform used by the project.

2.2.1. Facebook

By M36 (August 2025), the FIERCE [Facebook page](#) had reached **437 followers**. During this reporting period, a total of **269 posts** were published.

Figure 5: FIERCE Facebook followers (M18-M36)

As shown in figure 5, the number of followers **steadily increased as the project progressed**. A particularly notable growth occurred when **FIERCE adopted a more participatory content strategy – encouraging audience interaction** through open calls, event registrations, and the sharing of project actions and results.

The following figure 6 provides an overview of the FIERCE Facebook page demographics. As illustrated, **women make up the majority of the audience, with over half of the followers falling within the 25–44 age range.**

Figure 6: Demographic analytics for the Facebook FIERCE page M18-M36

During the reporting period, the project's Facebook page recorded over **1,500 interactions**, averaging around **10 likes, comments, or shares** per post.

Figure 7: Interactions in Facebook page (M18-M36)

2.2.2. X (Twitter)

The X (formerly Twitter) account of the project, [@Fierceprojecteu](#), has a total of **231 followers** during this reporting period. Between M7 and M36, **444 posts were published**.

Due to recent changes in the platform’s reporting policies, detailed account-level analytics are no longer accessible without a paid subscription. It is worth noting that, while Twitter was once a highly influential platform, its transition to X has led to a decline in reliability and trustworthiness, affecting both the project’s engagement and its relevance to our audiences.

2.2.3. LinkedIn

The [FIERCE LinkedIn](#) page of the project has accumulated a total of **727 followers**. Based on LinkedIn analytics aggregated over a 12-month period prior to the preparation of this report – and within the limits of available platform data – FIERCE posts have generated over **22,500 impressions**, defined as the number of times content appeared on users’ screens. Engagement with the content has been strong, with **870 reactions** and **26 reposts** recorded.

Figure 8: Highlights for the LinkedIn page M24-M36

The **engagement rate** – then ratio of people interacting with the content to those who viewed it – stands at **16%**, which is more than **400% above** the highest industry benchmark¹. Notably, some posts achieved an engagement rate of **25.8%**, meaning that **one in four viewers** actively reacted to the content.

Such results are exceptionally high for research and EU-funded project communications, highlighting the strong resonance of FIERCE content with its audience and the effectiveness of its engagement strategy. These high levels of interaction were achieved particularly when communicating **key project outputs and milestones** – including **scientific publications**, the **Final Conference**, **registration links for events**, and **project resources** – showing the concrete value and relevance of FIERCE’s activities for its community.

Figure 9: Summary of LinkedIn engagement rate (M24-M36)

LinkedIn Visitor Demographics – Job Functions

As shown in Figure below FIERCE LinkedIn attracts a diverse and strategically relevant audience, reflecting the project’s broad impact across research, policy, and practice. The largest groups of visitors come from **Research (12.1%)** and **Media & Communication (12.1%)**, showing strong interest from both academic stakeholders and communication professionals. This is followed by **Program and Project Management (10.5%)**, **Education (7%)**, and **Business Development (5.4%)**, highlighting FIERCE’s appeal to knowledge producers, educators, and decision-makers.

Importantly, FIERCE also reaches **Community and Social Services (4.2%)**, **Healthcare**, **Legal**, and **administrative professionals**, demonstrating its relevance across sectors engaged in gender equality, inclusive innovation, and social change.

¹ Source: [Socinator](#)

These insights confirm that the project’s online presence successfully engages key audiences from researchers and activists to policymakers and practitioners, who can act as multipliers in advancing feminist democratic innovation across Europe.

Figure 10: LinkedIn Visitor Demographics – Job Functions

2.2.4. Instagram

The Instagram page of the project, [@fierceproject_eu](https://www.instagram.com/fierceproject_eu), currently counts **444 followers**, with **129 posts** and more than double that number in stories. During this reporting period, the page has reached **26,400 accounts**, as shown in the figure below. Notably, this reach has been achieved entirely **organically**, without any paid promotion – a strong indicator of the page’s growing visibility and engagement.

Figure 11: Instagram Analytics (M18-M36)

Followers’ demographics reveal that the vast majority are women, primarily within the **25–44 age range**. This is consistent with the audience trends observed on Facebook, pointing to a solid and coherent community across FIERCE’s social media platforms.

Figure 12: Instagram Followers Demographics

In terms of **country demographics**, the audience shows a **widespread across several European countries**, extending well beyond the FIERCE partner countries.

Figure 13: Instagram Followers by Top Countries

During the reporting period, the profile received **2,939 views**, with approximately **25% of these coming from non-followers** – a clear sign that the use of hashtags and discoverability strategies is attracting new audiences. The profile recorded a **2% link-in-bio click-through rate**, demonstrating strong performance in driving traffic to project resources.

Figure 14: Instagram Engagement Statistics (M18-M36)

2.3. The FIERCE Newsletter

Since the project's inception, the **FIERCE Newsletter**, all issues accessible by project's website, has served as a vital communication vehicle, fostering engagement across stakeholders, disseminating project milestones, and shaping public discourse on feminist democratic innovation. A total of **17 editions** have been published to date, making the newsletter one of the project's most consistent and widely anticipated outreach tools.

Each edition provided timely updates on FIERCE activities, including new deliverables, events, campaign highlights, research insights, and opportunities to get involved. The newsletter is created and distributed via Mailchimp², a GDPR-compliant platform that ensures secure data management and reliable delivery directly to recipients' inboxes (avoiding spam folders). Designed with clarity and accessibility in mind, the newsletter effectively bridged the gap between internal progress and public visibility, while reinforcing the project's institutional identity and messaging.

The table below summarises the **topics** covered in all editions and publications of the FIERCE Newsletter; each linked to the corresponding issue on the project website for easy access and reference.

Newsletter No	Publication Date	Topic
1st Newsletter	February 2023 (M6)	Introduction to our audience informing them about the project, its scope and next planned actions.
2nd Newsletter	October 2023 (M13)	Activities that happened during the first year of the project with an emphasis on the successful completion of the first co-creation cycle.
3rd Newsletter	December 2023 (M16)	Special newsletter issue announcing the 1st FIERCE online roundtable discussion and inviting subscribers to join.

² <https://mailchimp.com/>

Newsletter No	Publication Date	Topic
4th Newsletter	February 2024 (M18)	Activities that happened during the past year of the project with an emphasis on the successful completion of the second co-creation cycle and the first FIERCE presentation video.
5th Newsletter	April 2024 (M20)	Dedicated edition for the announcement of the FIERCE Campaign Launch event: “Candidates and Feminists ready for a change” and an open invitation to those interested to participate.
6th Newsletter	May 2024 (M21)	This Newsletter issue announces the “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe” campaign-closing and pre-electoral event and openly invites those interested to participate.
7th Newsletter	May 2024 (M21)	This newsletter issue announces the launch of project’s new feminist podcast series, FIERCE Dialogues.
8th Newsletter	September 2024 (M25)	This newsletter issue is announcing the OPEN CALL for the FIERCE Actions.
9th Newsletter	September 2024 (M25)	A dedicated Newsletter edition for the release of a new podcast episode “Feminist Mobilizations in Italy”
10th Newsletter	October 2024 (M26)	A dedicated Newsletter edition for the release of a new podcast episode “Cybersexism and Democracy” from France
11th Newsletter	December 2024 (M28)	A special Newsletter issue that shares the year’s highlights and the FIERCE key moments and milestones of 2024!
12th Newsletter	April 2025 (M32)	This Newsletter shares the invitation of the 2nd FIERCE Transnational Network Online Meeting
13th Newsletter	May 2025 (M33)	This Newsletter edition announces the opening of the registrations for the FIERCE Final Conference “Feminist Futures for Revitalising Democracy Across Europe “
14th Newsletter	May 2025 (M33)	A dedicated Newsletter edition for the release of two new FIERCE podcast episodes. The Spanish: “Anti-Racist Perspectives on Feminist Activism in Spain” and the Turkish: “Legal Feminist Activism: Voices from the Field”
15th Newsletter	June 2025 (M34)	This Newsletter edition shares an official invitation for policymakers, researchers, feminist activists, and civil society organisations to join us in Brussels for our Final Conference.
16th Newsletter	July 2025 (M35)	This Newsletter edition is dedicated to two major outcomes of the FIERCE project. The launch of the FIERCE Feminist Online Course and the transfeminist Self-Defense Manual created by the Italian National Lab.
17th Newsletter	July 2025 (M35)	This Newsletter issue presents the Greek podcast episode: “The feminist politics of the body as pivotal to the struggle for social justice in our times”

Table 1: Publication Date and Topic of the FIERCE Newsletters

Newsletter subscribers – Community of stakeholders

According to data extracted from Mailchimp, the platform used for creating and distributing FIERCE newsletters, there are currently **919 subscribers** at the time of this report. The subscription form invites subscribers to identify their background and area of activity, such as EU-wide or global networks, civil society, policymakers, feminist organisations/activists, and researchers. The breakdown of these categories is presented in the diagram below.

Figure 15: Subscribers per affiliation

Mailchimp Subscriber Affiliation breakdown (from dropdown form responses)

The Mailchimp subscriber list demonstrates FIERCE’s wide international reach and strong connections across sectors. The majority of subscribers (671) come from **EU-wide or global networks and initiatives**, showing the project’s resonance beyond national borders. Significant engagement also comes from **researchers, academics and community experts** (110), while **feminist organisations and activists** (43) and **civil society members** (38) highlight grassroots and public interest. Smaller but important groups include **policymakers** (9), whose involvement signals policy-level attention, and a mix of **other/uncategorised subscribers** (48), pointing to potential areas for refining future classifications.

Newsletter Performance Insights

Regarding newsletter performance, the open rates recorded during this reporting period range between **25% and 55%**, as illustrated in the figure below. This positions FIERCE well above industry benchmarks³, placing it among the **top-performing senders** in terms of audience engagement. Such results indicate a consistently high level of interest from subscribers, reflecting both the relevance of the content and the effectiveness of the project’s communication strategy.

³ Source: [CampaignMonitor.com](https://campaignmonitor.com)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Status	Audience	Analytics
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Online Feminist Course Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Wed, Jul 02, 10:31 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Wed, Jul 02, 10:31 AM	Fierce Project eu 673 recipients	25.7% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Final Conference - Brussels 19-20 June 2025 Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Tue, Jun 03, 10:38 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Tue, Jun 03, 10:38 AM	Fierce Project eu 432 recipients	38.7% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Dialogues_ Spanish and Turkish Podcasts Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Mon, May 12, 10:19 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Mon, May 12, 10:19 AM	Fierce Project eu 245 recipients	50.4% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Final Conference Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Mon, May 05, 09:35 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Mon, May 05, 09:35 AM	Fierce Project eu 236 recipients	48.1% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	2nd FIERCE Transnational Network Meeting! Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Mon, Apr 28, 05:08 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Mon, Apr 28, 05:08 AM	Fierce Project eu 236 recipients	54.8% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Highlights of the Year! Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Mon, Dec 23, 2024, 09:07 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Mon, Dec 23, 2024, 09:07 AM	Fierce Project eu 213 recipients	37.3% Opens
<input type="checkbox"/>	FIERCE Dialogues_ Cybersexism and Democracy - the French podcast Regular email · Legacy builder Last edited Thu, Oct 03, 2024, 09:15 AM by Fierce Project	Sent Thu, Oct 03, 2024, 09:15 AM	Fierce Project eu 200 recipients	50.5% Opens

Figure 16: Newsletter Open Rate Insights

To increase the number of subscribers, “teaser” social media posts announcing an upcoming newsletter are posted a few days before its publication. The following figures represent graphics prepared for posting in social media channels before and after the newsletter publication.

Figure 17: Tailored visual graphics for promoting the FIERCE newsletter

2.4. Press Releases

There are currently **12** [Press Releases](#) available on the FIERCE website. Press releases are prepared by VIL and disseminated to all partners to fill in their respective information and disseminate them in

their networks and their organisations’ communication channels and media, either in English or in their respective languages. All newsletters are displayed on the project website in chronological order.

Figure 18: FIERCE "Press Release" webpage

The **table below** summarises the topics covered in all Press Releases of the FIERCE Newsletter, each linked to the corresponding file on the project website for easy access and reference.

Press Release No	Publication Date	Topic
1st Press Release	April 2022	AAU Press release New project – Feminist Movements Revitalising Democracy in Europe
2nd Press Release	August 2022	ViL Press release ViLabs goes FIERCE!
3rd Press Release	September 2022	Europa Wire The Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE) project kicks-off!
4th Press Release	December 2023 (M16)	FIERCE Invitation to the 1st FIERCE Online Roundtable Discussion
5th Press Release	April 2024 (M20)	FIERCE Invitation to the Launching Event of the FIERCE campaign
6th Press Release	May 2024 (M21)	FIERCE Invitation to the Pre-Electoral Event of the “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe”

		campaign
7th Press Release	December 2024 (M28)	FIERCE FIERCE Week in Venice brings Together Feminist Activists, Local and EU gender equality Organizations, and Academia 4–7 November 2024
8th Press Release	March 2025 (M31)	FIERCE FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network – First Online Meeting
9th Press Release	March 2025 (M31)	FIERCE International Day for Women’s Rights 2025 • Stronger Together, Always FIERCE!
10th Press Release	June 2025 (M34)	FIERCE Final Conference “Feminist futures for revitalising democracy across Europe” and Pre-Conference event “Feminist Movements in Time and Space & Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe” in Brusells 19-20 June 2025
11th Press Release	June 2025 (M34)	FIERCE Launches Free Online Feminist Course to Resist Anti-Gender Backlash and Strengthen Feminist Alliances Across Europe
12th Press Release	July 2025 (M35)	FIERCE Final Conference – “Feminist futures for revitalising democracy across Europe” Brussels – 20 June 2025

Table 2: Press Releases overview

2.5. FIERCE Blog post series

The FIERCE blog space has served as a dynamic platform for knowledge sharing, partner engagement, and public outreach. Hosted on the project website under the [Blogs section](#), a total of **34 blog posts** have been published to date.

Figure 19: FIERCE "Blogs" webpage

FIERCE "Blogs" webpage Throughout the project, several **curated blog series** were developed in close collaboration with FIERCE partners:

- **“Meet the FIERCE Team”**

This introductory series showcased all project partners, offering insight into the organisations they represent, their specific roles within the project, and their expectations regarding FIERCE’s impact.

- **“Why is FIERCE Relevant to...?”**

Authored by the eight national teams, this series addressed the relevance of the FIERCE project within each country’s context, drawing on local political, social, and gender equality dynamics.

- **“Wins of Feminism”**

Based on findings from Deliverable 2.1, this series highlighted key feminist achievements across partner countries from 2010 to 2021. Partners contributed country-specific narratives that celebrated progress and acknowledged ongoing challenges.

Additional blogs have been published to complement FIERCE’s social media campaigns and international observances, including:

- A **March 2023 blog** for International Women’s Day
- A **November 2023 blog** for the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women
- A country-specific article on **Feminism in Denmark**, authored by our Danish partners

Most recently, in **November 2024**, and as part of the **joint campaign with sister projects**, FIERCE published a compelling **four-article blog series** on gender-based violence, with contributions from **UCM, AU, AUTH, and UL**. Each blog post contributed to the project’s overarching aim of bridging feminist research, activism, and public dialogue, while ensuring visibility for partner contributions and national perspectives across Europe.

Our blogs have been promoted on our social media channels, inviting our audience to view and engage with them. For that reason, tailored visual materials were created to accompany the social media posts and “catch the eye” of the reader, making it more attractive for them to engage with our content.

Figure 20: Digital banners used in the social media promotion of blogs

2.6. FIERCE Podcasts

FIERCE developed its own feminist podcast series, “[FIERCE Dialogues](#)” as an innovative communication tool to reach diverse audiences and share feminist knowledge in an accessible way. During the reporting period, **eight podcast episodes** were produced, fully meeting the relevant project KPI.

Through interviews with voices from eight different European countries, the podcast series offered rich, nuanced discussions that linked past experiences to present realities and future feminist strategies. The episodes explored a wide spectrum of themes – **from feminist movements and gender equality to women’s and LGBTQ+ rights** – while addressing both country-specific challenges and solutions, as well as broader issues at the EU level.

Episodes were conducted by FIERCE partners, who interviewed members of civil society organisations, feminist activists, gender experts, researchers from sister projects and academics from their respective countries. Recordings took place in partner’s national language or in English. The aim was to offer authentic, context-specific insights while fostering cross-border knowledge exchange.

The series’ objectives were to:

- Provide insights into pressing feminist challenges and achievements at national and EU level.
- Increase public understanding of efforts to achieve gender-equal and inclusive democracies.
- Promote intersectional, inclusive knowledge-sharing through accessible formats.

All episodes were published on the [FIERCE website](#), [YouTube channel](#) (with English subtitles), and [Spotify](#) account. The decision to include YouTube with subtitles was strategic and directly aligned with FIERCE’s commitment to accessibility – ensuring that feminist discussions could be followed by people with hearing impairments and those who do not speak the original recording language.

Production Process

The process of producing the podcast series was demanding and meticulously carried out by the WP6 leader (VIL), who handled the workflow and coordination of the task single-handedly, while liaising closely with project partners. All episodes were conducted via Zoom through a link provided by VIL and were recorded, with the WP6 leader present to ensure the sessions ran smoothly.

1. Planning & Guidelines

- WP6 prepared **detailed guidelines** to help partners identify topics and guests, structure the interviews and set recording dates.
- Before each podcast, partners received a **briefing document** outlining the episode’s theme, objectives, and technical considerations, helping interviewers feel confident and well-prepared (Annex 2).

2. Recording

- Episodes were recorded via Zoom using links provided by WP6.
- WP6 leader joined each session to ensure smooth facilitation.
- Recordings were exported in both audio and video formats.

3. Branding & Consistency

- A branded **intro and outro** was created for all episodes, using the same music and also visuals for social media posting and promotion for consistency (See figure 21)

- **Intro script:**

“Welcome to FIERCE Dialogues; the official podcast of the European Project FIERCE! Across a series of episodes featuring interviews from 8 different European countries, we delve into insightful conversations, fostering informative discussions that touch upon historical contexts, present challenges, and explore potential future pathways.

These FIERCE Dialogues traverse topics related to feminist movements, gender equality, women’s and LGBTQ+ rights, and the political challenges and solutions unique to each FIERCE country or at the European Union level.”

- **Outro script:**

“FIERCE. Engendering Democracy! FIERCE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme.”

4. Editing & Subtitling

- WP6 leader (VIL) edited all audio and video files using a video editing platform.
- Subtitles were added for YouTube versions, with careful attention to **accurate translation into English** and **precise synchronisation**. Partners reviewed subtitles before publication.
- Intro/outro visuals were added to each episode.

5. Publication & Promotion

- Episodes were uploaded to **YouTube** and **Spotify**.
- Dedicated **social media posts** were published across all platforms. (See figure 22 below for selected examples)
- **Newsletters** announcing each episode were sent to the FIERCE mailing list. Selected example [HERE](#)

The **FIERCE Dialogues** podcast series has proven to be a valuable legacy tool for the project. Beyond the reporting period, the episodes remain freely accessible, offering a lasting repository of feminist knowledge, strategies, and experiences from across Europe. With **over 500 listeners reached across YouTube and Spotify**, the series has already demonstrated its ability to engage diverse audiences. By combining academic and activist voices in an inclusive, multilingual, and accessible format, the podcasts ensure that FIERCE’s insights continue to inspire, inform, and support feminist movements, policymakers, and researchers well beyond the project’s end.

A full list of episodes, topics, participants, and publication dates is provided in the table below.

Partner’s country	Publication Date	Participating Speakers	Topics and Spotify/YouTube links
Slovenia	Jun 2023	Partners: Roman Kuhar (UL) Mojca Pajnik (MI) Guests: Dr. Metka Mencin, Tea Hvala, and Tija Jakič	Feminism and reproductive rights • Slovenia Spotify YouTube N/A video recording
Denmark	Apr 2024	Partner: Andreas Beyer Gregersen (AU) Guest: Gertrud Magnusson (Danish NGO “Tegn Buen”)	Feminism from the perspective of people with disability • Denmark Spotify YouTube

Poland	July 2024	Partner: Grzegorz Piotrowski (UG) Guest: Prof. Elżbieta Korolczuk (University of Södertörn, University of Warsaw and sister project CCINDLE ⁴)	Reproductive Rights and Interactions with the Political System • Poland Spotify YouTube
Italy	Sep 2024	Partners: Anastasia Barone (SNS), Giada Bonu Rosenkranz (SNS) Guest: Aurora Perego (member of sister project CCINDLE)	Feminist mobilizations in Italy • Italy Spotify YouTube
France	Oct 2024	Partner: Gabrielle Jourde (EA) Guest: Laure Salmona (French organisation “Féministes contre le cyberharcèlement”)	Cybersexism and Democracy • France Spotify YouTube
Spain	April 2025	Partners: Elin Peterson (UCM), Inés Campillo (UCM) Guest: Tatiana Romero (Migration and Anti-racism Commission of the 8M Commission of Madrid)	Anti-Racist Perspectives on Feminist Activism in Spain • Spain Spotify YouTube
Turkey	May 2025	Partner: Bertil Emrah Oder (KU) Guest: Deniz Bayram (Lawyer and active member in civil society & Turkish feminist movement)	Legal Feminist Activism: Voices from the Field • Turkey Spotify YouTube
Greece	July 2025	Partner: Alexandros Kioupiolis (AUTH) Guest: Nina Seferiadou (member of the feminist collective “Meduses” and the “Anti-racist Initiative” in Larisa - Greece)	The feminist politics of the body as pivotal to the struggle for social justice in our times • Greece Spotify YouTube

Table 3: Publications overview M7-M36

Figure 21: Examples of digital banners used for the promotion of each episode

⁴ CCINDLE - Co-creating Inclusive Intersectional Democratic Spaces Across Europe: <https://ccindle.org/>

Figure 22: Selected example of a social media post

2.7. FIERCE Videos

The project's target KPI was to produce at least three videos over its lifecycle. To date, the FIERCE project has produced a total of **23 videos**, of which **15** are uploaded to the project's official YouTube channel. These include:

- **One introductory and promotional video** about FIERCE, produced by VIL.
- **Six campaign videos** were created to support key project initiatives and uploaded on YouTube as 'shorts'.
- **Seven subtitled podcast videos** from the **FIERCE Dialogues** series.
- **One video** created by our UCM partners capturing moments of their second National Lab. Following participant consent, this video was also published on the FIERCE YouTube channel.
- **Eight short videos** published directly on social media platforms to capture timely moments and maximise audience engagement.

A complete table of all videos on YouTube, including titles, links and publication dates, is provided below to the table below.

Videos on YouTube	Date
FIERCE Official Presentation Video	February 2024
FIERCE 2nd Co-Creation National Lab in Spain	December 2024
International Women's Day 2024 - Our feminist claims for and Engendered Democracy!	March 2024
FIERCE campaign-Global Development, Peace and Feminist Foreign Policy.	May 2024
Reproductive Health Care Access-EU2024 FIERCE Campaign published in YouTube's Shorts	July 2024
Guarantee the protection of LGBTIQ+ Rights-EU2024 FIERCE Campaign published in YouTube's Shorts	July 2024
My Body, My Choice-EU2024 FIERCE Campaign published in YouTube's Shorts	July 2024
Protect LGBTIQ+ people-EU2024 FIERCE Campaign published in YouTube's Shorts	July 2024
Feminism from the perspective of people with disability • Denmark (Podcast)	April 2024
Reproductive Rights and Interactions with the Political System • Poland (Podcast)	July 2024
Feminist mobilizations in Italy • Italy (Podcast)	September 2024
Cybersexism and Democracy • France (Podcast)	October 2024
Anti-Racist Perspectives on Feminist Activism in Spain • Spain (Podcast)	April 2025
Legal Feminist Activism: Voices from the Field • Turkey (Podcast)	May 2025
The feminist politics of the body as pivotal to the struggle for social justice in our times • Greece (Podcast)	July 2025

Table 4: FIERCE videos on YouTube overview M7-M36

A complete table of all videos shared directly on Social Media, including titles, links and publication dates, is provided below.

Videos on Social Media	Date
Highlights of the FIERCE Kick-off meeting (presentation of WP5 - Innovative strategies and solution pathways by the EA partner)	September 2022
Highlights of the FIERCE Kick-off meeting (presentation of WP7 - Project management & Coordination by VIL)	September 2022
Highlights of the FIERCE 4th Consortium meeting in Madrid	February 2024
FIERCE Actions ready for action-FIERCE Week in Venice	November 2024
Highlights of FIERCE Week in Venice	November 2024
2nd FIERCE Transnational Lab Successfully Concluded	February 2024
Presentation of the "Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe" (by the EA partner at the launching event of the FIERCE campaign. Live Instagram video)	April 2024
FIERCE Final Conference a glimpse of the welcoming remarks by José Antonio Moreno Díaz, Member of the European Economic and Social Committee	June 2025

Table 5: FIERCE videos shared on social media M7-M36

These videos have been an essential communication and dissemination tool, enabling FIERCE to present its work in an engaging, visually compelling format. They have expanded the project's outreach, increased audience engagement across multiple platforms, and provided accessible, shareable content that supports the project's broader objectives of visibility, knowledge exchange, and advocacy for feminist and inclusive democratic practices.

2.8. Awareness and Communication Activities and Social Media Campaigns

As part of its strategic communication and dissemination efforts, FIERCE developed and implemented a series of targeted social media campaigns and awareness activities throughout the project lifecycle. These actions were designed to promote project milestones, amplify key messages, and engage a wide range of stakeholders across the academic, activist, and policy communities. Campaigns were carefully aligned with relevant international observances – such as International **Women's Day (March 8)** and the **International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (November 25)** – as well as key project outputs and public events, and were often carried out **jointly with sister projects and related initiatives**, highlighting the importance of collaboration between EU-funded projects to amplify impact and contribute meaningfully to broader conversations on gender equality.

Each campaign was supported by dedicated visuals, tailored messaging, and the strategic use of hashtags and partner tagging to maximise reach and visibility. But FIERCE's social media presence was not limited to promotion. It also played a role in coalition-building, intersectional engagement, and fostering a sense of community among gender equality advocates across Europe. Campaigns were coordinated across platforms and often amplified through resharing by consortium partners, sister projects, and relevant institutions.

In addition to these awareness-raising activities, this section also presents the project's flagship political communication campaign: **"Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe."** Co-designed by FIERCE partners together with feminist activists and organisations participating in the **FIERCE Transnational Feminist Lab**, the campaign was directed at candidates running in the **2024 European Parliament elections**. It aimed to promote pivotal feminist claims and urge prospective Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) to commit to integrating gender equality in the EU legislative agenda. The campaign reflected FIERCE's ambition to bridge research, activism, and policymaking – and to hold political actors accountable to feminist demands.

2.8.1. Campaigns for International Awareness Days

FIERCE actively engaged with a range of international observances and awareness days that directly aligned with the project's research focus on gender-based violence (GBV), women's and LGBTQI+ rights, anti-gender backlash, and feminist democratic innovation. These campaigns amplified FIERCE's key themes by linking academic research with public-facing advocacy, and by engaging broader audiences in critical conversations around gender justice in Europe and beyond.

Campaigns were either independently developed by the project or carried out in close collaboration with sister projects to maximise outreach and collective visibility. The content shared across platforms included original messaging, coordinated visual assets, curated blog posts, and selected reposts from trusted feminist and institutional sources.

Throughout the project’s lifetime, **six social media campaigns for International Awareness Days** were carried out, most of them in collaboration with sister projects (March 2023, November 2023, March 2024 and 2025 and November 2024). For this report, the focus is on the campaigns implemented from **February 2024 (M18) onwards**, which reflect FIERCE’s continued commitment to amplifying feminist voices and strengthening collaboration across EU-funded initiatives.

International Women’s Day (March 8, 2024)

In **March 2024 (M19)**, a joint campaign with FIERCE’s sister projects UNTWIST and Push Back Lash was launched under the theme **“Our Feminist Claims for an Engendered Democracy”**. The featured coordinated messaging and cross-platform sharing to increase the visibility of feminist priorities in policy and democratic participation.

Inspired by women's demands and feminist struggles across key areas of gender equality, the campaign adopted the slogan *“Engendering Democracy”* and centred around a short, visually impactful social media video. The video presented a series of feminist claims for gender equality, set to dynamic music and designed for fast-paced engagement across platforms.

The visuals prominently featured the logos of **FIERCE, UNTWIST, and Push*Back*Lash**, reflecting the collaboration between the three projects and their shared vision for feminist transformation in Europe. A template was created by VIL and sent to the communication managers of the sister projects to be used accordingly. Moreover, to build anticipation, a teaser visual (Figure 23) was released the day before the campaign launch.

Figure 23: International Women’s Day 2024_social media teaser

The final campaign video showcased **12 feminist claims for gender equality** (Figure 24) and was published across all project channels: **Facebook, Instagram, X, LinkedIn (N/A due to platform’s restrictions), YouTube**, and the **FIERCE website**.

Figure 24: International Women's Day 2024_13 feminist claims

The idea of this campaign is to document and present a broad spectrum of urgent issues of gender equality that, when addressed collectively, contribute to building a more inclusive and engendered democracy. Those claims were:

1. **Equal Representation** - Ensure diverse voices and perspectives in decision-making.
2. **Reproductive Rights** - Safeguard and promote reproductive rights, including access to healthcare, contraception, and the right to make choices about one's body.
3. **Address Gender Based Violence** - Combat all forms of violence against women, including domestic violence, harassment, and human trafficking.
4. **Political Participation** - Encourage and facilitate women's active participation in political processes
5. **Intersectionality** - Acknowledge and address gender with other aspects of identity, including race, ethnicity, sexuality, and class.
6. **Public Healthcare Access** - Guarantee access to public healthcare services for all women, addressing women's specific health needs and eliminating barriers to healthcare.
7. **Protect LGBTQIA rights** - Ensure LGBTQIA rights are incorporated by EU anti-discrimination law
8. **Challenge gender norms** - Transformative social and cultural change to challenge gender norms and stereotypes. Promote a more inclusive and equitable society.
9. **Gender Pay Equity** - Ensure that women receive equal pay for equal work across all industries and professions.
10. **Education Equality** - Foster an environment that encourages girls and women to pursue education at all levels.
11. **Workplace Equality** - Inclusive workplace policies, promoting equal opportunities, and eliminating discrimination based on gender.
12. **Address sexism from a minority perspective** - Include minority perspectives such as ethnic and sexual minorities as well as people with disabilities in the political work against sexism and gender-based violence

International Women's Day (March 8, 2025)

To mark the **International Day for Women’s Rights 2025 (March 8)**, FIERCE launched a powerful call to action under the theme **“Stronger Together, Always FIERCE!”** This campaign was not only a moment of visibility, but also a strategic invitation to feminist collectives, organisations, and individual activists to **join the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network**, created within the project.

Figure 25: International Women’s Day 2025_Join the FIERCE Feminist Transnational Network

The campaign focused on the escalating global threats posed by **anti-gender movements**, highlighting recent developments in Europe, the Americas, and beyond. From abortion bans and criminalisation of LGBTQI+ rights to disinformation campaigns and online hate speech, the campaign framed these attacks as part of a **coordinated, transnational backlash** against gender justice, democracy, and human rights.

Through a strong political message and a widely disseminated social media campaign, FIERCE presented the **Transnational Feminist Network** as a space for collective resistance and solidarity. The Network, developed as part of the FIERCE Transnational Lab, provides a platform for sharing ideas, struggles, strategies, and resources among feminist activists and organisations across Europe and beyond. It hosts **online discussions, workshops, and training sessions**, supporting feminist mobilisation against anti-gender backlash.

The campaign highlighted the **FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe** with the following demands to be for immediate action:

- Strengthen and fund feminist networks defending human rights and intersectional justice
- Expose and dismantle anti-gender actors infiltrating European institutions
- Combat online hate speech and disinformation that silence feminist voices
- Enforce gender equality laws with concrete action, not symbolic promises

The call to action concluded with an open invitation for feminist collectives and activists to **join the network**, reinforcing the project’s commitment to community building, transnational solidarity, and the sustainability of feminist resistance.

The campaign was published across all project channels: [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [X](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [website](#)

International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (November 25, 2024)

In November 2024, FIERCE initiated a joint campaign with sister projects CCINDLE, UNTWIST, and PushBackLash under the shared banner "Our FIERCE Claims for Tackling SGBV in Europe." This coordinated effort aimed to amplify feminist policy demands, spotlight structural gaps in addressing Sexual and Gender-Based Violence (SGBV) and strengthen transnational solidarity among EU-funded projects working for gender justice.

The sister projects that accepted FIERCE's proposal for a shared campaign were tagged in the posts and invited to re-share and re-post the campaign on their own social media.

Figure 26: Social media intro text for the campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women -November 2024

The campaign was rooted in the recognition that, although the EU Directive on Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence represents a significant milestone, further action is urgently needed to ensure meaningful implementation across Member States. FIERCE emphasised the need to address the intersectional dimensions of violence. Running from November 25 to 29, the campaign featured a coordinated series of visual posts across FIERCE's social media channels, presenting key feminist claims for more effective and inclusive responses to SGBV in Europe.

The figures below showcase the tailored posters created for the campaign.

Figure 27: Social media visuals for the campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women - November 2024 - 1

Figure 28: Social media visuals for the campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women - November 2024 – 2

To further enhance the campaign’s impact, FIERCE invited project partners to contribute a series of **original blog posts** addressing national and international dimensions of SGBV. Four powerful articles were published and widely disseminated across platforms during the campaign week:

- [*Feminist Data Exposes the Structural Roots of Femicide in Greece*](#)
- [*The Reality of Intimate Partner Murders in Slovenia: Breaking Down Misconceptions*](#)
- [*Feminism Reshaping Spain’s Fight Against Gender Violence: Progress and Challenges*](#)
- [*Child Marriage and Female Genital Mutilation: Addressing Global Challenges*](#)

The blog posts were published the following days of November 25th on project’s social media.

This multi-channel, multi-voice campaign reflected FIERCE’s commitment to translating research-based knowledge and policy recommendations into accessible, public-facing communication. Drawing directly from the project’s findings on SGBV, gender backlash, and intersectional inequalities, the campaign helped raise awareness of the structural nature of violence and the urgent need for inclusive and feminist-informed policy responses across Europe.

Transgender Day of Remembrance (November 20, 2024)

In **November 2024**, FIERCE joined a joint awareness action initiated by the **CCINDLE project** to mark the **Transgender Day of Remembrance** – a day dedicated to honouring the memory of trans individuals lost to anti-trans violence around the world. The campaign, also supported by sister projects **RESIST** and **UNTWIST**, drew attention to the increasing mainstreaming of **transphobia across Europe**, often intersecting with broader anti-democratic and anti-gender agendas – themes central to FIERCE’s research.

As part of the campaign, FIERCE contributed by sharing a recent report by the [**European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights \(FRA\)**](#) highlighting rising levels of **harassment and violence against LGBTIQ+ individuals** across EU Member States. The report shed light on persistent inequalities in access to safety, healthcare and legal protection for LGBTIQ+ people, reinforcing the urgency of addressing transphobia as a systemic human rights issue.

Figure 29: Social media posts for the campaign on the 25th Transgender Day of Remembrance

This campaign formed part of FIERCE’s commitment to raising awareness on gender-based violence in all its forms, while contributing to a shared effort across Horizon Europe projects to promote inclusive, feminist-informed responses to social injustice.

2.8.2. Awareness Activities and Communication Support for Project Actions

In addition to dedicated social media campaigns, the FIERCE communication strategy played an active role in supporting, amplifying, and enhancing the visibility of key activities implemented under various project Work Packages (WPs). Communication did not operate in isolation; rather, it was fully embedded across the project’s structure – interacting closely with the research, co-creation, and policy engagement strands of FIERCE.

This section highlights a range of activities - implemented during the reporting period - that were not designed as standalone campaigns, but nevertheless involved **significant communication and outreach components**, contributing to stakeholder engagement and the project’s public impact. These include: the **Open Call for FIERCE Actions**, where feminist organisations were invited to apply for funding to implement grassroots initiatives; the **FIERCE Week in Venice**, which served as a high-profile, multi-stakeholder event; the **FIERCE online Feminist Course**, and a series of **online gatherings** organised within the **FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network**, which brought together activists and researchers in facilitated virtual spaces.

Additionally, this section outlines the **extensive communication work surrounding the FIERCE Final Conference** – including the development of branded materials, social media coordination, live updates, newsletters, and the management of the dedicated event webpage – all of which ensured high visibility and engagement before, during, and after the conference.

Communication support for the Open Call - FIERCE Actions: “Empowering Feminist Movements in Europe”

As part of its participatory action-research methodology, FIERCE launched an **Open Call for Applications** to support the implementation of **FIERCE Actions** – grassroots initiatives aimed at responding to the rise and influence of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors across Europe (see section 3.5.2). These actions were directly linked to the project’s core research themes, including labour market inequalities, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQIA+ rights, migration, and gender-based violence. The Open Call aimed to fund 1-2 actions per country in each of the FIERCE research contexts (Greece, Denmark, Italy, Spain, France, Poland, Slovenia, and Turkey), resulting in a total of **11 supported FIERCE Actions**. The selected initiatives reflected a diversity of formats, including campaign efforts countering anti-gender rhetoric, artistic and cultural interventions, feminist assemblies and encounters, participatory democracy experiments, and grassroots activities engaging underrepresented groups in political processes.

To support **the visibility and outreach of the Open Call**, a coordinated communication effort was launched across multiple channels to ensure broad dissemination among feminist collectives, civil society organisations, and grassroots actors across the FIERCE countries.

A series of targeted social media posts were developed and published across platforms, providing accessible information on the objectives of the Open Call, eligibility criteria, and application process. The campaign included **initial announcement posts** as well as **follow-up reminders** – such as countdown messages (e.g., “*Only 14 days remaining to apply*”) and updates during the evaluation phase (e.g., “*The Selection Committee has important decisions ahead*”). These posts were designed to maintain momentum and visibility throughout the application period and were accompanied by a **dedicated visual identity** to ensure consistency and recognisability. (See Figure below).

Figure 30: Poster for the FIERCE Actions OPEN CALL

Figure 31: Social media posts for the FIERCE Actions OPEN CALL

In addition, a [news item](#) was published on the FIERCE website, featuring all essential information about the call, including links to the official guidelines and application form. The call was also prominently featured in a dedicated issue of the [FIERCE newsletter](#), sent to the project's mailing list and partner networks to further maximise outreach.

This communication effort contributed to attracting a strong pool of applicants across the eight project countries, ensuring diversity in proposed activities and alignment with the project's feminist and intersectional values.

Communication support for FIERCE Week in Venice

The **FIERCE Week 2024**, held from **November 4th to 7th** in the historic city of **Venice**, was a landmark closed-door event that brought together over **50 participants**, including feminist activists from eight European countries, researchers, members of the **FIERCE Advisory Board**, and representatives from sister projects (More at section 2.12 FIERCE Week in Venice). Structured into three interrelated and dynamic segments – the **Third Transnational Lab**, the **FIERCE Winter School**, and the **launch of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network** – the event fostered rich dialogue, critical reflection, and future-facing discussions.

Due to the **targeted and closed nature** of the event, no public-facing social media campaign or promotional communication activities were carried out in advance. However, **dedicated communication support was provided during the event**, coordinated by the WP6 leader (VIL), in collaboration with the WP4 leader (SV).

- **Participant Presentation Booklet**

One of the core communication tools was a 29 pages **participant presentation booklet**, designed to reflect the diversity of the FIERCE community and strengthen connections among participants. This internal-use booklet featured names, short bios, photos, contact information, and organisational logos of all participants – grouped into categories including FIERCE partners, Advisory Board members, National Lab participants, FIERCE Actions carriers from feminist collectives and EU organisations.

The collection of participant information was managed by SV, with VIL overseeing design and layout. The booklet began with a welcome note and concluded with a list of project contact points. It was circulated in advance of the meeting to support engagement and informal networking throughout the week. Relevant screenshots are displayed below.

Figure 32: Screenshots from the Presentation Booklet – FIERCE Week

- **Event Posters Showcasing the FIERCE Actions**

To support the **Third Transnational Lab**, the **FIERCE Winter School**, and the **launch of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network**, a series of 19 large-format posters were created to visually present the scope and impact of the **FIERCE Actions** - including both those developed through the National Labs and those selected through the Open Call. These posters were showcased at the **event venue** throughout the FIERCE Week.

The posters were designed and produced by the WP6 leader (VIL), with input and support from SV and EA, and printed in A2 format. Each one aligned with the FIERCE branding and colour palette to ensure visual consistency and recognisability.

Two types of posters were displayed:

- **National Lab FIERCE Actions Posters:** These included the action theme, key outcomes, implementation status, and a list of participating organisations and feminist movements.
- **Open Call FIERCE Actions Posters:** These highlighted the leading organisation or collective, a short description of the action, the applied democratic innovation approach, and the timeline for implementation.

Together, the posters offered a powerful visual overview of the diversity, creativity, and democratic ambition of the FIERCE Actions across Europe. See Figures below for selected examples.

Figure 33: Selection of Posters – FIERCE Actions National Labs_ FIERCE Week

Figure 34: Selection of Posters – FIERCE Actions OPEN CALL_ FIERCE Week

• Communication Support During the FIERCE Week

During the FIERCE Week, real-time communication activities were carried out to increase visibility and engagement. These included:

- Publishing a series of social media posts across all platforms and [stories](#) on Facebook and Instagram.
- Sharing [reels and short videos](#) capturing key moments from the event.
- Posting live updates and photos to highlight the vibrant exchanges among participants. (See screenshot below.)

Figure 35: A screenshot of a social media post during the FIERCE week

- Publish a general social media post across all project's platforms addressed to EU Commissioners and broader institutional audiences, focusing on the intersection of gender equality and democracy. (See screenshot below.)

Figure 36: Social media post addressed to EU Commissioners

These actions not only documented the week’s atmosphere but also allowed a broader audience to engage with the event remotely, despite its closed format.

- **Communication after the FIERCE Week**

Following the FIERCE Week, post-event communication focused on consolidating outcomes and broadening their reach:

A dedicated website article was published, summarising the goals, structure, and impact of the week:

[“FIERCE Week in Venice Brings Together Feminist Activists, Local and EU Gender Equality Organizations, and Academia”](#)

Selected highlights and reflections from FIERCE Week were included in the [December 2024 edition of the FIERCE newsletter](#), dedicated to showcasing the project’s most important milestones of the year.

Together, these actions ensured that the impact of FIERCE Week extended well beyond its four-day programme, contributing to the project’s outreach and sustainability objectives.

Figure 37: A photo collage created for the post communication of the FIERCE Week

Communication support for the [FIERCE Feminist Online Course](#)

The FIERCE Course [“Learning Intersectional Feminism in Context: A Course on Strategies and Alliances in Times of Anti-Gender and Far-Right Movements”](#) - launched in **June 2025** - is a **free, open-access learning programme** designed in response to the growing influence of anti-gender and anti-feminist politics across Europe and beyond. The course equips participants with the tools to understand, critically reflect on, and counter these developments through **intersectional** and **transnational** feminist strategies.

Drawing on FIERCE’s research findings and co-creation processes with feminist organisations, the course integrates **academic knowledge** with **activist experience**. It features lectures by leading gender and political studies scholars alongside first-hand insights from feminist activists, addressing current political dynamics, sharing resistance strategies, and envisioning collective feminist futures.

Communication support for the launch was led by the WP6 leader (VIL) in collaboration with the WP4 leader (SV) and included:

- Creation of a [dedicated page on the FIERCE website](#) with detailed course information. (See screenshot below)

Figure 38: A screenshot from the FIERCE Course dedicated page on website

- Design of a **course poster in different dimensions**, used across the website and social media, which served as the course’s visual branding. (See figures below.)

Figure 39: Social media Poster for the FIERCE Course

- Development of a [Press Release](#) announcing the launch.
- Inclusion of a feature article in the [FIERCE newsletter](#) sent to the project mailing list and partner networks.
- A series of **targeted social media posts** introducing the course, its structure, and its target audience.

Figure 40: Screenshot of the social media caption for the Online Course

Communication support for the online Transnational Feminist Network events

The **FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network** was launched during the FIERCE Week in Venice (4–7 November 2024) and subsequently held three online meetings (February, April, and May 2025) and a final in-person gathering in Brussels on 19 June 2025 (More at section 2.12 Events organized by FIERCE) Throughout these milestones, WP6 provided targeted communication support to promote participation, share outcomes, and strengthen the visibility of the Transnational Feminist Network across the project's channels.

This included the design and dissemination of dedicated visuals, publication of [announcements and summaries on the FIERCE website](#), targeted **social media posts** (see Figure 43), [newsletter features](#) and a [press release](#) highlighting the launch of the Network fostering cross-border feminist collaboration. These actions ensured consistent messaging and engagement throughout the **Transnational Feminist Network's** activities.

See Section 3.5.8 for a full description of the Transnational Feminist network's structure, participants, and sustainability potential.

Figure 41: Poster for the 2nd online meeting by EA

Figure 42: Screenshot of the social media post-communication of the 1st online meeting

2.9. “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe” – Flagship Political Campaign

The “[Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe](#)” campaign was a flagship political communication initiative of the FIERCE project, launched in the run-up to the 2024 European Parliament elections. It emerged directly from the co-creation work of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Lab, where feminist activists, organisations, and researchers jointly identified priority political demands for the upcoming legislative term.

The campaign aimed to place feminist and intersectional perspectives at the centre of the European political debate, while urging prospective Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) to commit to accountability towards feminist movements and gender scholars.

The Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe are:

- A Recognised European Feminist Network to Stop the Anti-Gender and Anti-Feminist Movement
- Social, Economic, and Reproductive Justice
- Fighting Against Sexual and Gender-Based Violence (SGBV)
- Protecting LGBTIQ+ Rights
- Global Development, Peace, and a Feminist Foreign Policy

Campaign Structure and Strands

The campaign was structured around three main strands:

- **Strand 1 – Signing the FIERCE Charter (Targeting EP Candidates)**

Over 650 EP candidates were contacted and invited to endorse the campaign and sign the [FIERCE charter](#). A total of 70 candidates from 11 countries supported the claims: **Belgium (7), Czech Republic (1), Denmark (8), Spain (2), Finland (3), France (24), Greece (3), Italy (11), Luxembourg (1), Netherlands (1), and Slovenia (9)**.

Of these, **14 candidates** were successfully elected to the European Parliament, with one joining the FEMM Committee. (see figure below)

Name	Country	National party	Group in the EUP
Per Clausen	Denmark	Enhedlisten - De Rød-Gronne	GUE
Li Andersson	Finland	Vasemmistoliitto	GUE
Madjouline Sbai	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
Mounir Satouri	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
Melissa Camara	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
David Cormand	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
Marie Toussaint	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
Raphael Glucksmann	France	Place Publique	S&D
Aurore Lalucq	France	Place Publique	S&D
Aodhan O Riordain	Ireland	Labour Party	S&D
Marc Angel	Luxembourg	Letzebuerger Sozialistesche Aarbechterpartei	S&D
Kim Van Sparrentak	Netherlands	GroenLinks	Greens/EFA
Vladimir Prebilic	Slovenia	Vesna	Greens/EFA
Matjaz Nemeč	Slovenia	Socialni Demokrati	S&D

Figure 43: The elected EP candidates who endorsed the FIERCE campaign

- **Strand 2 – Partnering the Campaign (Engaging Feminist Organisations)**

Feminist collectives from and beyond the Transnational Lab were invited to partner with the campaign. **15 organisations** joined as official partners, including EU-level actors such as **WIDE+, Gender Five Plus, ERRC, IPAS, and national organisations such as Women’s Lobby of Slovenia, Hands Away (France), Rainbow School (Greece), and International Women Space – IWS** (Germany).**

- **Strand 3 – Campaigning in Social Media, Newsletters, and Advertisements**

FIERCE allocated a dedicated budget and following an open call, contracted a communication agency to design and implement the campaign. Working in close collaboration with the WP6 leader (VIL), WP4 team (SV), and WP4 team (EA), the agency developed the campaign’s visual identity, prepared all graphic materials, and managed the paid social media content.

The campaign’s public outreach efforts faced significant challenges due to Meta’s security policy for the European Parliament elections, which imposed strict limitations on the dissemination of political content in sponsored posts. According to the policy, such content had to be published by a verified user physically located in the target country - an unfeasible condition for the communications team, based in Moldova. This limitation prevented paid posting on Instagram and Facebook, leaving LinkedIn as the only viable paid channel.

Despite these constraints, the campaign achieved substantial organic and paid reach:

- **LinkedIn:** 160,200 impressions and 74 new followers (total: 426 – M22)
- **Facebook:** 13,102 impressions and 40 new followers (total: 275 - M22)
- **Instagram:** 67,269 impressions and 130 new followers (total: 338 - M22)
- **Website traffic:** 4,869 clicks from social media platforms to the campaign website

Paid media placements further amplified the message in European high profile News Outlets:

- **El Salto** (Spain): 154,851 impressions, 1,134 clicks, 0.7% CTR (See figures 45-46)
- **Politico:** 160,000 impressions, 67 clicks, 0.04% CTR (See figures 47-48)

Overall, the campaign generated **240,571 total impressions⁵** and **6,070 clicks**, resulting in an average **CTR⁶ of 2.5%** - above industry benchmarks, indicating strong audience engagement and message resonance.

The content mix included:

- Short videos from feminist influencers and activists on the claims of: [Global Development, Peace and Feminist Foreign Policy, Guarantee the protection of LGBTIQ+ Rights, Reproductive Health Care Access, Reproductive justice – My Voice My Choice, Protect LGBTIQ+ people](#) (See Figure 49)

⁵ **Impressions:** A metric that indicates the number of times a piece of content (such as an advertisement, social media post, or webpage) is displayed to users, regardless of whether it is clicked. Impressions measure visibility, not engagement, and are often used alongside metrics like CTR to assess campaign performance. [Google Ads Help – About impressions](#)

⁶ **CTR (Click-Through Rate):** A metric used in digital marketing to measure the percentage of users who click on a specific link or advertisement after seeing it. CTR is calculated by dividing the number of clicks by the number of impressions (times the content was viewed) and multiplying by 100. A higher CTR generally indicates that the content is relevant and engaging to its audience. [Google Ads Help – About CTR](#)

- Advertisements in *El Salto* and *Politico*, and a feature article in the Italian feminist magazine *Rivista InGenere*. (Figures 45-46)
- A series of **organic posts** featuring the **five feminist claims** was shared across all FIERCE platforms (see Figures 50-51), each accompanied by visually engaging graphics designed in line with the project's branding. These posts aimed to communicate the claims in an accessible, shareable format, fostering broad engagement among followers and partners. (See in Annex 3 the social media campaign posters for paid and organic posts.)

“Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe” Campaign – Online Events

The “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe” campaign was supported **by two major online events** that amplified its visibility and deepened engagement with key stakeholders. For both events, comprehensive communication efforts were undertaken, including the development of dedicated [press releases](#), [newsletter issues](#) disseminated to the FIERCE mailing list, and targeted **social media posts**.

- **Launching Event – April 26, 2024**

This event officially launched the campaign and invited political candidates to the 2024 European Parliament elections to share their views and proposals on the campaign's central themes. Members of feminist organisations also participated as discussants, enriching the dialogue with diverse feminist perspectives.

- **Pre-Electoral Event – June 4, 2024**

Held just days before the EP elections, this event once again brought together political candidates and representatives from feminist organisations to reflect on the campaign's key claims and share their final messages.

Both events were accompanied by consistent and strategic communication across channels to maximise outreach and engagement. (see more in section 2.12 Events Organised by FIERCE)

Significance and Impact

This campaign represented the integration of research-based feminist claims into electoral advocacy and policymaking. It connected FIERCE's academic and activist outputs to concrete political commitments, secured visible endorsements from candidates and organisations, and extended the project's reach through partnerships and targeted media presence. Despite technical challenges in social media promotion, the campaign succeeded in positioning feminist priorities within the public debate leading to the 2024 European elections.

Figure 44: Paid banners on El Salto

Figure 45: Analytics for paid banners on El Salto

Figure 46: Paid banners on Politico

Figure 47: Analytics for paid banner on Politico

Figure 48: Screenshots of short campaign videos

Figure 49: Screenshots of selected social media posts – Organic 1

Figure 50: Screenshots of selected social media posts – Organic 2

2.10. Final Conference

The FIERCE Final Conference, held in Brussels in June 2025, at the European Economic and Social Committee, attracting approximately **200 participants** (both online and onsite) was one of the project's most significant public events. WP6 led a comprehensive communication plan to ensure high visibility, clear messaging, and wide stakeholder engagement before, during, and after the conference.

Pre-event communication included:

- Creation of a **dedicated page** on the FIERCE website with the programme, speaker bios, and logistical information.
- Development of **graphic designs** for online promotion, including save-the-date visuals, banners, and panel-specific graphics featuring speakers and a series of **social media posts** announcing the event and opening registration (See Annex 4)
- Design and dissemination of a **newsletter** and **press release** to announce the conference and invite registrations.
- Coordination of partners for resharing content and amplifying reach to their networks.

Event branding and materials:

- Creation of branded **merchandise** for participants, including coasters, bookmarks and stickers both designed in line with the project's visual identity. (See Annex 4)
- Preparation of **name tags** for all participants, using the conference branding for a professional and cohesive look. (See Annex 4)

Communication during the event:

- **Live social media posting** on all platforms, sharing real-time updates, photos, promotion of key discussions and panel highlights throughout the day to maintain high online visibility and encourage interaction both with the onsite participants and the online audience. (See Annex 4 for selected examples.)

Post-event communication included:

- A **press release** summarising the conference highlights, speakers, and key messages.
- Website update of the dedicated conference page with selected photos and event highlights.
- Social media wrap-up posts, thanking participants, partners, and hosts

Through these activities, WP6 ensured that the Final Conference was consistently branded, well-publicised, and effectively documented, maximising its visibility and impact both within and beyond the project's immediate network.

Figure 51: Example of banner announcing the final conference

2.11. FIERCE Publications

Throughout the project, FIERCE partners have produced a number of scientific and policy-oriented publications that contribute to advancing knowledge on feminist movements, gender equality, anti-gender backlash etc. All FIERCE publications are openly accessible via the project website under the “[Publications](#)” subpage, at the ZENODO Community and at the [Genport](#). The following table provides an overview of these publications and their key details.

No	FIERCE Publications
1	Altan Olcay, Ö., & Alniaçık, A. (2023). Advocacy in the face of government backlash: Feminist movements in Turkey and new avenues of research in redemocratization. Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/69424
2	Barone, A., Bonu Rosenkranz, G., Markelj, L., & Smrdelj, R. (2025). Feminist responses to anti-abortion attacks in Italy and Slovenia: Building democratic innovations in contexts of de-democratization. <i>Interdisciplinary Political Studies</i> , 11(1). https://doi.org/10.1285/i20398573v11n1p129
3	Bonu Rosenkranz, G., & della Porta, D. (2023). Gendering democracy: The new wave of feminist mobilization in Italy (2010–2021). Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/69423
4	Caumes, L., & Pruvot, S. (2023). From alterfeminism to femellisme: The rise of anti-feminist mobilisations against “neofeminism” in France in the last decade (2011–2023). Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/69435
5	Gregersen, A. B., Meret, S., & Rolandsen Agustin, L. (2023). The gender exceptionalism backlash? Rise and development of the contemporary anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in Denmark. Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/69434
6	Grammatikopoulou, C. (2025). Feminist networks of care in Greece: Practices of resistance from the streets to the screens. <i>Digital Geography and Society</i> , 8, Article 100113. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666378325000029
7	Kioupkiolis, A., & Grammatikopoulou, C. (2025). Antifeminist regress in Greece today: The politics of ‘active dads’ and ‘fertility’ campaigns. <i>Redescriptions: Political Thought, Conceptual History and Feminist Theory</i> , 28(1), 40–62. https://journal-redescriptions.org/articles/10.33134/rds.474
8	Kioupkiolis, A., & Karydou, K. (2023). Feminist agency for dismantling patriarchy and violence in Greek society. Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/71431
9	Muszel, M. (2023). Ideological foundation of the contemporary anti-gender movements in Poland. <i>Miscellanea Anthropologica et Sociologica</i> , 3(2). https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/69425
10	Smrdelj, R., Kuhar, R., & Kalin Golob, M. (2023). Anti-gender discursive “legacy”: Framing gender debate by opposing “gender theory”. In <i>ESARN23 Abstract Book</i> . https://esarn23.files.wordpress.com/2023/09/abstract_book_esarn23-1.pdf
11	Smrdelj, R., Kuhar, R., & Kalin Golob, M. (2023, October 19–21). Teorija spola kot prevladujoč okvir javne razprave o spolu in spolnosti: Diskurzivna dediščina antigenderskega gibanja. In R. Kuhar, M. Sedmak, & I. Jurekovič (Eds.), <i>Dolgoživa družba: Posledice in izzivi: Slovensko sociološko srečanje</i> , Koper, 19–21 October 2023 (p. 74). Slovensko sociološko društvo.

No	FIERCE Publications
12	Kuhar, R., & Smrdelj, R. (2023, September 4–8). Anti-gender movement in Slovenia: Between fighting marriage equality and strengthening LGBT+ community. In ECPR General Conference: Charles University, 4–8 September 2023. European Consortium for Political Research. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/71814
13	Oder, B. E., & Eskitascioglu, İ. (2025). Anti-gender policies, feminist advocacy, and democratic struggle: Turkey as a case study. Paper presented at the ICON-S Annual Conference: At the crossroads of public law: Equality, climate emergency, and democracy in the digital era. International Society of Public Law. https://www.icon-society.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/BOOKLET-2025-Final.pdf
14	Smrdelj, R., Kuhar, R., (2024). Neoconservative opposition to the politics of equality: the anti-gender movement in Slovenia. Social science forum, 40(105/106), pp. 17–41. https://www.sociolosko-drustvo.si/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/DR105-106-Smrdelj-Kuhar.pdf
15	Pajnik, M., Kuhar, R., Smrdelj, R. (2025) "Gender ideology" as a frame repertoire: transversal instrumentalization of gender equality. Submitted to Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research.
16	Bonu Rosenkranz, G., & della Porta, D. (2025) "Disentangling intersectionality in action. The new cycle of contention of feminist movements in Italy". In European Journal of Politics and Gender. Article accepted.
17	Smrdelj, R., Kuhar, R., & Učakar, T. (2025, June 13–14). <i>Who speaks louder? Network analysis of intimate citizenship debates in Slovenian mass media</i> . In M. Vesković Anđelković & M. Urošević (Eds.), <i>Conference New divisions, struggles, and solidarities in South East Europe, Belgrade, 13–14 June 2025</i> (pp. 50–51). Sociological Scientific Society of Serbia. https://snds.rs/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/New-Divisions-Struggles-and-Solidarities-in-SEE-2025-Book-of-Abstracts.pdf
18	Markelj, L., Barone, A., Bonu Rosenkranz, G., & Smrdelj, R. (2025, May 20–23). Feminist responses to anti-abortion attacks: Building democratic innovations in informal fields. In Gendering democratic resilience: ECPR joint sessions of workshops, Prague, Charles University, 20–23 May 2025. European Consortium for Political Research. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/78896
19	Smrdelj, R., & Kuhar, R. (2025, May 20–23). From direct action to productive resistance: Feminist and LGBT+ responses to anti-gender mobilizations in Europe. In Joint Sessions of Workshops: Charles University, 20–23 May 2025. European Consortium for Political Research. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/78498
20	Smrdelj, R., & Kuhar, R. (2025). Productive resistance: Feminist and LGBT+ responses to anti-gender mobilizations. In <i>Knowing justice in the anthropocene: Book of abstracts</i> (pp. 925–926). International Sociological Association. https://www.isa-sociology.org/uploads/imagen/2252-5th-isa-forum-of-sociology-abstracts-book.pdf
21	Kuhar, R., Smrdelj, R., & Kalin Golob, M. (2024, September 24–27). <i>Still a debate or just an echo chamber effect? Gender theory in Slovenian Twitter discussion</i> . In <i>ECREA 2024: Communication & social (dis)order: Book of abstracts: 10th European Communication Conference, University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences, 24–27 September 2024</i> (p. 348). CZECH-IN. https://ecrea2024ljublana.eu

No	FIERCE Publications
22	Kuhar, R., Smrdelj, R., & Kalin Golob, M. (2024, August 27–30). Expanding boundaries: Gender theory/ideology and Twitter debate on gender-sensitive language. In ESA'24 Porto: 16th conference, 27–30 August 2024, Porto, Portugal: Tension, trust and transformation (p. 1028). European Sociological Association. https://www.europeansociology.org/media/e68213f0-f856-4c07-9288-301b2d153fd0
23	Smrdelj, R. (2024, July 8–10). <i>Practising counter-strategies: Resisting the anti-gender backlash in Slovenia</i> . In <i>European Conference on Politics and Gender (ECPG), Ghent University, 8–10 July 2024</i> . European Consortium for Political Research. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/73957
24	Kuhar, R., & Pajnik, M. (2024, July 8–10). <i>Re-nationalizing citizenship and democratic backsliding: Anti-gender movements in Central-Eastern Europe</i> . In <i>European Conference on Politics and Gender (ECPG), Ghent University, 8–10 July 2024</i> . European Consortium for Political Research. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/74202
25	Smrdelj, R., Kuhar, R., & Kalin Golob, M. (2025). Expanding boundaries: “Gender theory” and the Twitter (X) debate on gender-sensitive language use in Slovenia. <i>Intersections. East European Journal of Society and Politics</i> . Manuscript submitted for publication.
26	Markelj, L., Pajnik, M. & Humer, Ž. (2024). Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse: shifting the human rights frame through affect. Paper presented at the ECPR General Conference, Dublin, 12-15 August 2024. https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/77577
27	Pajnik, M., Markelj, L. & Humer, Ž. (2024). Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse: shifting the human rights frame through affect. Paper presented at ESA conference, 27-30 Aug. 2024, Porto. https://www.europeansociology.org/media/e68213f0-f856-4c07-9288-301b2d153fd0
28	Markelj, L., Pajnik, M. & Humer, Ž. (2024). Framing abortion discourse through affect: Anti-gender appropriation of feminist human rights frame. Paper presented at SISP (Societa Italiana di Scienza Politica) conference, Trieste, 12.-14. September 2024. https://www.sisp.it/convegno2024/?pagename=cms&name=sessiontracks&trackname=gender--sexuality--and-intersectionality-in-politics
29	Pajnik, M., Kuhar, R., Smrdelj, R. (2025) “Gender Ideology” as the Master Frame: Transversal Instrumentalization of Equality Politics by Mechanisms of Regularity. Article submitted to <i>Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research</i> , waiting final confirmation of acceptance after positive reviewer's feedback.

Table 6: Publications overview by M36

2.12. Events organized by FIERCE

Throughout its duration, FIERCE has organised a diverse range of external, open, and outreach events designed to amplify the project's messages, strengthen collaborations, and engage stakeholders from across Europe and beyond. These events have served as key moments to share research findings, present project results, support partner-led actions, and create spaces for dialogue between activists, policymakers, researchers, and the public.

From participation in high-profile gender equality festivals and the hosting of online roundtables, to the organisation of the targeted **FIERCE campaign** events, large-scale gatherings such as the **FIERCE Week in Venice** and the establishment of the **Transnational Feminist Network**, each occasion has contributed to the project's visibility, impact, and legacy.

The reporting period culminated in the **FIERCE Final Conference** at the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) in Brussels – a landmark closing event that brought together partners, EU institutions, feminist organisations, and academics to present FIERCE's results, celebrate its achievements, and outline its legacy for advancing feminist and intersectional democracy across Europe.

During the previous reporting period (M7-M18), FIERCE organised two external open and outreach events: [FIERCE at the gender equality festival "Talk Town"](#) (Date: 24 November 2023 (M15) | Location: Copenhagen, Denmark | Partner: AAU) and [1st FIERCE Online Roundtable Discussion](#) (Date: 09 January 2024 (M17) | Location: Online | Partner: SV).

The following list outlines the events held during the reporting period, highlighting their scope, audiences, and thematic focus.

[Launching Event of the "Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe" Campaign](#)

Date: 26 April 2024 | **Location:** Online | **Partners:** SV, EA

Official launch of the campaign, featuring political candidates to the EP 2024 elections and feminist organisations.

This event targeted candidates running in the 2024 European Parliament elections, aiming to showcase FIERCE's key feminist claims and push for their integration into the next legislative agenda. The objective was to encourage prospective MEPs to commit to ongoing engagement and accountability towards feminist activists and gender equality scholars.

It represented the culmination of a collaborative process involving over 25 feminist activists from diverse movements across eight countries – Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey – along with representatives from European feminist networks.

During the event, invited political candidates presented their views and policy proposals on the campaign's core themes, while members of feminist organisations took part as discussants, adding depth, expertise, and lived experience to the conversation. **The event attracted 47 participants who were registered and actively participated.**

In Figure 53 below are the visuals created for the branding and promotion of the campaign launch. The presentation of the Five FIERCE Claims by our EA partner was [broadcast live on Instagram](#), allowing wider audiences to follow the event in real time.

FIERCE Campaign Launch for 2024 EP Elections

Candidates & Feminists ready for a change!

When?
April 26th
14:00 – 15:30 CET

Where?
Zoom

FIERCE
Funded by the European Union

#WeareFIERCE
NATAŠA SUKIČ
Slovenian candidate to the EP 2024 elections-Left Party
Speaker
Topic: Global Development, Peace and Feminist Foreign Policy

#WeareFIERCE
Pati Vardham
Candidate to EP Elections with MÉPA25
Member of DIEM25
Discussant

Funded by the European Union
Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission.

Figure 52: Designs for the promotion of the launching event

FIERCE Campaign Closing and Pre-Electoral Event

Date: 04 June 2024 | **Location:** Online | **Partners:** SV, EA

Pre-election dialogue between political candidates and feminist organisations to present and discuss the campaign's claims.

Held on 4 June 2024, just days before the European Parliament elections, this event brought together political candidates and representatives of European feminist organisations to discuss the dissemination of the FIERCE feminist claims and the campaign's impact. **This event attracted 66 registrants and 49 connected participants.**

Building on FIERCE's three years of research, activism, and collaboration, the event showcased the project's ongoing work and determination to advocate for gender equality, counter anti-gender narratives, and influence policymaking at the European level. By engaging directly with candidates and amplifying feminist voices, the event sought to ensure that the demands of activists and gender scholars remain at the forefront of the EU's democratic agenda.

In Figure 54 below, the visuals created for the branding and promotion of the Pre-Electoral Event are presented.

Figure 53: Designs and posts for the promotion of the pre-electoral event

The FIERCE Week

Date: 4–7 November 2024 | **Location:** Venice, Italy | **Partner:** SV, EA

Held over four days in Venice, FIERCE Week brought together activists, researchers, and allies from across Europe for an intensive programme of dialogue, learning, and strategic planning.

FIERCE Week transformed Venice into a hub of feminist collaboration and exchange, **bringing together more than 50 participants from eight European countries** – feminist activists, researchers, Advisory Board members, and representatives from sister projects. Over four days, the programme combined three major components: the Third Transnational Lab, the FIERCE Winter School, and the launch of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network.

The Winter School provided an innovative learning space rooted in feminist pedagogies, where activists and researchers engaged in mutual knowledge exchange. Sessions explored feminist responses to anti-gender backlash, intersectional mobilisations, the Istanbul Convention, and feminist action in multilateral arenas – all while challenging traditional hierarchies between academia and activism.

The Third Transnational Lab revisited the “Five Feminist Claims for a Feminist Europe” campaign, assessing its outcomes and discussing strategies for translating its proposals into concrete political and policy actions. These exchanges laid the groundwork for the establishment of the Transnational Feminist Network.

The week concluded with the official launch discussion of the Transnational Feminist Network, affirming participants’ commitment to sustained, cross-border collaboration against anti-gender movements. Taking place at a moment of significant challenges for gender equality and democratic values in Europe, FIERCE Week served as both a space for reflection and a catalyst for future collective action.

In the Figure 55 below two photo collages showcasing highlights of the FIERCE week.

Figure 54: Highlights of the FIERCE Week in Venice

FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network events

Locations: Venice, Brussels & Online | **Partner:** EA

The Transnational Feminist Network was one of FIERCE's key legacy actions, designed to sustain and expand cross-border feminist collaboration beyond the project's lifetime. It provided a structured space for activists, researchers, and policy actors to exchange knowledge, coordinate actions, and strengthen alliances against anti-gender backlash.

More than 300 people are registered in the mailing list of the Transnational Network. On average, the online meetings **attracted 35 to 40 participants**. The majority of the participants came from organisations and collectives across the FIERCE partner countries, with a high number of academics, including some younger researchers.

Below is an overview of the Transnational Feminist Network's launch and key meetings during the reporting period. For the full account of its objectives, outcomes, and sustainability strategy, see Section 3.5.8.

Launch of the Transnational Feminist Network

Date: 4–7 November 2024 | **Location:** Venice, Italy

The Transnational Feminist Network was officially launched during FIERCE Week, gathering over 50 feminist activists, researchers, Advisory Board members, and sister project representatives from eight European countries. The launch set shared objectives for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and coordinated action against anti-gender backlash.

Figure 55: Photos of the Launch of the Transnational Feminist Network in Venice

1st Online Meeting

Date: 19 February 2025 | **Location:** Online

Focused on the role of feminist activists in local struggles and coordination against anti-gender movements, the 1st Online meeting of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network attracted **more than 40 members** from organizations and collectives across the FIERCE countries, strengthening our collective effort for gender equality. Included a presentation of FIERCE research findings on

conservative influence in policy and public discourse. The meeting opened with thought-provoking presentations from the FIERCE team, setting the stage for dynamic exchanges on key priorities:

- **Defining the FIERCE Transnational Network** – Participants discussed the vision and objectives of the Network, highlighting its role as a feminist, intersectional, and transnational space for activists and organisations to share knowledge, support local struggles, and coordinate collective actions.
- **Exposing Anti-Gender Strategies and Strengthening Resistance** – Rok Smrdelj, researcher at the University of Ljubljana and FIERCE team member, presented his findings on the tactics and influence of anti-gender movements in Europe. He outlined how well-funded conservative forces are shaping public discourse, influencing policy, and weaponising social media to spread disinformation, underscoring the urgent need for stronger feminist media literacy and coordinated counterstrategies.
- **International Women’s Day – Mobilisations and Strategies** – In breakout sessions, participants exchanged ideas for feminist actions on International Women’s Day, focusing on ways to amplify collective demands. They emphasised the value of transnational coordination and increased visibility to counter the ongoing anti-feminist backlash.

2nd Online Meeting

Date: 18 April 2025 | **Location:** Online

The second Transnational Feminist Network meeting attracted approximately **40 participants** and was structured into two sessions.

- **Feminist Mobilisations Across Contexts** – Speakers from Türkiye, Serbia, and Greece shared powerful insights into current protests and the dynamics of feminist organising in their countries. Deniz (Türkiye) described the increasingly repressive political climate, where feminist and LGBTQI+ activists face systematic monitoring and criminalisation. Aleksandra (Serbia) spoke about student-led protests following two mass shootings in 2023 and how feminist students have transformed these spaces, confronting patriarchal and neoliberal violence with demands rooted in care and justice. Eirini (Greece) recounted the mass mobilisations after the Tempi train disaster, which exposed the deadly consequences of austerity, privatisation, and state neglect. Feminist and transfeminist collectives played a key role, joining the general strike under the banner: *“Our bodies know state violence. Tempi, Pylos, femicides, Palestine – we demand justice.”*
- **Workshop: Resisting Cyberviolence** – Laure Salmona from *Féministes contre le cyberharcèlement* led an engaging workshop on resisting online violence, equipping participants with strategies to identify, counter, and prevent cyber harassment targeting feminist activists and communities.

3rd Online Meeting

Date: 27 May 2025 | Online

The third meeting brought together speakers from Georgia, Hungary, Romania, and the initiative *Against Conversion Therapy* (ACT) for collective learning and exchange. The meeting attracted more than **35 participants** from organisations and collectives across the FIERCE partner countries, with a high number of academics, including some younger researchers.

- **Facing Democratic Threats and Mobilising for Change** – Ketevan (Georgia) described the 17 May “Purity of Family” demonstrations, during which queer and feminist activists faced

intimidation and threats to democracy. Lilla (Hungary) outlined government attempts to undermine Budapest Pride and the proposed transparency law that could severely restrict NGOs and media. Cristina (Romania) reflected on the recent presidential election, highlighting the decisive role of women in defeating the right-wing candidate and advancing gender equality. Caleb (ACT) presented the successful EU-wide campaign against forced transitions, which gathered over one million signatures — a milestone for European civil society action.

- **Shaping the Future of the Network** – The meeting concluded with a participatory session using the Miro Board, where partners and participants shared ideas on the Network's next steps. A strong preference emerged for maintaining momentum through regular hybrid meetings that balance accessibility with meaningful engagement.

Figure 56: Screenshots of the Transnational Feminist Network online meetings

Final In-Person Meeting

Date: 19 June 2025 | **Location:** Brussels, Belgium

The final gathering of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network took place as part of the pre-conference programme for the *FIERCE – Feminist Movements Revitalising Democracy in Europe* Final

Conference. Hosted at the RoSa Library (Feminist Library Book), the event combined a book launch with strategic discussions on sustaining the Transnational Feminist Network’s work beyond the project. This final meeting held at the RoSa Library in Brussels, gathered 40 participants, with 32% from academia and 68% from feminist organisations, NGOs, and politicians.

Two landmark publications capturing three years of FIERCE research and collaboration were presented:

- *Feminist Movements in Time and Space: A European Perspective* – presented by Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, with Victoria Showunmi (Associate Professor, University College London, UK) as facilitator.
- *Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe and the Feminist Response – Productive Resistance* – presented by Rok Smerdelj, with Birgit Sauer (Professor, University of Vienna) as facilitator.

This closing meeting reinforced the Transnational Feminist Network’s role as a space for coordinated feminist action, creating renewed momentum among activists and strengthening commitments to continue joint initiatives in the years ahead.

Figure 57: Highlights from the Pre-conference book launch

FIERCE Final Conference – “Feminist Futures for Revitalising Democracy Across Europe”

Date: 20 June 2025 | **Location:** Brussels, Belgium | **Partner:** VIL

Concept and objectives of the FIERCE Final Conference

Full Agenda

The **FIERCE Final Conference**, held on **20 June 2025** at the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) in Brussels, marked the culmination of three years of collaborative research, activism, and policy engagement. Under the title “*Feminist Futures for Revitalising Democracy Across Europe*,” the event gathered **60 onsite participants and 135 online attendees** including feminist activists, researchers, policymakers, and civil society representatives from across Europe to reflect on the project’s findings and explore future feminist strategies for democratic renewal.

The programme was structured around **key thematic panels**, each offering space for dialogue between scholars, activists, and institutional actors:

- **Opening Session – Feminist Pathways to Democratic Renewal**

Featuring welcoming remarks José Antonio Moreno Díaz, Member of the European Economic and Social Committee and Rosa Pérez Monclús, Policy Assistant at the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission.

- **FIERCE Research Results**

Presentation by the FIERCE Coordination team – **Project Coordinator Kyriaki Karydou** (ViLabs) and **Scientific Co-Coordinators Susi Meret and Lise Rolandsen Agustin** (Aalborg University) of the project’s key research findings, addressing the state of feminist movements across Europe, the impact of anti-gender mobilisations, and strategies of resistance. Key highlights include the project’s: **Research results** developed through an interdisciplinary, multi-level framework and a bottom-up approach to analysing anti-gender/anti-feminist and feminist movements across eight country case studies, **the co-creation methodologies and activities** including 8 National Labs, 3 Transnational Labs, 18 FIERCE Actions and the **rich array of resources** including podcasts, the FIERCE campaign, interesting blogposts, and the online FIERCE feminist course that will remain accessible beyond the project’s lifetime.

- **Panel 1 – “How anti-gender and anti-feminist actors and campaigns undermine democracy”**

Moderated by **Roman Kuhar** – **FIERCE project partner, University of Ljubljana**, highlighted that anti-gender mobilization has evolved into a global, mainstream, and institutionalized phenomenon over the past decade, becoming a versatile “toolbox” used by diverse actors. This project has professionalized, shifting its epicenter to politics and far-right think tanks, effectively leveraging digital platforms and exploiting societal fears to influence public opinion and policy. The participants at the round table raised a concern that there is a complacency among progressive actors who often underestimate the threat, failing to adequately prepare or strategize against these mobilizations, leading to internal divisions and the erosion of democratic foundations.

- **Panel 2 – “Feminist approaches and responses to democratic crises in the context of rising challenges to gender and equality across Europe (and beyond)”**

Moderated by **Giada Bonu Rosenkranz** – **FIERCE project partner, Scuola Normale Superiore** highlighted the diverse yet interconnected ways in which feminist actors are navigating rising authoritarianism and anti-gender backlash across different national contexts. Panelists underscored both the risks of institutional capture and the transformative potential of feminist strategies, in a landscape where gender regimes across Europe are changing. Despite the hostile climate, feminist movements continue to act as vital democratic forces, keeping space open for alternative futures grounded in care and collective action.

- **Panel 3 – “Feminist Futures for Revitalising Democracy Across Europe – Taking Stock of Project Results for Democratic Innovation and Policy Implications”**

Moderated by **Maria Sangiuliano** – **FIERCE project partner, Smart Venice** reflected on the key lessons learned from the FIERCE project, charting bold feminist pathways for democratic renewal in Europe and beyond. It showcased how FIERCE has fostered spaces for democratic participation and tested feminist innovations through participatory, bottom-up approaches – all contributing to a more inclusive and resilient democratic future. The participants of this panel included representatives from policymaking institutions, FIERCE actions participants and members of the FIERCE team, bringing a different perspective about the future of democracy across Europe.

The conference closed with reflections from the Coordination team, who emphasised that although the FIERCE project will formally conclude in August 2025, its vision and purpose will carry on. The coming phase will centre on ensuring that the project’s outcomes are not only preserved but actively applied, disseminated, and built upon well beyond the funding period. United in this commitment, all FIERCE partners aim to create enduring avenues for impact and to continue advancing feminist democratic innovation across Europe and beyond – working towards a truly “engendered” democracy.

Below in Figure 59 a highlight of the Final Conference.

Figure 58: Highlights of the FIERCE Final Conference

2.13. Articles and Interviews

Throughout the project's lifetime, numerous articles and interviews were published by partners in both online and print media, at national and local levels. These publications helped bring FIERCE's messages, findings, and activities to wider audiences, fostering public awareness and encouraging dialogue on the project's themes. Examples include features in newspapers, specialised magazines, and online news portals, each tailored to the context and readership of the respective country.

- **Mirovni Institute:** An interview – article at Nedelo Slovenian newspaper and the journalist Urša Izgoršek, about the feminist exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia. Article title: "The battles that never end".

Figure 59: Interview - article Mirovni Institute May 2024

- **UL:** An article edited from our partner from University of Ljubljana published in Slovenian political weekly Mladina under the title “Knjige za pridne punce (Books for good girls)”. below the cover of the issue.

Figure 60: Cover of the Political Magazine Mladina

- **AAU:** an interview with Susi Meret, scientific co-coordinator of the FIERCE project about [The Success of the Radical Right in Northern Europe and the Agenda of the Conservatives Project 2025](#).

Figure 61: Screenshot of the article-Susi Meret (AU)

AAU: Article about [antifeminism in a Danish](#) context published in the web-magazine Videnskab.dk

Figure 62: Screenshot from videnskab.dk article

EA: Article "[Transnational Feminism and Its Foes](#)" on Green European Journal

Figure 63: Screenshot of the article in Green European Journal

FIERCE was also featured in the Research Executive Agency's (REA) article "[Science for Democracy](#)" (29 May 2024), which has attracted significant visibility. This recognition underscores the project's contribution to advancing feminist perspectives within democratic processes and highlights its relevance at the European level.

Figure 64: Screenshot from REA's article

2.14. Synergies with FIERCE's sister projects and relevant initiatives

From the outset, FIERCE has prioritised sustained communication and meaningful collaboration with its sister projects and other related initiatives. To support this goal, we created a dedicated [Clustering](#) section on our website, presenting each sister project with a short description and links to their online channels. This not only increases visibility but also strengthens connections across our networks.

Collaboration has been continuous and multi-faceted, ranging from cross-promotion, sharing and reposting news to joint advocacy initiatives. We regularly share updates from sister projects in our newsletters and on social media, while also providing them with our own content to circulate through their channels. This reciprocal exchange has allowed all projects to reach broader audiences and amplify common messages.

A key outcome of this collaboration has been the co-development of over five joint social media campaigns, reshares and cross-posting (see figures 66 – 67 – 68 for selected social media post examples), particularly around high-visibility international days, including:

- International Women's Day (8 March)
- International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women (25 November)

- Transgender Day of Remembrance (20 November)

These campaigns have involved close cooperation with projects such as CCINDLE, UNTWIST, and Push-Back-Lash and RESIST. (See section 2.8.1. Campaigns for International and Awareness Days).

Beyond communication, event-based collaboration has been equally important. For example:

- Representatives from Gender 5+ and Push-Back-Lash participated in our Transnational Labs, both in person and online.
- Push-Back-Lash delivered a presentation during FIERCE Week in Venice.
- Two members of CCINDLE were guest speakers in FIERCE Dialogue podcast episodes by our partners in [Poland](#) and [Italy](#).
- Participation of FIERCE partners in sister project conferences and webinars: The RESET project Final Conference “*The challenges of impact and sustainability of gender equality*” and the NEXUS project webinar “*The impact of anti-gender discourses and politics on academia and research organisations*” (See Figures 70 - 71)

These joint efforts demonstrate that clustering is not limited to visibility – it is a strategy for mutual learning, resource-sharing, and building stronger feminist and research alliances capable of sustaining momentum beyond individual project lifetimes.

Figure 65: Reshare of CCINDLE content from FIERCE

Figure 66: Reshare of FIERCE content from CCINDLE

Figure 67: Digital banner of the 8th of March joint campaign

Newsletters can serve as a platform for **cross-promotion** between sister projects. In the [second](#) issue of our newsletter, we introduced a special section dedicated to showcasing the work of our “sister” projects. In the eleventh Newsletter issue we promoted the NEXUS webinar (Screenshots of the Newsletters in Figure 69 below)

Keeping up with our Sisters!

 CCINDLE project

 RESIST project

 PUSHBACKLASH project

 UNTWIST project

At FIERCE, we believe in the power of **collaboration!**

We have created a dedicated page on our website showcasing our sister projects with which we share a common vision of a more inclusive democracy in Europe and opened up communication channels with the overall aim of increasing our projects' impact through collaborative activities.

[Explore our page!](#)

In each newsletter issue, we are going to showcase parts of the work of our Sisters! We kick off this initiative with an interesting **blog post** from the CCINDLE project, titled "**Democracy and feminist politics: a crucial relationship**".

In their insightful blog post, the CCINDLE project highlights how feminist politics democratizes the state, empowers marginalized voices, and promotes gender equality. Using Barcelona as a case study, they illustrate how feminist institutional politics can transform municipal institutions and promote intersectional equality.

[Read the full article here!](#)

Not to be missed next year: The NEXUS webinar!

NEXUS Online Webinar: The impact of anti-gender discourses and politics on academic and research organizations

Tune in to learn about:

- The presence of anti-gender actors and politics in Europe
- How they affect policies in universities & research institutions
- Strategies for fostering inclusive gender equality

Guest speakers:

- Lise Rolandsen Agustín – FIERCE Project
- Silvia Díaz Fernández – CCINDLE Project
- Rachel Palmén – INSPIREquality Project

Date: 10 February 2025
 Time: 11:00–12:30 CET
 Where: Zoom

[Register Now](#)
[Learn More](#)

10 February 2025, 11:00 – 12:30 CET

The impact of anti-gender discourses and politics on academic and research organizations

offered by

In collaboration with

Guest speakers:

Lise Rolandsen Agustín
 Aalborg University | FIERCE

Silvia Díaz Fernández
 Universidad Complutense de Madrid | CCINDLE

Rachel Palmén
 Universitat Oberta de Catalunya | INSPIRE

 Online via Zoom

Part of the Sister Projects Webinar Series

Figure 68: FIERCE Newsletters (2nd and 11th) promoting sister projects' activities and clustering collaboration

Figure 69: RESET Final Conference presentation of FIERCE's project coordinator

Figure 70: Poster of the NEXUS project webinar featuring FIERCE partners as speakers

2.15. Partners' communication and dissemination activities

Throughout the project's period, our partners participated in numerous external events, contributing to the dissemination of FIERCE.

Over 68 Communication and Dissemination activities were carried out by FIERCE partners, demonstrating the project's strong outreach efforts and commitment to engaging diverse audiences across Europe and beyond. The following tables present a detailed overview of these activities as reported by the partners themselves. For each activity, the tables specify the partner(s) involved, the title and a brief description, the date in which it took place, the location, and – where available – a relevant link. These activities were promoted either through the official FIERCE communication channels or via the partners' own networks, ensuring broad visibility and impact.

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
MI	6/25-27/2025	Paper presentation at Conference of Europeanists "Legacies and Ruptures: Making sense of Europe"	In the paper on the appropriation of reproductive rights, co-authored with L. Markelj and Ž. Humer, Mojca Pajnik demonstrated how anti-gender actors strategically mobilize emotions such as fear, compassion, and anger to legitimize and normalize pro-natalist positions.	Recasting of feminist abortion discourse: The role of affect	Temple University, Philadelphia	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/transfor-mations-of-public-communication-the-epistemology-of-affective-governance/
AUTH	6/9/2025	FIERCE ACTIONS. National labs	FIERCE ACTIONS. Dissemination activities related to the Greek National Labs. Presentation of the labs' outcomes to civil society, researchers and academic. At Karditsa, Rethymno, Volos.	Feminist and antifeminist movements and mobilizations in Greece, 2010-2023	Karditsa's Women Center, Faculty of Sociology at Rethymnon, Crete, Center of New Media and Feminist Practices in the Public Space, Volos	N/A
SV	6/5/2025	SUPPORTER FINAL CONFERENCE	Final conference of the project. Maria Sangiuliano, Research Director SV was an ABM from the Supporter project		Prague	https://www.supporter-project.eu/looking-back-at-supporter-final-conference
MI	5/27/2025	Paper presentation at ECPR Joint Sessions of Workshops (workshop "Gendering Democratic Resilience")	This paper provides a comparative perspective on feminist responses to anti-abortion attacks in Italy and Slovenia.	Feminist Responses to Anti-Abortion Attacks. Building Democratic Innovations in Informal Fields	Charles University Prague, Jinonice Campus	https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/78896

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
KU	5/10/2025	Paper presentation at a conference in Bilgi University, Istanbul, Turkey	Members of KU research team presented a paper on mixed method approach developed in the FIERCE project.	Toplumsal Cinsiyet Çalışmalarında Karma Yöntem Uygulamaları: Sınırlar ve Fırsatlar	Bilgi University, Istanbul, Turkey	https://www.bilgi.edu.tr/tr/etkinlik/12602/sosyal-bilimlerde-metotlar-ve-sinirlar-disiplinlerarasiliginin-neresindeyiz/
AU	4/24/2025	Talk on antifeminism	Talk to 30-40 young adults at a folk high school	Antifeminism: A New Countermovement?	Parkvej 61, 9700 Brønderslev (Denmark)	N/A
AU	4/24/2025	Online talk on antifeminism	Public talk on antifeminism based on FIERCE's research	Antifeminism: A New Countermovement	Online	N/A
SV	4/17/2025	GE webinar series: Webinar 4 - Nexus project (GA N° 101094949)	Explore anti-gender politics in Europe, their impact on HEIs and RPOs/RFOs, and reflect on strategies to promote inclusive gender equality amid growing anti-feminist discourses.	The impact of anti-gender discourses and politics on academic and research organizations	Online	https://agrigeu.eu/2024/12/16/webinar-4/
MI, UL	3/28/2025	Participation at the roundtable about anti-gender mobilizations in Italy and Slovenia	In her presentation, Leja Markelj (MI) highlighted the key characteristics of the Slovenian context and emphasized the specific forms of operation and institutionalization of anti-gender discourse in Slovenia. Rok Smrdelj (UL) presented the organizational tactics and political influence of anti-	Round Table on Anti-Gender Movements between Italy and Slovenia – The Politics of Anti-Gender: Mobilizations and Discourses	University of Padova, Italy	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Locandina_28-Marzo.pdf

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
			gender actors in Slovenia.			
AU	3/26/2025	QUALREP Seminar Series	Presentation of FIERCE preliminary results as contribution to seminar series on cutting edge research in the area of gender and politics	The FIERCE project: aims and early findings	Online	https://www.qualrep.org/
SV	3/20/2025	Strategic steps for successful implementation of sustainable GEPs - Supporter project internal workshop	Maria Sanguliano, Research Director of Smart Venice organised an internal workshop of the supporter project	N/A	Ljubljana	https://www.supporter-project.eu/
AU	2/10/2025	NEXUS Webinar. The Impact of anti-gender discourses	Webinar focusing on the impacts of anti-gender discourses and politics in HE and Research environments with presentation of preliminary research results from the FIERCE project	FIERCE perspectives on the impact of anti-gender discourses and politics on academic and research organizations	Online	https://nexusproject.info/upcoming-webinar-the-impact-of-anti-gender-discourses-and-politics-on-academic-and-research-organizations/
KU	12/7/2024	Paper presentation: Wither away the family? Feminist responses to the familialist anti-equality and anti-freedom discourses	This is a paper presented in SUGender's 2nd International Gender Studies in Turkey Conference. In this conference, Ayşe Alnıaçık(KU) presented a work-in-progress paper coauthored with Özlem Altan(KU).	Wither away the family? Feminist responses to the familialist anti-equality and anti-freedom discourses	SUGender, Minevra Han, Istanbul, Turkey	https://genderconference.sabanciuniv.edu/en

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UCM	11/7/2024	Paper presentation at the Workshop "Contentious Politics within Civil Society. How the rise of new cleavages and the far right transform civil society", in the Center for Civil Society Research in Berlin	Dissemination of preliminary results from WP1 and WP2	From Confrontation to Avoidance: Feminist Responses to Anti-Gender Mobilization in Spain	WZB Berlin Social Science Center	N/A
UG	10/18/2024	Presentation at an autumn school 'Rule of Law in Central Europe'	Presenting results of the DNA analysis by showing changes in the discursive field in Poland after 2015	N/A	N/A	N/A
MI	9/12-14/2024	Paper presentation at the Annual Conference of SISP (Societa Italiana di Scienza Politica)	The paper explores the affective appropriation of the feminist abortion discourse in Slovenia. The analysis draws upon empirical data obtained through a critical frame analysis of activist documents addressing abortion, covering the period from 2010 to 2023.	Framing abortion discourse through affect: Anti-gender appropriation of feminist human rights frame	University of Trieste, Italy	https://www.sisp.it/convegno2024/?page_name=cms&name=sessiontracks&trackname=gender--sexuality--and-intersectionality-in-politics

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
UCM	8/30/2024	Paper presentation at the 16th European Sociological Association Conference in Porto	Disseminating the preliminary results of the Critical Frame Analysis (of parliamentary debates around gender policy issues and feminist movements' documents) carried out within the work of WP2	Gendered Public Policies: The Discourse around Feminism in Spain	Faculty of Architecture - University of Porto	N/A
MI	8/29/2024	Paper presentation at 16th ESA Conference 2024: Tension, Trust and Transformation	The authors examine feminist and anti-gender discourse on the right to abortion, drawing on the concept of affective atmospheres.	Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse: Shifting human rights frame through affect	Porto, Portugal	https://www.europeansociology.org/media/e68213f0-f856-4c07-9288-301b2d153fd0
UCM	8/29/2024	Paper presentation in the 16th European Sociological Association Conference	Dissemination of the preliminary results of the Digital Network Analysis carried out in FIERCE as part of WP1 and WP2 fieldwork	Gendered Public Policies: The Discourse around Feminism in Spain	Faculty of Architecture - University of Porto	N/A
UCM	8/28/2024	Paper presentation	Dissemination of the preliminary results of the fieldwork carried out within WP1 of the FIERCE project	The Rise of Anti-gender Politics in Spain: Frames, campaigns and political alignments	Faculty of Architecture - University of Porto	N/A

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
MI	8/15/2024	Paper presentation at the General conference of the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR)	In the paper, the authors examine feminist and anti-gender discourse on the right to abortion, drawing on the concept of affective atmospheres.	Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse: Shifting human rights frame through affect	University of Dublin, Ireland	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/anti-gender-appropriation-of-feminist-abortion-discourse-through-affect/ https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/77577
UL	7/21/2024	Conference	The activity was carried out with the aim of disseminating scientific findings among the wider academic community, ensuring that new insights and knowledge are shared broadly.	Practicing Counter-Strategies: Resisting the Anti-Gender Backlash in Slovenia	University of Gent	https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PaperDetails/73957
MI	7/3/2024	Paper at the “Radical Europe: Violence, Emancipation & Reaction” conference	The presentation focused on the discursive structural regularity in the speeches of anti-gender mobilization actors.	Gender Ideology as a Frame Repertoire: Transversal Instrumentalization of Gender Equality	Lyon, France	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/discursive-regularity-in-the-rhetoric-of-the-anti-gender-movement/
UL	7/1/2024	Alliances And Resistances: Shaping Feminist Mobilizations in the Context of Neoconservative Pushback	Chairing a panel on anti-gender mobilizations (and results from FIERCE) at ECPG 2024 in Ghent, 8. 7. 2024	Alliances and resistances: Shaping feminist mobilizations in the context of neoconservative pushback	University of Ghent	https://ecpr.eu/Events/Event/PanelDetails/14673

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
UCM	6/28/2024	Presentation at XV Congreso Español de Sociología, June 26-29, Seville.	Dissemination of research results to the academic community	Care work as the focal point of change. Feminist struggles and discourses and their impact on the political agenda	Universidad Pablo Olavide, Seville, Spain	https://congreso2024.fes-sociologia.com/
KU	6/25/2024	Sunbelt Annual Conference	Using DNA to study feminist and anti-feminist discursive networks	Explaining the Resilience of Feminist Discourses in Turkey Using Discourse Network Analysis	Sunbelt Network Analysis Annual Conference, Edinburgh	N/A
MI	5/24/2024	Interview/article in the media (Saturday edition of newspaper Delo)	Article by Urša Izgoršek, journalist of Nedelo about the feminist exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia.	The battles that never end	published article	N/A
KU	5/17/2024	Association for the Study of Nationalities Conference - Paper presentation on Discourse Network Analysis of Feminist and Anti-Feminist Debates	Network analysis of anti-feminist groups	Mapping the Anti-Feminist Discourses in Turkey	Association for the Study of Nationalities Annual Conference, New York	N/A
AU	4/25/2024	Presentation about antifeminism	Presentation of our research for an NGO (The Association Dad)	Webinar om ligestilling	Online	N/A

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
SV	2/9/2024	Second Transnational lab_Madrid	Sister project Gender5+ participation to transnational lab		Madrid	N/A
AU	11/17/2023	Presentation for students	Presentation of our project to students in political science	Feminism and antifeminism	Aalborg University - Fibigerstræde 15 (9220 Aalborg East)	N/A
AU	10/25/2023	Presentation for high-school students	Present our research and preliminary findings to Danish high-school students	Feminism and antifeminism	Pontoppidanstræde 105, 9220 Aalborg East (Denmark)	N/A
UL	9/28/2023	Presentation of research results at the conference.	Presentation of preliminary findings to an international research audience in order to review research progress and propose potential future directions in the subject in focus.	Anti-gender discursive "legacy": Framing gender debate by opposing "gender theory"	The conference ESA RN23 Sexuality, 'Making a difference: the hope and promise of sexuality studies' took place on Thursday 28th and Friday 29th September 2023. The location was Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Ulica Ivana Lucica 3, Zagreb.	N/A
SV	9/19/2023	FIERCE first transnational lab	First transnational lab co-creation lab organised in Brussels joining feminist activists and allies from national labs and transnational feminist organisations	First FIERCE transnational lab	Amazone - Carrefour pour l'égalité des genres (Rue du Méridien 10, 1210 Brussel, Belgio)	N/A

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
UL	9/7/2023	Presentation of results at the conference	Presentation of initial results to an international research audience to review progress in research and explore possible future directions in the field.	Anti-gender Movement in Slovenia: Between Fighting Marriage Equality and Strengthening LGBT+ Community	ECPR General Conference 2023, 4 – 8 September, Charles University, https://ecpr.eu/Events/214	https://ecpr.eu/Event/Event/PaperDetails/71814
KU	9/7/2023	European Consortium for Political Research Annual Conference Paper presentation	Feminist advocacy work and its contribution to revitalizing democracy	Advocacy in the Face of Government Backlash: Feminist Movements in Turkey and New Avenues of Research in Redemocratization	European Consortium for Political Research Annual Conference, Prague	N/A
MI	6/27-29/2023	Paper presentation at the conference "Europe's Past, Present and Future: Utopias and Dystopias"	Presentation analyzed the anti-gender mobilizing in the context of Central-Eastern Europe, emphasizing the Slovenian case. Particularly, it showed how anti-gender actors instrumentalize the crises to re-nationalize citizenship and to reify heteronormative visions of social development.	Anti-gender Backlash in Central-Eastern Europe: Instrumentalizing the Crisis	University of Iceland, Reykjavik	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/gender-and-the-far-right-at-the-conference-europes-past-present-and-future/

Partner's name	Date	Dissemination activity name	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Title of presentation (if applicable)	Location of the event (venue / online - if applicable)	URL of the activity (if applicable)
AU	6/22/2023	Seminar presentation	Presentation to other scholars who provided relevant feedback on particularly the co-creation labs	Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy? Reflections on the Case of Denmark	Aalborg University	https://twitter.com/OscarGarAgu/status/1670795167085785090
MI	6/21-23/2023	Presentation at the conference Anti-feminism and Anti-gender Politics in Authoritarian Regimes	Mojca Pajnik presented populist strategies of anti-gender movement in defending »the tradition«. She analysed how imagining of the tradition, traditional families, values, sexual relations etc. are formed and how they are used to undermine feminist and LGBTQ+ struggle.	Anti-gender Mobilization: Defending 'the Traditional' from a Post-sexual Imaginary in Central-Eastern Europe	Marburg, Germany	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/confERENCE-on-anti-gender-in-authoritarian-regimes/
MI	5/25-26/2023	Presentation at the conference European Politics, Equality and Democracy	Mojca Pajnik presented the functioning of feminist initiatives online as a policy of "connective alliance" and examined how movements address gender inequalities at the intersection of critiques of patriarchy, racism, neoliberalism, and the rise of authoritarian anti-politics.	Feminist activism against democracy back-lash: experiences from post-socialist Slovenia	University of Helsinki, Finland	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/gostovanje-konferenca-helsinki/

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AU	5/23/2023	Presentation at a workshop in the network "Masculinity, masculinist politics, and political extremism in the Nordic"	Mainly to get feedback on ongoing work in the Danish team with workpage 1	Mapping Anti-Feminist and Anti-Gender Activity in Denmark	Kompas Hotel, Aalborg	N/A
UG	5/4/2023	Meeting with contentious politics research cluster at Coventry University	The Polish research team was invited to present initial outcomes of the project	N/A	online appearance at the research cluster meeting	N/A

Table 7: Partners dissemination activities throughout the project's duration

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
SV	10/17/2025	Presentation of the self-defence manual developed in the Italian lab in an event organised by the "A Scuola Per Conoscerci" network	"A Scuola Per Conoscerci" is a project for the prevention and countering of homophobic, lesbophobic, biphobic, and transphobic bullying in schools in Friuli Venezia Giulia. The event will include a panel discussion with participants from different feminist networks that took part in the co-creation lab where the manual was developed. As part of the event's		Trieste, Italy	Not available yet

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
			dissemination strategy, the organisers will produce short thematic videos focusing on topics addressed in the manual.			
SV	9/27-28/2025	Presentation of the self-defence manual developed in the Italian lab in the annual meeting of the Rete Educare alle Differenze	This possibility is being coordinated with members of the network who participated in the co-creation process.	Educare alle Differenze – XI annual meeting	Padua, Italy	https://www.educarealleanze.it/educare-alle-differenze-xi/
SV	9/17/2025	Presentation of the self-defence manual and debate with teachers, school unions, and NGOs scheduled for 19 September at “Pordenone Fuorilegge”	This is an initiative created as a parallel event to the well-known literary festival "Pordenonelegge". It consists of a series of meetings and activities organized with the aim of raising awareness on the civil rights of sex workers, sensitize on omo-transphobia, while also fighting exploitation and human trafficking.	Pordenone Fuorilegge	Pordenone, Italy	Not available yet
MI	7/24/2025	Webpage post on published article	The journal Interdisciplinary Political Studies has published the article “Feminist Responses to Anti-Abortion Attacks in Italy and Slovenia. Building Democratic Innovations in Contexts of De-Democratization” co-authored by Anastasia Barone, Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, Leja Markelj, and Rok Smrdelj.	Feminist Responses to Anti-Abortion Attacks in Italy and Slovenia	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/feministicni-odzivi-na-napade-na-pravico-do-splava-v-italiji-in-sloveniji/
MI	7/8/2025	Webpage post on paper presentation	At the Temple University in Philadelphia, Mojca Pajnik	Transformations of Public	Mirovni institute's	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/transformati

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
			presented the paper titled "Recasting of feminist abortion discourse: the role of affect", co-authored with Leja Markelj and Živa Humer.	Communication: The Epistemology of Affective Governance	website	ons-of-public-communication-the-epistemology-of-affective-governance/
MI	6/24/2025	Webpage post on Fierce final conference	Post describes the participation of Mirovni institute at the Fierce final conference in Brussels. It highlights it's inputs within the roundtable on feminist responses to anti-gender movements.	On the democratic potential of feminist movements in Brussels	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/v-bruslju-o-democraticnem-potencialu-feministicnih-gibanj/
MI	5/27/2025	Webpage post on paper presentation	Post describes the paper presentation at ECPR joint sessions of workshops at Charles university in Prague. At the workshop titled <i>Gendering Democratic Resilience</i> , Leja Markelj presented the paper ' <i>Feminist Responses to Anti-Abortion Attacks. Building Democratic Innovations in Contexts of De-Democratization</i> ', co-authored with Anastasia Barone, Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, and Rok Smrdelj.	Feminist Democratic Innovations as a Response to Anti-Abortion Attacks	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/feminist-democratic-innovations-as-a-response-to-anti-abortion-attacks/
MI	5/13/2025	Web page post announcing Fierce final conference	Invitation to participate at the Fierce final conference	"Feminist Futures for the Revitalization of Democracy in Europe": Final	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/feministicne-prihodnosti-za-revitalizacijo-demokracije-v-evropi-zakljucna-

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
				Conference of the Fierce Project		konferenca-projekta-fierce/
AU	5/15/2025	Presentation at national seminar on LGBTQ+ rights	Presentation on misinformation about LGBTQ+ persons in Denmark and the rest of Europe	Misinformation about LGBTQ+ persons in Denmark	The Danish Institute for Human Rights in Copenhagen / Online presentation	https://menneskeret.dk/arrangementer/stemmer-modvind-lgbt-rettigheder-tid-misinformation
MI	3/24/2025	Webpage post on partner meeting in Gdansk	The post describes the Consortium meeting in Gdańsk, Poland (18–19 March). Discussions addressed the rise of anti-gender actors, feminist resilience, and the role of transnational solidarity, with plans for policy recommendations and continued network activities.	The FIERCE Project in Gdańsk: How to Bring the Feminist Agenda into Political Processes	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/the-fierce-project-in-gdansk-how-to-bring-the-feminist-agenda-into-political-processes/
MI	3/21/2025	Webpage post on book chapter	The book Feminist Movements in Time and Space: A European Perspective (ed. Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, Donatella della Porta), published by Palgrave Macmillan, includes a chapter by Leja Markelj and Mojca Pajnik (MI) on the trans-thematic action of contemporary feminist mobilisations in Slovenia.	Trans-thematic Action: Contemporary Feminist Mobilizations in Slovenia	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/trans-thematic-action-contemporary-feminist-mobilizations-in-slovenia/
MI	11/25/2024	Web page post on Fierce	Within the Fierce action carried out by the Slovenian collective	Gender on the	Mirovni institute's	https://www.mirovni-

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
		actions roundtable	TransAkcija, round table discussion entitled Gender on the Radar took place, focusing on the response of the LGBTIQ+ community and society as a whole to the rise in violence and hatred towards the LGBTIQ+ community.	Radar	website	institut.si/spol-na-radarju/
AU	11/14/2024	Panel conversation: LGBT+ politisk topmøde ("LGBT+ political summit")	Participation at a panel in a political conference/summit arranged through cooperation between all the major LGBT+ organizations in Denmark.	"LGBT+ rights: Is it going the wrong way?"	Ny Kongensgade 10, Copenhagen	https://lgbt.dk/politisk-topmoede/
SV	11/14/2024	FIERCE campaign "Five FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe"	FIERCE Transnational Lab co-created a communication campaign for the 2024 EP elections, developed in meetings on 19 Sept 2023 and 7–8 Feb 2024, launched online on 26 April, and concluded with a pre-election event on 4 June 2024.	"Five FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe"		https://campaign.fierce-project.eu/
SV	11/7/2024	FIERCE week	In presence event mixing: (i) third transnational lab, (ii) FIERCE winter school and (iii) launching of the FIERCE transnational network		Laguna Libre (Fondamenta di Cannaregio, 969, Venice)	
MI	9/5/2024	Webpage post	Invitation to participate in Fierce actions	Public call for Fierce actions for implementation of feminist activities	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/javni-razpis-fierce-actions-za-izvajanje-feministicnih-aktivnosti/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
MI	8/23/2024	Webpage post on paper presentation	At the general conference of the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) at University College Dublin, Leja Markelj presented a paper ' <i>Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse: Shifting human rights frame through affect</i> ,' co-authored with Mojca Pajnik and Živa Humer.	Anti-gender appropriation of feminist abortion discourse through affect	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/anti-gender-appropriation-of-feminist-abortion-discourse-through-affect/
MI	7/9/2024	Webpage post on paper presentation	At the conference "Radical Europe: Violence, Emancipation & Reaction," held July 3-6, 2024, in Lyon, Mojca Pajnik presented a paper co-authored with Roman Kuhar and Rok Smrdelj titled "Gender Ideology as a Frame Repertoire: Transversal Instrumentalization of Gender Equality."	Discursive Regularity in the Rhetoric of the Anti-Gender Movement	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/discursive-regularity-in-the-rhetoric-of-the-anti-gender-movement/
AU	7/12/2024	Antifeminisme	Contribution to Danish online encyclopedia on antifeminism		Online	https://denstoredanske.lex.dk/antifeminisme
UL	5/31/2024	Knjige za pridne punce (Books for good girls) - political magazine article	Text about the anti-gender backlash in the context of European elections	Knjige za pridne punce (Books for good girls)		https://www.mladina.si/232787/alternativa-bicanje-evrope/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
SV	5/21/2024	Verso un'agenda politica femminista Europea	Communication event with local Venetian feminist movements to present the FIERCE project, share next steps, and encourage their involvement in organising FIERCE Week (4–7 November). Included information on the FIERCE Actions call.	Towards a European Feminist Political Agenda	Laguna Libre (Fondamenta di Cannaregio 969, Venezia)	
MI	5/16/2024	Webpage post on Fierce feminist campaign EP 2024	"Feminist campaign for the upcoming European Parliament elections"	Feminist campaign for the upcoming European Parliament elections	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/feministicna-kampanja-ob-prihajajocih-volitvah-v-evropski-parlament/
MI	5/8/2024	Webpage post	Report on the feminist exhibition opening and guided tour (national lab outcome)	Opening of the exhibition on reproductive rights	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/otvoritev-razstave-o-reproduktivnih-pravicah/
MI	4/26/2024	Webpage post Exhibition "Reproductive rights: On health, sexuality and equality of women"	Invitation to the opening and guided tour of feminist exhibition on reproductive rights (national lab outcome)	"Reproductive rights: On health, sexuality and equality of women"	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/razstava-reproduktivne-pravice-o-zdravju-spolnosti-in-enakosti-zensk/
AU	3/8/2024	Popular science article Er der nogle antifeminister derude ("Are there any antifeminists out there?")	Article about antifeminism in a Danish context published in the web-magazine Videnskab.dk			https://videnskab.dk/kultur-samfund/er-der-nogen-antifeminister-derude/
MI	2/19/2024	Webpage post	Webpage post on the MI's website about the project meeting in	FIERCE in Madrid:	Mirovni institute's	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/fierce-in-

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
			Madrid	partners meeting and designing a feminist campaign for the upcoming European elections	website	madrid-partners-meeting-and-designing-a-feminist-campaign-for-the-upcoming-european-elections/
SV	1/9/2024	FIERCE roundtable	Public roundtable with European feminist networks and organisations on challenges and political strategies for the EP elections, held as part of the Transnational Lab meetings. Panelists represented WIDE+, Young Feminist Europe, European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual and Reproductive Rights, and the Women's Lobby of Slovenia.	Feminist Agendas in the 2024 EP? Reaching out to the candidates	N/A	N/A
MI	1/3/2024	Webpage post on Fierce roundtable	Invitation to the public roundtable with European feminist networks and organisations on challenges and political strategies for the EP elections, held as part of the Transnational Lab meetings.	Vabilo na prvo spletno okroglo mizo 'Feminist agendas in the 2024 European Parliament? Reaching out to the candidates'	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/vabilo-na-prvo-spletno-okroglo-mizo-feminist-agendas-in-the-2024-european-parliament-reaching-out-to-the-candidates/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
EA	12/4/2023	FIERCE - Green European Journal article "Transnational Feminism and Its Foes"	Journal Article	Transnational Feminism and Its Foes	Green European Journal	https://www.greeneuropejournal.eu/transnational-feminism-and-its-foes/
AU	11/29/2023	Presentation of paper "Antiviolence as the new spirit of feminism"	Presentation of a paper on the campaign for a consent-based rape legislation in Denmark at the annual meeting of the Danish Political Science Association	N/A	Danish Political Science Association Denmark	N/A
AU	11/24/2023	Sexism from a minority perspective	Panel discussion at the gender equality festival Talk Town	N/A	Talk Town (in Copenhagen)	N/A
AU	10/31/2023	Paper presentation at the GINAAU-seminar	Paper presented for the first seminar in the Gender- and Intersectionality Netværk at Aalborg University (GINAAU)	N/A	Aalborg University	N/A
MI	7/10/2023	Webpage post	Webpage post on the MI's website with a short report from the roundtable "Feminism and reproductive rights" organized as a part of first national lab	Feminizem in reproduktivne pravice	Ljubljana	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/feminizem-in-reproduktivne-pravice/
MI	7/5/2023	Webpage post on paper presentation	Mojca Pajnik attended the international conference »Europe's Past, Present and Future: Utopias and Dystopias« that took place in Reykjavik. She presented a paper co-authored with Roman Kuhar entitled "Anti-gender Backlash in Central-Eastern Europe:	Gender and the Far Right at the conference Europe's Past, Present and Future	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/gender-and-the-far-right-at-the-conference-europes-past-present-and-future/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
			Instrumentalizing the Crisis”.			
UL	6/29/2023	Podcast: Feminism and reproductive rights	Round table on sexual and reproductive rights in Slovenia, addressing historic feminist struggles, current anti-feminist backlash, and threats to existing rights. Featured contributions from academics and activists, moderated by Dr. Roman Kuhar. Opened with an introductory address by Dr. Mojca Pajnik, and the discussion involved Dr. Metka Mencin (Faculty of Social Sciences), Tea Hvala (sociologist), and Tija Jakič (8th March Institute).	Feminism and reproductive rights	Pritličje, Ljubljana	https://spotifyanchor-web.app.link/e/LhXDt3aKeBb
MI	6/26/2023	Webpage post on participation at the conference	Mojca Pajnik was invited to attend the international conference »Anti-feminism and Anti-gender Politics in Authoritarian Regimes«, in Marburg, Germany. Her talk was titled “Anti-gender Mobilization: Defending ‘the Traditional’ from a Post-sexual Imaginary in Central-Eastern Europe”.	Conference on Anti-gender in Authoritarian Regimes	Mirovni institute’s website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/conference-on-anti-gender-in-authoritarian-regimes/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
VIL	6/20/2023	Participation to the final event organized by RESISTIRE project	Raising awareness about FIERCE and had the opportunity to connect with other sister projects and exchange ideas as we work towards our mission of challenging norms and building a more equitable and inclusive society.		Brussels, Belgium	N/A
MI	6/6/2023	Webpage post on paper presentation	At the conference "European Politics, Equality and Democracy" in Helsinki, Mojca Pajnik presented a paper titled "Feminist activism against democracy backlash: experiences from post-socialist Slovenia".	Gostovanje na konferenci 'European Politics, Equality and Democracy' v Helsinkih	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/gostovanje-konferenca-helsinki/
MI	5/25/2023	Website post	Post about the second consortium meeting in Aalborg	Na Danskem o potencialih feminističnih gibanj za krepitev demokratičnih praks	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/na-danskem-o-potencialih-feministicnih-gibanj-za-krepitev-demokraticnih-praks/
KU	12/20/2022	The now and future of women's movements: Turkey, Iran, and global developments	Webinar	N/A	Webinar	https://kockam.ku.edu.tr/events/kadin-hareketlerinin-bugunu-gelecegi-turkiye-iran-kuresel-gelismeler/

Partner's name	Date	Communication Activity Name & Title	Description	Title (if applicable)	Location of the event	URL of the activity (if applicable)
KU	11/12/2022	Participation in the annual meeting of the Assembly on Women's Shelters and Solidarity Centers	One of our research team members participated in the annual meeting of the Assembly on Women's Shelters and Solidarity Centers, held on 12-14 November 2022 in Diyarbakır. The Assembly is composed of women's organizations specialized on the issue of domestic violence.	N/A	Diyarbakır, Turkey	https://siginaksizbirdunya.org/
EA	10/24/2022	Project Presentation on organization's website	Informative article about FIERCE objectives and countries involved	FIERCE: FEMINIST MOVEMENTS REVITALIZING DEMOCRACY IN EUROPE	N/A	https://euroalter.com/project/fierce/
MI	10/12/2022	Web page post	Web page post on the first project meeting taking place in Thessaloniki	FIERCE project's first meeting	Mirovni institute's website	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/prvi-sestanek-mednarodne-raziskave-fierce/
AU	4/1/2022	Press release about the FIERCE project	News item on the website for Institute for Politics and Society at Aalborg University about the FIERCE project	N/A	Online	https://www.politik-samfund.aau.dk/nyheder/vis/new-project---feminist-movements-revitalizing-democracy-in-europe.cid533391

Table 8: Partners communication activities Throughout the project's duration

3. Exploitation, Sustainability and Replication Plan

3.1. FIERCE's overall Exploitation, Sustainability and Replication Strategy

Introduction

Over the past three years, FIERCE has generated innovative impacts in research and practice by bridging disciplinary gaps and scaling knowledge from national to transnational levels. Rooted in core democratic values – equality, solidarity, rights, participation, and dialogue – the project combined academic excellence with participatory, feminist, and activist approaches.

Through interviews, Critical Frame Analysis, and Discourse Network Analysis, the project investigated how feminist movements mobilise and respond to threats, while also highlighting their role as democratic innovators. Complementing this ecosystem of knowledge, FIERCE placed democratic innovation at its core through co-creation and participatory methods, ensuring impact at local, national, and European levels.

These achievements form the basis of FIERCE's Exploitation, Sustainability, and Replication Strategy. Beyond producing high-level research, the project sought to ensure that its knowledge, tools, and networks remain impactful and transferable, offering long-term value for academia, civil society, and policymakers across Europe.

Objectives

This Exploitation, Sustainability, and Replication Strategy aims to ensure that the project's key outcomes continue to generate value beyond the project's lifetime. It seeks to:

- Support the long-term use and relevance of FIERCE's outputs among diverse stakeholders
- Strengthen feminist democratic practices and networks at local, national, and transnational levels
- Enable the transfer and adaptation of successful methodologies and actions to new contexts
- Ensure access to practical tools, knowledge, and funding opportunities that empower feminist actors to continue their work.

FIERCE Exploitation, Sustainability and Replication strategy pillars

To ensure the continuity of FIERCE's innovative approach, maximise the impact of its outputs, and safeguard its sustainability beyond its duration, this Exploitation, Sustainability and Replication Plan is structured around three main pillars:

1. Identification, presentation, and description of the project's Key Exploitation Results as they were developed throughout the project's duration.
2. Co-design of all partners' Individual Exploitation Plans with project partners and stakeholders to ensure the continued use, enhancement, and upscaling of all FIERCE outputs.
3. Creation of a Replication / Transferability Guidebook to support the replication of the FIERCE Actions implemented during the project, equipping grassroots organisations, feminist movements, activists and other stakeholders with knowledge, tools, and access to funding through a curated map of opportunities.

3.2. Identification, presentation and description of FIERCE's Key Exploitation Results

Introduction

The identification of FIERCE's **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** lies at the heart of the project's exploitation and sustainability strategy. KERs refer to both tangible and intangible outputs that hold the potential for long-term impact, broad adoption, and meaningful replication. These results form the foundation for extending FIERCE's influence beyond the project's duration - shaping policy, practice, and academic discourse across Europe and beyond.

This is not a static exercise, but a dynamic and iterative process. An initial version of the KERs was outlined in **Deliverable D6.1: Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan**, serving as a preliminary framework. Over the course of the project, this list was further enriched through continued work and partner engagement.

A significant milestone in the process was the **Exploitation and Sustainability Workshop**, held in Gdańsk in March 2025, where partners collectively reviewed, discussed, and refined the KERs. Each partner contributed from their perspective and role in the project, helping to shape and validate the final list presented in this section.

FIERCE's Key Exploitation Results

The table below presents the updated and final version of the FIERCE Key Exploitable Results (KERs), outlining their descriptions, objectives, and target audiences (both internal and external). These KERs form the foundation for co-designing the Individual Exploitation Plans of all FIERCE partners (see Section 3.3).

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	Description – Goals – Audiences
1. Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement analysis	<p>Description: This KER refers to the interdisciplinary, multidimensional, multi-level framework built on a bottom-up approach to feminism and democracy</p> <p>Goal: Develop a framework to analyze social movements through interviews, Critical Frame Analysis, and Discourse Network Analysis - 8 country case studies analysis Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Feminist movements and networks, Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>
2. Transnational Feminist Network	<p>Description: The establishment of the Transnational feminist Network aims at a continued exchange of experiences, peer review and scaling up of the experimented democratic innovations at local/national levels, including the willingness to strengthen the capacity of the feminist actors and to mobilize against anti-gender movements.</p> <p>Goal: Develop an active community of stakeholders - Involvement of > 65 organisations/individuals Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>
3. FIERCE's Training Material	<p>Description: FIERCE's training material consists of a self-paced online feminist course that explores non-hierarchical forms of feminist knowledge generation, bridging research and activism to strengthen intersectional alliances and counter anti-gender and anti-feminist discourse. Drawing on FIERCE's research and co-creation with feminist organisations, the course brings together academic knowledge and activist experience. It features lectures by gender and political studies scholars alongside first-hand insights from feminist activists, exploring current political dynamics, sharing resistance strategies, and imagining collective feminist futures.</p> <p>Goal: Recorded modules from the Feminist winter School exploit in other trainings and capacity building - 3 modules with video lectures Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Civil Society Organisations, feminist & minorities' movements, Research Centers/ Academia (External stakeholders)</p>
4. FIERCE Actions	<p>Description: FIERCE Actions are feminist-driven initiatives designed to promote democratic participation and innovation from an intersectional feminist perspective. 18 FIERCE ACTIONS were supported by the project (7 actions were proposed as the result of collaborative work elaborated within the FIERCE National Labs and 11 Actions were selected as the result of an open call). FIERCE Actions combined several forms of actions, notably when it comes to public events that combined round tables, cultural events, workshops and/or exhibitions.</p> <p>Goal: To ensure the replication and adaptation of FIERCE Actions beyond the project's lifespan, supporting their continued use by feminist movements and stakeholders across diverse contexts. Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>
5. FIERCE National	<p>Description: FIERCE National Labs were conceived as action-oriented <i>dialogues</i> – hybrid spaces of encounter between</p>

Labs	<p>academic research and empirical co-creation processes. As meeting points for a diverse range of actors, the labs prioritised discursive engagement, focusing on the most pressing themes and challenges faced by feminist movements across Europe. Beyond dialogue, each lab led to the co-creation and implementation of a concrete political or policy-oriented outcome.</p> <p>Goal: Implement 8 National Labs for each FIERCE country / 3 national labs per country Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>
6. Scientific publications	<p>Description: Peer-reviewed articles and other academic outputs produced during the FIERCE project.</p> <p>Goal: To contribute to the project’s scientific legacy by advancing feminist scholarship and ensuring long-term access to research findings across disciplines and sectors. Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Research Centers/Academia, Civil society organisations, political institutions and actors (External stakeholders)</p>
7. FIERCE’s communication material – website, videos, podcasts, campaigns	<p>Description: A collection of communication tools and content developed for the project, including the website, videos, podcasts, social media campaigns, and visual assets to promote FIERCE’s messages and results.</p> <p>Goal: To amplify FIERCE’s visibility, engage diverse audiences, and ensure broad dissemination and long-term accessibility of the project’s outcomes. Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>
3. Policy Toolkit	<p>Description: Policy toolkit that present methods and practices - in a simple and easily usable manner</p> <p>Goal: Provide innovation in democratic engagement, while also introducing policy recommendations to defend women and LGBTQ+ rights in the face of the identified 'backlash' against Gender Rights. Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Political institutions and political actors, Public Authorities, Civil Society Organisations, Research Centers/Academia (External stakeholders)</p>
5. FIERCE’s Lessons Learnt	<p>Description: Insights and reflections gathered from the collective experience of FIERCE partners over the course of the project.</p> <p>Goal: To synthesise key insights from the overall FIERCE experience - across research, co-creation, and collaboration - to inform future EU-funded projects and strengthen practices across sectors. Targeted Audiences: All partners (Internal stakeholders) - Research Centers/Academia, Civil Society Organisations, Political institutions and political actors (External stakeholders)</p>

Table 9: Complete List of the FIERCE Key Exploitable Results

3.3. The Co-Design of Individual Exploitation Plans

Introduction

An Individual Exploitation Plan is a document co-created by each consortium partner to define how they intend to use, apply, and benefit from the project's outcomes. These plans are essential to sustaining the impact of FIERCE beyond its funding period, whether through internal application within partner organisations or by sharing and adapting the results across broader networks and communities.

This section outlines the co-design process of the Individual Exploitation Plans (IEPs), which aim to ensure that FIERCE's results are aligned with the strategic priorities and needs of each partner. It includes the methodology used to co-create the IEPs, followed by the presentation of each partner's plan.

The section also lays the foundation for the wider exploitation of FIERCE's outcomes after the project's conclusion. The FIERCE consortium includes 11 organisations from 8 European countries (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey), comprising:

- **Seven Universities:** Aalborg University (AAU), Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS), Complutense University of Madrid (UCM), University of Gdansk (UG), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Koç University (KU), University of Ljubljana (UL)
- **Two Civil Society Organisations (CSOs):** European Alternatives (EA), Mirovni Institute (MI)
- **Two Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs):** ViLabs (VIL), Smart Venice (SV)

According to the FIERCE Grant Agreement (Section 2.2.3 - Annex 1 - Description of the Action, Part B) the FIERCE consortium brings together well-established organisations with the expertise and capacity to ensure the project's results are effectively exploited and sustained.

Methodology

The co-design of IEPs forms the core of FIERCE's exploitation and sustainability strategy. By tailoring a plan for each partner, the project ensures that its results will continue to be visible, applicable, and transferable - adopting and adapting FIERCE's innovative framework, co-creation methods, and participatory approach.

To achieve this, ViLabs (task leader for Communication, Dissemination, and Sustainability) coordinated the following key activities:

1. Organised a dedicated **Sustainability, Exploitation, and Replication Workshop** during the in-person consortium meeting in Gdańsk
2. Designed a **tailored questionnaire** to guide partners in drafting their IEPs (see Annex 5)
3. Analysed the questionnaire responses and finalised each partner's plan

The Participatory Workshop

A key milestone was the **in-person consortium meeting in Gdańsk (March 18–19, 2025)**, which featured a structured participatory workshop, including:

- A presentation of the overall strategy for Sustainability, Exploitation, and Replication
- An introduction to the IEPs: purpose, structure, and process

- A discussion of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), with partners contributing input and refinements
- A group activity using posters and prompt cards to guide exploration of each KER's potential

The Process

Before the Workshop

To prepare, ViLabs created **four A2 posters** listing the project's KERs. Each poster included four columns:

- A brief KER description
- Sections for: Exploitation, Sustainability, and Replication/Transfer
- A prompt card with questions and tips to guide responses

During the Workshop

The session began with a brief presentation and overview of the KERs. Partners were divided into four groups and invited to fill out the poster columns collaboratively, using the prompt cards for guidance. The group discussions explored how each KER could be:

- **Exploited** within their specific organisational context
- **Sustained** beyond the project's lifetime
- **Replicated** or transferred to other institutions, contexts, or regions

Each group then presented their reflections, sparking collective discussion.

After the Workshop

The WP6 leader (VIL) collected and synthesised feedback from the posters.

The partner's IEP Questionnaire

Following the participatory workshop, VIL designed and distributed an open-ended questionnaire (Annex 5) to all partners to support the development of their Individual Exploitation Plans (IEPs). The goal was to help each organisation reflect on FIERCE's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and articulate their own plans for how to use, sustain, and potentially replicate them after the project's completion.

Each partner received a table listing all the KERs, with space to respond to a series of guiding questions and examples and had two months to complete it. To support this process, the questionnaire also included a file summarising the feedback collected during the Gdańsk workshop, offering additional context and inspiration.

The questions were designed to prompt strategic thinking while allowing each response to reflect the organisation's mission, expertise, and sectoral role. They were grouped thematically as follows:

1. Strategic Interest

How will you use this KER within your organisation or sector? (i.e., how it links to your organisation's mission or strategy, concrete steps to apply it, key people or departments involved)

2. Exploitation

In what ways has this KER contributed (or can it contribute) to building your organisational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e. replication in other projects, inclusion in methodology, enhancing teaching methods, developing new consulting, training, or facilitation services; generating new project ideas)

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e., building networks with partners or clients; new or continued research collaborations; opportunities for Horizon Europe proposals; fostering interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)

4. Sustainability

How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e., necessary resources, funding, personnel, or infrastructure; ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support; potential evolution or scaling over time; already initiated uses in academic activities)

5. Replication / Transferability

Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, or settings? If yes, how? (i.e., application in other departments, sectors, or regions; adjustments needed to enable broader transfer beyond the organisation)

Additionally, for **KER 9 – FIERCE’s Lessons Learnt**, partners were invited to reflect on key insights gained through their participation in the project and describe how these lessons could inform future initiatives, practices, or institutional strategies.

Below is presented the contribution of each partner after completing the questionnaire.

3.4. FIERCE partners’ Individual Exploitation Plans

This section presents the Individual Exploitation Plans (IEPs) of each FIERCE partner, based on their responses to the questionnaire. Each IEP is structured around six thematic areas: **Strategic Interest, Exploitation, Networking and Future Collaborations, Sustainability, Replication / Transferability, and Reflections on Lessons Learnt**.

Within each thematic section, partners reflected on the **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** most relevant to their institutional goals and contexts. Rather than addressing each KER in isolation, the responses are integrated into the thematic categories, providing a coherent narrative of how each partner intends to build upon the FIERCE project outcomes in alignment with their own mission and sector-specific priorities.

3.4.1. Academic and Research Institutions Partners

3.4.1.1. Individual Exploitation Plan - Aalborg University (AAU)

Aalborg University, based in Denmark, has previously worked on European research projects involving data collection (mainly interviews) among politicians, policymakers, feminist and migrant subjects and movements, as well as with radical right actors. Participating in FIERCE, AAU facilitated the process of

setting up a framework for the cross-country comparative analysis of feminist and antifeminist movements across Europe but also feminist innovations through co-creation labs. The Aalborg University team contributed to bridging the divide between academic research and democracy in action through cooperation with feminist movements.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how AAU intends to sustain and further develop the FIERCE results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

Aalborg University aims to embed FIERCE's results into its core activities across teaching, research, and institutional development. The team will refer to the **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** in future academic work, drawing on its conceptual formulations and empirically grounded distinctions for both research and dissemination. The **Transnational Feminist Network** offers valuable opportunities to maintain contacts at the transnational level and learn from the collaborative knowledge production between academics and activists, particularly through co-participation activities. The FIERCE Action organized by The Center for Violence Prevention in Aalborg, Denmark, included a series of different activities during the annual campaign 'Orange Days' in the city about preventing and combating Gender Based Violence. After the FIERCE Action, AAU continues to collaborate with The Center for Violence Prevention and they are planning new activities for this year's 'Orange Days' in Aalborg. They expect the collaboration to continue in the coming years as well. **FIERCE's training material** is considered a useful tool for teaching and will be integrated into the Global Gender Studies module within the MA programme in International Relations. AAU is also interested in exploring the results of the **FIERCE Actions** and drawing inspiration from their knowledge outputs. The Danish **FIERCE National Lab** has led to the creation of a unique network among disability, ethnic minority, LGBTQ+, and feminist organisations; AAU intends to remain connected to this network, support its continuation, and explore potential future collaborations based on the lab's themes. Regarding the **Scientific Publications**, AAU has already contributed to two anthologies and several co-authored articles, which are now part of its dissemination strategy and may also be used in teaching. These publications offer strong examples of FIERCE's comparative research and are seen as a concrete academic output of high value. **FIERCE's Communication Material** will continue to be referenced to highlight the project as an exemplary Horizon Europe initiative in both academic and public settings, including through podcasts and social media.

2. Exploitation

FIERCE's outcomes have contributed meaningfully to enhancing Aalborg University's academic and professional capacities, particularly in research, teaching, and institutional collaboration. **FIERCE's conceptual framework** has helped nuance AAU's research approaches to feminist and anti-feminist movements and to better target emerging issues in future research projects and academic publications. It is also directly applicable to teaching, particularly within the elective module *Global Gender Studies* in the Master's programme in International Relations. Through the **Transnational Feminist Network**, AAU became more aware of national and transnational activities in the field, as well as the varying organisational needs and modes of collaboration across borders. This exposure has deepened their understanding of collaborative feminist knowledge production. The **FIERCE Action** in Denmark organised in collaboration with the Centre for Violence Prevention in Aalborg, was part of the annual "Orange

Days" campaign focused on gender-based violence. This collaboration has continued beyond the project's timeline, with new activities already being planned for this year's campaign and expectations for future joint initiatives. The **National Lab** methodology has significantly strengthened personal and institutional connections with a range of organisations working on social justice. This has laid the foundation for future interdisciplinary and community-based collaborations. In terms of **Scientific publications** AAU's participation in the co-authoring of book chapters and articles has expanded their capacity to publish collaboratively across universities and NGOs, enhancing both the visibility and impact of FIERCE's findings. Finally, **FIERCE's communication material** has played a key role in the external dissemination of AAU's work within FIERCE. The professional visual identity and content of the project - especially the website and graphics - have facilitated presentations and strengthened the credibility of FIERCE in academic and public contexts.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The FIERCE project has significantly contributed to expanding Aalborg University's institutional and interdisciplinary networks, both within Denmark and across Europe. The **conceptual framework** facilitated interdisciplinary collaboration with colleagues and supported successful applications for new Horizon-funded projects, such as *YOU-DARE*. It also strengthened local and national networks, including partnerships with GINAAU, the Gender and Intersectionality Network at Aalborg University, and a national coalition including scholars, NGOs, and politicians collaborating on combating the anti-gender movement. The **Transnational Feminist Network** opened new pathways for international engagement, offering opportunities to expand beyond the European context and explore collaborations with feminist initiatives in countries like the US and Canada. **Project's training material** serves as a valuable reference when reaching out to educational platforms. It offers a solid baseline for similar activities in future Horizon Europe projects, enabling AAU to position itself as a proactive knowledge-sharing partner. The Danish **FIERCE Action** served as a springboard for ongoing cooperation with local actors, especially around the annual *Orange Days* campaign focused on gender-based violence. Additionally, the networks developed during the National Lab have provided a foundation for future project applications related to intersectionality, such as the intersection of gender and disability. The co-creation methodology of **National Labs** has also expanded AAU's research networks. The relationships built during this process are expected to lead to future research collaborations, funding applications, and shared dissemination activities with partner organisations. Participation in the project's **scientific publication efforts** has already contributed to the successful application of the Horizon Europe project *YOU-DARE (HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-05, 101178147)*, demonstrating how FIERCE has laid the groundwork for continued collaborative research at the European level.

4. Sustainability

Aalborg University is committed to ensuring that FIERCE's results continue generating value beyond the project's formal conclusion, both within the institution and through extended collaborations. The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will support long-term engagement with disability organisations, feminist groups, and charities, especially in initiatives focusing on intersectionality. It also enables AAU to continue building synergies with other national and international research projects, such as *INSPIRE*, *CCINDLE*, *PUSHBACKLASH*, and *RESIST*, sustaining the knowledge and alliances formed through FIERCE.

The **Transnational Feminist Network** offers a strong foundation for ongoing activism-research collaboration. To consolidate this network, AAU plans to apply for COST Action funding, ensuring its continued operation and growth across European and international contexts. The Danish **FIERCE Action** held during the 2024 *Orange Days* is envisioned as a lasting annual initiative. It will serve as a blueprint for future local campaigns on gender-based violence. A notable sustainability success is the integration of bystander workshop materials - created through the national lab - by the *Everyday Sexism Project Denmark*, which continues to run these workshops across Danish high schools using FIERCE-generated content focused on sexism against minorities from an intersectional perspective. Finally, the *co-creation methodology* and outcomes from the **National Labs** have lasting value. The network of organisations engaged through the lab is expected to foster further collaborations and inspire new forms of activism, particularly around intersectional issues affecting feminist, LGBTQ+, and other social justice movements.

5. Replication / Transferability

Aalborg University identifies strong potential for adapting several FIERCE outcomes across different contexts and initiatives. The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** is already being drawn upon in the new Horizon project YOU-DARE, particularly to explore intersections between masculinity and far-right gendered narratives. Beyond academic research, the conceptual tools and knowledge produced by FIERCE are also being considered for practical applications, such as informing gender equality plans and strategic development work within institutions like universities and public administrations. The **FIERCE Actions** carried out offer versatile examples for replication. Specifically, the inclusion of survivors of gender-based violence and the integration of theatrical elements into activism are approaches that - if thoughtfully adapted - could be transferred to other cultural and national contexts. The bystander workshop developed through the Danish National Lab also holds transferable value: it provides a replicable model for engaging broader audiences, beyond youth, in proactive strategies to address gender-based violence and intersectional sexism. The **National Labs'** co-creation methodology and thematic focus likewise demonstrate replicability. The intersectional approach - centering on how sexism uniquely affects minorities - can inspire new civil society coalitions and inform the development of new policy proposals in the field of gender-based violence based on an intersectional lens.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the AAU FIERCE Team

“Through the FIERCE project, we have gained in-depth practical knowledge on participatory action-research and so-called ‘academic activism’ through the organization of the national labs and the FIERCE Actions. These activities have also significantly contributed to strengthening our knowledge about networks and possibilities for future collaborations, highlighting a key lesson in prioritizing this kind of research. Furthermore, as scientific coordinators, the FIERCE project has provided us with several key lessons on the vital importance of securing the scientific quality at every step of our work, which requires not only reactive but also proactive coordination to ensure both a consistent and a continuous knowledge production at high academic standard. Finally, another key lesson is that publication plans ought to be discussed and concretized as soon as possible in the project duration, so that most of the publications do not have to be produced and published only towards the end of the project. This means finding a balance between knowledge sharing and empirical data sampling in the beginning and publication goals. In the FIERCE project, particularly the WP3 has provided the occasion for concretizing most of the publication plans with the aim of producing a significant number of academic publications

before the project end. This is a consideration that can, and will, be applied to not just other Horizon projects, but new long-term research projects in general.”

3.4.1.2. Individual Exploitation Plan - University of Gdansk (UG)

The University of Gdańsk (UG), based in Poland, has a highly experienced FIERCE team specialising in the study of feminist movements. The team has established strong ties with the local NGO Fundacja Zatoka, as well as with other civil society organisations in Gdańsk. They have participated in several research and social projects funded by the Gdańsk municipality, provided auditing services, and engaged actively in networking events. These collaborations have also fostered close connections with regional authorities and municipalities across the Tri-City area—Gdańsk, Sopot, and Gdynia. As part of the FIERCE project, the UG team collected data for the Polish case study and contributed to all stages of the project. The project’s practical orientation and the co-creation of knowledge with activists have opened new pathways for sociology in Gdańsk, reinforcing its role in addressing contemporary social challenges.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how UG intends to sustain and further develop the FIERCE results beyond the project’s completion.

1. Strategic Interest

The University of Gdańsk plans to strategically embed FIERCE’s results across its research, teaching, and engagement activities. The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will support the design and implementation of individual publication strategies and overall development planning within the department. The **Transnational Feminist Network** offers valuable opportunities for future collaborations, enabling its integration into upcoming project proposals and COST Action applications. The **FIERCE training material** will be incorporated into NGO-linked seminars and published as an open-access online course aimed at feminist activists, expanding outreach and visibility. Similarly, elements from the **FIERCE Actions** will be used as supplementary materials in academic seminar discussions. The concept behind the **National Labs** resonates with the work of the university’s own Social Movements Lab and is expected to inspire an expansion of its activities beyond traditional academic functions. In terms of research, the **Scientific Publications** derived from FIERCE will inform multiple upcoming publications within the department and contribute to joint articles and edited volumes. This will enhance the visibility of Gender Studies and support researchers’ career development across departments. The **FIERCE Communication Materials** - including stickers, podcasts, and blog posts - are highly useful both as teaching tools and as a means of documenting and showcasing the university’s involvement in the project. Lastly, the **Policy Toolkit** offers essential learning on how to formulate practically oriented and engaged research outputs. The skills acquired through this KER will inform future research initiatives and reflect a crucial dimension of social movement studies: the interface between activism and policymaking.

2. Exploitation

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will inform future research projects and methodological courses, particularly those focused on applied or participatory methods, helping to address gaps identified during FIERCE. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has strengthened ties between academia and civil society, supporting more collaborative knowledge production. **FIERCE’s Training Material** will be used in classrooms and student clubs, offering practical resources for feminist education. Among the **FIERCE**

Actions, the self-defence manual stands out as particularly relevant, although adaptations may be required to align with local legal frameworks. The experience of the **FIERCE National Labs** will be leveraged to expand the activities of UG's existing Social Movements Lab and incorporated into teaching participatory methods. The lab manuals, in particular, offer useful tools for students interested in facilitating workshops and events. **Scientific Publications** will be made available through institutional repositories and personal academic websites, increasing visibility among both academic peers and activists, where credibility and trust are key. Finally, **FIERCE's Communication Material**, including stickers, podcasts, and blog posts, will continue to serve as educational content and a record of project activities. The **Policy Toolkit** provided essential insights into the formulation of engaged and practically oriented outputs. This learning will be exploited in future research projects, where the ability to develop policy-relevant tools is increasingly required. Moreover, it aligns with core concerns in social movement studies, particularly regarding the interface between social movements and policymaking.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The University of Gdańsk plans to build on FIERCE's collaborations to expand its academic and activist networks. The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** has already supported new partnerships within the consortium, including Horizon and COST proposals, with activist collaboration as a key strength. The **Transnational Feminist Network** helped strengthen ties between movements and NGOs, broadening the research base for future projects. **FIERCE's Training Material** will be shared across educational and activist groups, supporting outreach and future joint initiatives. Outputs from the **FIERCE Actions** will serve as blueprints for future collaborations and activities with other networks. Through the **FIERCE National Labs**, joint publications with activist participants have already begun, deepening academia–activism cooperation. **Scientific Publications** based on FIERCE data will foster ongoing collaborations and enhance the visibility of Gender Studies research across institutions. **FIERCE's Communication Material** continues to support outreach, teaching, and documentation of project work. The **Policy Toolkit** experience will inform future research proposals requiring hands-on, policy-relevant outputs, reinforcing the role of academia in democratic innovation.

4. Sustainability

At the University of Gdańsk, FIERCE's outcomes will be sustained through ongoing research, institutional learning, and extended academic engagement. **FIERCE's Conceptual Framework** will continue to inform academic work through the utilization of collected data in future publications. The project also served as practical training for university administration in managing large-scale research initiatives. **The Transnational Feminist Network** will be maintained and further mobilised for new project applications and external funding opportunities. **FIERCE's Training Material** will be developed and adjusted to meet evolving academic and activist needs. **Scientific Publications** will remain accessible via academic repositories and personal research platforms, ensuring visibility across academic and activist audiences. These outputs will contribute to career development and help consolidate Social Movement Studies within the institution. **FIERCE's Communication Material** will continue to support teaching, public engagement, and visibility of the project's impact, through formats such as stickers, podcasts, and blog posts. Finally, **the Policy Toolkit** represents an essential takeaway. As research increasingly demands practical application, the skills gained in policy formulation will be integrated into future projects. This

aligns with the broader goals of social movement studies, particularly the intersections between activism and policymaking.

5. Replication / Transferability

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** offers valuable insights that can be adapted across future research contexts. Participation in FIERCE-related networks enables collaboration under various banners beyond the academic institution, expanding the framework's reach. While the **Transnational Feminist Network** is not directly sustained by the university, it provides opportunities to invite activists to student events, fostering practical engagement and dialogue between academia and civil society. The **FIERCE training material** can be further developed and adapted to meet diverse needs, offering flexible tools for different educational settings and communities. The **FIERCE Actions** resources have potential for replication in other contexts, provided they are adapted to align with local legal and cultural frameworks. The methodology and experience of the **National Labs** will certainly be reused in future research projects and proposals, with necessary adjustments to context, topic, and audience. The **scientific publications** stemming from FIERCE will inform both internal and collaborative academic work. They will be made accessible through repositories and personal websites to increase visibility and trust across academic and activist audiences.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the UG FIERCE Team

"The main lesson learned mainly from the Polish FIERCE Labs was that there is a gap between scholarship and activists in Poland. One of the issues the activists pointed out was the problematic access to the history of the movement. Activists with longer experience in the movement claimed that contemporary activists have the same discussions they had years ago. Here, scholarships would be able to fill in this gap by documenting the actions and developments of the movement. Another lesson learned was that there is a need and will to co-create knowledge on social movements and their actions and internal discussions, with the activists being open to co-authoring articles and participating in other research-related activities."

3.4.1.3. Individual Exploitation Plan - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) based in Greece, participated in FIERCE through its Department of Political Sciences, which provides theoretical and empirical tools for analysing relations, ideologies, and policies to support decision-making in the public sphere. The AUTH team has a great expertise in feminist movements from an intersectional point of view and was actively involved in every stage of the project - from producing timely, up-to-date knowledge on European anti-gender, anti-feminist, and feminist movements, to organising co-creation lab activities with feminist activists, NGOs, political representatives, and other Greek social actors. These efforts aimed at co-producing knowledge and developing policy recommendations to strengthen gender equality and democratic participation.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how AUTH intends to sustain and further develop the FIERCE results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) will integrate FIERCE's outcomes into research, teaching, and institutional activities across departments. The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will further inform research and publications, undergraduate and postgraduate teaching, and will be disseminated through seminars, conferences, and academic supervision. The **Transnational Feminist Network** will be embedded in research and teaching, particularly in feminist theory and social movements courses. Internal workshops and interdisciplinary dialogues - led by the Gender Equality Committee and research labs - will ensure continued reflection on feminist strategies in response to anti-gender and far-right politics. The **FIERCE training material** will be used in departmental seminars and workshops, including a scheduled seminar at the School of Political Sciences in late 2025 - early 2026, with potential expansion to other faculties such as Fine Arts. The **FIERCE Actions** offer a model for applied feminist research and will shape fieldwork-based modules emphasizing decentralised collaboration and local knowledge. Engagements in Karditsa, Volos, and Rethymno will serve as case studies to support feminist pedagogies and postgraduate training. AUTH plans to reuse the **FIERCE National Labs** methodology through future seminars and workshops, with the first dissemination scheduled for late 2025. The **scientific publications** will support further research, student theses, academic presentations, and contribute to the department's research profile for evaluation and funding purposes. Finally, the **communication material** will support joint academic-civil society narratives, amplifying alternative feminist perspectives and showcasing collaborations via digital platforms. Online joint statements with civil society partners can showcase the project's overall impact and collaborations, bringing together academia and public actors. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** will support awareness-raising and foster dialogue through workshops, campaigns, and training initiatives. It will provide the foundation for future research proposals and inspire doctoral and postdoctoral projects. By involving additional faculties - such as media, education, sociology, and management - AUTH aims to institutionalise gender both as a lens for analysis and as a framework for future research. Dissemination of findings will help open channels to ministries and professional associations, expanding the project's impact and contributing to long-term policy engagement.

2. Exploitation

At AUTH, FIERCE's results are already enhancing both academic and civic practice. The **Conceptual Framework** has contributed to new publications and will inform future research and teaching across multiple political science domains. It also lays the groundwork for future research proposals. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has offered valuable insights into feminist and anti-feminist dynamics, which AUTH plans to integrate into European project proposals and academic modules—such as a forthcoming course on feminist resistance in comparative perspective. These insights also support the development of participatory teaching practices and civic training materials. The **FIERCE training material** can be used to build cross-departmental collaborations and engage feminist collectives and the Gender Equality Committee. Translation into Greek will be essential for broader impact. The **FIERCE Actions** have introduced participatory research models grounded in trust-based relationships and feedback loops with feminist communities. These models will now be integrated into fieldwork approaches and outreach strategies, especially for underrepresented areas. The **National Labs** methodology supports AUTH's ongoing refinement of co-creation practices and will be incorporated into new research, including an upcoming project on grassroots democratic cooperatives. The **Scientific**

Publications broaden the PI's and the research team's expertise in feminist and anti-gender mobilizations in Greece, enriching their academic profiles and strengthening the department's research diversity. **Communication Material**, such as activist interviews and campaign content, has opened new channels for academic-community exchange. These materials enhance public engagement and will continue to be shared via open-access platforms to support broader community use. Lastly, the **Policy Toolkit** has sharpened AUTH's capacity to design impactful public dialogues and create training tools around rights-based advocacy, democratic participation, and gender sensitivity. These approaches will inform future consulting services, research projects, and course offerings.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The **Conceptual Framework** has already helped expand AUTH's interdisciplinary connections, notably through the 2025 FIERCE Actions at the Universities of Crete and Thessaly. These activities initiated new networks between political scientists and scholars in fields such as architecture and art, all engaged by gendered perspectives. The **Transnational Feminist Network** provides a foundation for lasting collaborations across institutions and disciplines. AUTH will maintain active ties through workshops, conferences, and shared initiatives, using the network as a springboard for new Horizon Europe proposals on anti-gender movements, democratic innovation, and intersectional justice - that focuses on feminist research centres in Southern and Eastern Europe, strengthening ties with local feminist collectives and NGOs through knowledge-sharing initiatives and co-hosted events. The **FIERCE training material** will be shared with departments and collectives within and beyond AUTH, especially the Gender Equality Committee and feminist NGOs. To maximise accessibility, translation into Greek has to be prioritised. The **FIERCE Actions** fostered horizontal, grassroots-oriented links with feminist centres and local collectives, enabling AUTH to act as a connector between community actors and international research infrastructures. These networks are already inspiring new collaborations for joint publications, events, and policy reports. The **National Labs** have strengthened AUTH's ties with researchers, NGOs, and civil society actors. Current discussions with a feminist research centre, an NGO, and individual researchers are paving the way for joint research proposals and shared activities. The **Scientific Publications** will be crucial for consolidating research networks and collaborations with activists in the fields of feminism-antifeminism and can provide a solid basis for AUTH researchers' participation in new international research projects in these particular areas. Finally, the **Communication Material** offers novel insights in conjunction with digital tools for mapping and analyzing movement dynamics or discourse. Campaigns in mainstream media outlets and online portals can be designed in ways that take into account cultural and societal pressures in terms of their gender, drawing on materials from the Fierce national labs and actions. Explanatory notes for methodologies and tools can be presented through various media platforms and websites, fostering knowledge exchange and peer support among feminist activists, researchers, and policymakers. Co-organized workshops, seminars, and webinars can draw the attention of researchers or activists from related fields. The **Policy Toolkit** experience has created informal bridges within the network, fostering shared recognition and collective learning. It offers a resource for staff training, workshops, and innovation in feminist organisational culture.

4. Sustainability

The **Conceptual Framework** will be sustained through continued research, teaching, supervision, and collaborations within and beyond AUTH, embedding the project's insights into long-term academic activity. The **Transnational Feminist Network** will remain an active resource, integrated into publications, open-access teaching materials, and ongoing research. AUTH plans to host webinars and roundtables under its Gender Equality Plan and apply for national funding to support the network's role in community training and participatory action research. The **FIERCE Action** partnerships will continue through ongoing communication and shared initiatives. Some collaborators have already expressed interest in contributing to open-access resources and future university-hosted educational programmes. The **Scientific Publications** will have lasting value through reuse in teaching, further research, and integration into the department's academic output and funding strategies. The **Communication Material** will be available through academic repositories, project partner platforms, and activist networks, ensuring wide and continued dissemination. These materials can support new analyses, classroom use, and inspire independent initiatives among students and researchers. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** will inform future policy dialogues, advocacy, and community-based training. The relationships built during FIERCE between academia and civil society will foster future collaborations, with the toolkit methodology empowering a new generation of researchers and activists to continue this work and trigger engagement with regional authorities or local NGOs.

5. Replication / Transferability

The **Conceptual Framework** has already been applied across disciplines such as architecture, environmental studies, degrowth, and post-colonial studies. It holds high potential for interdisciplinary replication, with collaborations initiated through FIERCE expected to continue post-project. The **Transnational Feminist Network** is highly adaptable and can be extended to departments like Media Studies, Education, and Law, as well as sectors such as public policy and civil society. Its multidimensional, bottom-up structure allows it to be tailored to national and institutional contexts, especially where anti-feminist backlash is prominent, requiring only minor adjustments. The **Training Material** will be translated into Greek and adapted for use by the AUTH Gender Equality Committee, other departments, and grassroots collectives. Adjustments will reflect the needs and audiences of each context, ensuring relevance and accessibility. The **FIERCE Actions** methodology is especially well-suited for adaptation in diverse socio-political contexts where marginalised groups or grassroots actors are active. One of its most transferable elements is the methodology developed during the National Labs and FIERCE Action in Greece, which provides concrete tools for working with collectives grounded in horizontal decision-making, feminist ethics of care, and democratic collaboration. This approach avoids rigid moderation structures and instead fosters dialogue-based, non-hierarchical exchanges, making it ideal for contexts where power imbalances must be consciously dismantled. The **FIERCE Labs** methodology will be shared in open-access formats to support replication by academic institutions and civil society. It can be used in graduate courses and adapted by NGOs and activist groups to foster synergies between research and grassroots action. AUTH's FIERCE **scientific publications** can certainly become resources and references for further research on contemporary Greek feminism-antifeminism in a variety of disciplines, from political science and sociology to Gender Studies, journalism and social anthropology as they break new ground and provide new insights in their fields of inquiry. Among others, the AUTH team has produced the first academic publication on the antifeminist Greek 'Fathers'

movement’ which brought about an important legislative reform in Family Law that is detrimental to women’s rights and struggle against gender-based violence. The FIERCE **Communication Material** can inspire local organisations to establish their own advocacy networks and adapt FIERCE’s participatory strategies. Materials and methodologies can be tailored to different socio-political contexts while maintaining FIERCE’s core values. AUTH and other partners may offer mentorship to new groups replicating the model, fostering transnational alliances for gender equality and countering anti-gender movements.

6. FIERCE’s Lessons Learnt by the AUTH FIERCE Team

“Engagement with the feminist and LGBTQIA+ movement in Greece (2010–2023) has revealed distinct features that can inform academic research, teaching, and collaboration with civil society:

- *A new feminist mode of mobilising, organising, and doing politics has emerged, moving away from macho, aggressive communication styles. Greater care, time, and respect are now given to participants, allowing them to express themselves without fear of dismissal.*
- *Since 2009, there has been a growing interaction between academia, queer theory, and LGBTQIA+ communities. Queer and gender issues have entered the vocabulary of radical left and anti-authoritarian spaces, fostering convergence between feminists and LGBTQIA+ groups. This interaction has nourished intersectional approaches that connect class, gender, and race, with transfeminism becoming a key development. Tensions persist between legalistic, state-centred feminisms and movement-based approaches, as well as between deconstructionist/queer and essentialist feminisms, transfeminists and TERFs.*
- *From the mid-2010s onwards, the digital sphere became a crucial platform for feminist activism, blending online campaigning with street mobilisation.*
- *The feminist movement amplifies its influence by engaging in “ants’ work” within education, labour, and broader society. Conversations grounded in equality, solidarity, and empathy, especially with young people, help raise consciousness and cultivate new forms of common sense. The internet, political events, and publications remain vital tools for reaching wider audiences.*
- *LGBTQIA+ voices highlight two pressing needs: further institutional reforms to secure rights and protections in health, labour, and education, and societal education on gender and sexual expression, starting from primary schools.”*

3.4.1.4. Individual Exploitation Plan - University of Ljubljana (UL)

University of Ljubljana (UL), based in Slovenia, is the country’s oldest and largest university, founded in 1919. Its Faculty of Arts has a longstanding tradition of research in gender studies and is recognised as a hub for critical thinking. The FIERCE team at UL engages in scientific research and advocacy to promote an open society rooted in equality, solidarity, human rights, and the rule of law. With extensive expertise on gender issues and social exclusion, including anti-gender attitudes, the team contributes to projects addressing pressing social and political challenges. Within FIERCE, UL sought to deepen the understanding of the emergence and successes of anti-gender and anti-feminist movements in Europe.

The project provided an excellent opportunity to generate new knowledge in gender studies and to develop effective feminist tools for strengthening democratic practices.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how UL intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

At the University of Ljubljana (UL), the results of the FIERCE project are set to become an integral part of the team's research, teaching, and public engagement strategy. The **Conceptual Framework on feminism and antifeminism movement analysis**, developed in FIERCE, will serve as a strategic foundation for the work of the research group *Problems of Autonomy and Identities at the Time of Globalisation* at the Faculty of Arts. The conceptual foundation laid by this result will be instrumental in fostering continuity between the FIERCE project and new academic and collaborative initiatives, aligning the group's future activities with a critical, feminist, and democratic research agenda. It will shape new research agendas, particularly on anti-gender mobilizations, democratic backsliding, and the role of knowledge production in contemporary society, while also deepening theoretical inquiries and informing empirical work in national and transnational contexts. The **Transnational Feminist Network** established through FIERCE will be used to strengthen collaboration with feminist organisations, activists, and practitioners across diverse national settings. This network provides a valuable infrastructure for exchanging practical strategies and activist tools, coordinating joint initiatives such as public events, awareness campaigns, and trainings in response to threats to gender equality and democratic participation. The **FIERCE training materials** will also enhance UL's teaching and mentoring efforts, particularly in courses on feminist theory, social movements, and political sociology. These resources bridge academic and activist knowledge, making them suitable for integration into both classroom settings and independent study modules. Students will be encouraged to engage with the material as an example of non-hierarchical feminist pedagogy. As part of **FIERCE Actions**, UL's participation in the *Exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia* - now also available online - will remain a key tool for feminist public engagement and reaching audiences outside academic settings. This FIERCE Action reflects UL's broader approach to connecting research with public memory and political education, and it will be showcased at universities, high schools, and cultural or activist events, extending its reach beyond academia. The co-creation methodology developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** will serve as a foundation for future initiatives linking academic research with feminist organising. This approach fits closely with UL's broader aim of strengthening socially engaged research practices and building collaborations with activists, NGOs, and community-based groups. UL plans to apply this method when developing new projects, especially those that require public engagement or collaboration across sectors. The **scientific research and publications** are one of the main activities of UL's research group. The produced articles and texts during the FIERCE project have strengthened UL's overall research agenda and they are already used to shape new research questions, to develop their conceptual framework further, and when preparing new project proposals. These publications are already part of their teaching, and they reference them in lectures and course materials. They also help demonstrate the international relevance of UL's work and their ongoing cooperation with partners across Europe. The **communication materials** produced during FIERCE have reinforced UL's research agenda and public outreach. These outputs will continue to shape teaching materials, presentations and

public engagement. The videos, podcasts, and campaign visuals are a helpful tool as they demonstrate how feminist knowledge can be shared outside of academic formats and also useful in lectures, especially when the goal is to bring in activist voices or present current feminist struggles in a way that's more accessible. The **Policy Toolkit** will also support UL's engagement with policymakers and political actors, particularly in advocating for gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights in Slovenia's institutional and political spheres. With parliamentary elections coming up in Slovenia next year, it will be especially useful to support efforts to include feminist demands in political party programs and campaign debates. The toolkit offers concrete and clearly formulated arguments that can be used to push for gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights in institutional settings.

2. Exploitation

The **Conceptual Framework** developed has provided a strong foundation for integrating analyses of feminist and antifeminist movements into UL's broader research on social inequalities. It is already embedded in the methodological design of new research proposals and has informed updates to undergraduate and postgraduate teaching content. By focusing on the dynamics of political backlash, the framework has helped fill conceptual and empirical gaps, especially regarding anti-gender discourse in various institutional settings. It also supports the creation of new seminar topics and elective courses while serving as a reference point for shaping future interdisciplinary research collaborations. Practically, it has proven valuable for structuring academic workshops and public events that bridge research and public engagement. The **Transnational Feminist Network** established through FIERCE has strengthened UL's capacity to engage with feminist actors and movements beyond academia. This has been particularly useful for developing research responsive to real-time political dynamics and for introducing activist-informed approaches in new projects addressing anti-gender mobilizations and democratic innovation. Ongoing interactions with network members have enabled UL to identify shared challenges, develop comparative perspectives, and refine teaching content—particularly in courses on social movements, citizenship, and feminist theory. The network has also inspired joint initiatives and facilitated the early stages of new project proposals. The **Training Material** has expanded UL's teaching tools, connecting theoretical insights with activist experience. By integrating activist voices alongside academic lectures, it broadens the perspectives offered to students and encourages methodological reflection in feminist epistemology and knowledge production courses. It also supports the development of new course content and reinforces the integration of social relevance into teaching practice. The **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia, created a powerful format for making academic research accessible and politically meaningful to wider audiences. This initiative bridged research, activism, and education while strengthening UL's capacity to plan and implement collaborative, interdisciplinary, and publicly engaged projects. The **National Labs** demonstrated how to design spaces for dialogue that balance academic and non-academic voices while maintaining a shared focus on outcomes—be it a joint analysis, policy proposal, or public statement. This approach has enhanced UL's facilitation skills and is now considered valuable for both future research and participatory assignments with students. The **Scientific Publications** produced within FIERCE have positioned UL's work within international debates, enriching their research agenda and inspiring new ideas - particularly around anti-gender mobilizations and democratic innovation. These

outputs are already used in course content and serve as examples of how critical theory and empirical research can effectively intersect.

The **Communication Materials** have informed UL's approach to public engagement, offering accessible ways to communicate feminist ideas. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** has supported UL in translating critical analysis into actionable political proposals. It strengthened their ability to contribute to public debates in ways that are both grounded in feminist research and accessible to broader audiences. The toolkit also provides a shared structure for collaboration with advocacy organizations and public institutions.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The **Conceptual Framework** developed through FIERCE will remain central to UL's research and teaching. It is already shaping new project proposals, including Horizon Europe and COST applications, and enriching course content at undergraduate and postgraduate levels. The framework provides a foundation for future collaborations with FIERCE partners and beyond, supporting interdisciplinary and comparative studies on feminist and anti-gender mobilizations. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has strengthened ties with academic and civil society actors across Europe, fostering partnerships for joint research, advocacy, and community-based initiatives. It provides a platform for interdisciplinary dialogue and supports the development of impact-oriented projects that address democratic backsliding and gender justice. The **Training Material** serves as a practical tool for engaging both academic and non-academic audiences. It supports collaborations with NGOs and feminist groups for workshops and civic education initiatives while also enriching UL's teaching and mentoring practices. The **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the exhibition on reproductive rights, created new connections with feminist organizations, educators, and cultural workers. Its online format ensures sustained visibility and serves as a catalyst for future partnerships at national and international levels. The **FIERCE Labs** brought grassroots and academic actors into dialogue, fostering networks based on shared values. UL plans to replicate this participatory format in future projects to encourage cross-border cooperation and collective problem-solving. **Scientific Publications** have enhanced UL's visibility and attracted interest from potential collaborators. They support future project development and demonstrate the team's expertise on feminist movements and democratic innovation. **Communication Materials** offer accessible tools for outreach, particularly to NGOs and activists. Short videos and campaign content have been used effectively in public events and collaborative planning, helping initiate partnerships and inspire joint initiatives. The **Policy Toolkit** facilitates engagement with policymakers and advocacy groups. It supports coalition-building around feminist priorities and highlights the connection between local actions and broader transnational struggles. It can also be used by UL to open conversations with new partners. Since it reflects the work of a transnational feminist project, it also helps show where UL's proposals come from and how they connect to broader struggles across Europe.

4. Sustainability

The **conceptual framework** will continue to be developed and applied in the context of future research projects, including new Horizon Europe applications and national funding schemes. It is already being used in academic activities, such as course design and student supervision, and will remain part of teaching at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels. UL provides institutional infrastructure to support research and international collaboration, including administrative and project development

assistance. Members of the research group will continue to work on refining and expanding the framework based on new empirical findings and debates. Collaboration with partners from the FIERCE network and beyond will help ensure the continued relevance of the framework and its integration into comparative and interdisciplinary work. The framework's value lies in its adaptability to different political contexts, which allows for its long-term use and gradual evolution. The **transnational feminist network** will also continue to generate value, as many of the relationships built are already active outside the formal FIERCE structure. These contacts foster ongoing collaboration through joint initiatives, informal exchanges, and rapid coordination in moments of political urgency, sustaining a vibrant space for knowledge-sharing and solidarity. The exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia, developed as part of **FIERCE Actions**, remains accessible online and continues to serve as a tool for public engagement and educational events without requiring additional resources. Similarly, the **co-creation methodology** piloted in the FIERCE Labs has been adopted in smaller-scale workshops and internal meetings and will remain part of UL's approach to participatory, socially engaged research. **Scientific publications** produced during the project are stored in institutional repositories and have already been integrated into teaching, supervision, and new research development. They continue to provide a conceptual foundation for academic work and public discourse. The **project's communication materials**, widely accessible online, are now part of UL's teaching resources and will inform future outreach initiatives by offering practical examples of how to present feminist knowledge to broader audiences. Finally, the **policy toolkit** is a valuable resource for engaging policymakers, advocacy groups, and institutional stakeholders, particularly in the context of upcoming elections or gender justice campaigns. Its clear, accessible format makes it suitable for adaptation and reuse in UL's future projects and public or policy interventions, ensuring that the lessons of FIERCE continue to influence policy dialogues.

5. Replication / Transferability

The **conceptual framework** developed through FIERCE is highly adaptable and can be applied across disciplines in UL such as sociology, political science, anthropology, cultural studies, and education. Its analytical flexibility allows integration into research and teaching in diverse departments, particularly those addressing democracy, political ideologies, or knowledge production. Beyond academia, it has strong potential for NGO and policy work, supporting strategies to counter anti-gender discourse, civic education initiatives, and alliances between academic and activist communities. Minor contextual adjustments – such as incorporating local case studies or adapting terminology – could further enhance its relevance in different national or institutional settings, both within and outside the EU. The **transnational feminist network** offers a model for collaboration that can be replicated in other projects and contexts, especially those involving participatory methods or activist engagement. Its informal structure makes it particularly suited for fostering alliances in regions facing intensified anti-gender mobilizations. The network can also be extended to colleagues in other university departments or civic organizations, creating bridges between academic knowledge and social action. The FIERCE **training material**, hosted online, remains a valuable open educational resource. It can be used in classrooms, civic workshops, or community outreach, and adapted to local needs, including translation into Slovenian or other languages. Similarly, **the exhibition on reproductive** rights in Slovenia is readily transferable, as its online format allows for easy sharing, adaptation, and contextualization in different

cultural and political environments. The **co-creation methodology** piloted in the FIERCE Labs has broad applicability for universities, NGOs, and public institutions working on feminism, democracy, and social justice. Its flexible format allows for adjustments based on participant groups, topics, or desired outcomes, while retaining its core principle of fostering collaborative spaces that produce concrete results. Communication materials from FIERCE are also highly transferable. These outputs can be integrated into teaching, training, and community education across disciplines and countries. They provide accessible entry points for policy analysis and awareness-raising activities, and their translation or adaptation to local contexts can further increase impact. The UL team is open to sharing expertise and supporting others in applying these tools, ensuring the lessons of FIERCE continue to resonate and inspire across diverse settings.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the UL FIERCE Team

“Being part of the FIERCE project has brought a lot of new knowledge about feminist and LGBT+ organizations across Europe and helped us better understand how these movements operate, both in everyday activism and in response to political pressure. It deepened our knowledge of social movements more broadly and allowed us to see how different contexts shape strategies, alliances and tensions. We also gained valuable experience working in a structured and organized way across an international consortium, which has improved how we plan and carry out our own research and collaborations. One of the most important outcomes has been the strong network we built with other universities and NGOs. These connections have already opened space for future cooperation, from joint events to potential new projects. The exchange of methods, ideas and practices within FIERCE has sharpened our focus and reminded us of the importance of combining academic work with political engagement.”

3.4.1.5. Individual Exploitation Plan - Koç University (KU)

Koç University (KU), based in Turkey, hosts the Center for Gender Studies (KOÇ-KAM), which is dedicated to advancing gender research and practice in Turkey and beyond. As part of KOÇ-KAM and the UNESCO Chair on Gender Equality and Sustainable Development, the KU team collaborates with civil society organizations, local authorities, UNESCO, and the UN Women Europe and Central Asia Regional Office in Istanbul. Their work includes delivering training and workshops on gender-based violence and engaging in civic action and academic projects focused on women's economic empowerment, employment, and gender-sensitive approaches to collective decision-making. As a research partner in the FIERCE Project, the KU examined feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender mobilizations in Turkey, offering insights into the ongoing global clash between feminist movements and anti-gender politics. The team contributed significantly to FIERCE's mission of bridging gaps between feminist movements, civil society organizations, and policy institutions at both national and EU levels.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how KU intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

Koç University (KU) intends to embed the outcomes of the FIERCE project into its academic, research, and community engagement activities. The **Conceptual Framework** will guide future project applications, academic and non-academic publications, course designs, conferences, and outreach

efforts. The Gender Studies Center, in collaboration with the university's Gender Equality Office, plans to apply this conceptual approach in contributing to university-wide policies that promote gender equality. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has provided valuable insights into social movements, policy outcomes, and transnational collaborations, which will inform future projects and partnerships. The team will draw on this experience to strengthen their engagement with feminist actors and organizations at local, national, and international levels. The **FIERCE Training Material** will be shared with students and university staff to stimulate interest in gender issues and feminist strategies. Three of the **FIERCE Actions** were carried out in Turkey, led by civil society actors. These included internal workshops and generated notable outputs such as cartoons, news articles, a policy brief, and a mini film. The policy brief and mini film are intended to serve as key resources for fostering connections with academics, policymakers, and activists. Moreover, these outputs and their production processes will provide valuable empirical data to inform future publications. Through the **FIERCE Labs**, KU's Gender Research Center has deepened its connections with scholars and activists, laying the groundwork for new collaborations beyond the project's lifetime.

The **Scientific Publications** emerging from FIERCE have already enriched KU's research agenda. Drawing on extensive data collected through diverse methodologies, the team has completed several analyses and is preparing articles for publication, including both single-case and comparative studies. These efforts will continue to strengthen KU's role as a producer of high-quality empirical research. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** and **Communication Materials** will be shared widely within the university and with external academic and civil society organizations. These resources will support KU's ongoing mission to promote gender-sensitive approaches to research, education, and public engagement.

2. Exploitation

The **Conceptual Framework** developed in FIERCE, centered on movement-counter-movement dynamics, offers a transferable model for future projects and interdisciplinary applications for KU. It can enrich political science, sociology, and gender studies courses while fostering dialogue between researchers, policymakers, and gender equality claimants. The **Transnational Feminist Network** enhanced KU's understanding of activist agendas in other countries and strengthened ties with feminist actors abroad. By facilitating the participation of Turkish activists, the network also extended their outreach and visibility. The **FIERCE Training Material**, co-produced with activists in Turkey, provides adaptable resources for future projects and supports integration into other projects. Through **FIERCE Actions**, KU gained valuable experience in developing policy briefs and exploring film production processes. Both outputs - the policy brief and the mini film - are replicable with new content and can be used as educational tools in university courses and training programs. The **FIERCE Labs** methodology has positioned the Gender Research Center as a dynamic hub for research on feminism and democracy, helping identify knowledge gaps and generating ideas that will inform future projects, potentially involving some Lab participants. The **Scientific Publications** produced through FIERCE support career development for young scholars and reinforce the interdisciplinary character of gender studies, with comparative publications expected to achieve broad academic reach. The **FIERCE Communication Materials** help KU stand out as a research center with a strong interest and expertise in the relationship between feminism and democracy and can help expand the reach of the project outcomes to a broader

public. The Policy Toolkit is based on research outputs and in that sense, it utilizes scientific research to intervene in policy debates on gender equality and it contributes to data-based policy making.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

Throughout the FIERCE project, Koç University strengthened and expanded networks involving gender research centers, scholars, policymakers, and activists at local, national, and international levels. The **Conceptual Framework** contributed to producing new knowledge and supporting gender equality policymaking, while also inspiring the formulation of potential applications for new Horizon Europe calls. The **Transnational Feminist Network** offers a platform for fostering collaborations between academics and activists, laying the groundwork for projects with gender equality policy relevance. The **Training Material**, combining activist and researcher perspectives, has potential for community outreach beyond the university, helping attract new audiences and collaborators for future activities. The **FIERCE Actions**, developed through collective work, deepened ties with gender equality activists locally and transnationally. The policy brief, in particular, can strengthen relationships with policymakers by providing insights into what works and what does not in gender equality policies at the international level. Similarly, the **FIERCE Labs**, which convened multiple times during the project, created a sense of connection among participants and enhanced engagement with activists. The **Scientific Publications** demonstrate KU's expertise in the fields covered in the FIERCE project attracting new readers and opening doors for future research collaborations. Finally, the **Communication Materials** and the **Policy Toolkit** amplify KU's visibility as a center with a strong interest and expertise in the relationship between feminism and democracy, helping build new partnerships, inspire Horizon project ideas, and strengthen networks with activists and policymakers alike.

4. Sustainability

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will continue to inform future project applications and academic activities of KU. Drawing on the research outcomes of FIERCE, the KU team has already presented at several conferences and submitted a number of academic articles. These efforts will be sustained, with plans to join upcoming conferences and produce further publications that deepen the project's legacy. The **Transnational Feminist Network** is expected to retain its value as long as it remains active or evolves into new forms of collaboration. Over time, it could expand or give rise to different networks that build on its foundations. The **FIERCE Training Material** will continue creating impact as long as it remains accessible. It holds the potential to inspire participants to develop innovative methods and approaches to advancing gender equality within their respective fields. The outputs of the **FIERCE Actions** are also intended to remain available after the project ends, ensuring their continued relevance and use in academic, activist, and community spaces. Through the **FIERCE Labs**, KU has strengthened long-term ties with activists by working closely over an extended period. This collaboration is likely to support future collective projects and outreach initiatives involving both researchers and activists. The **Scientific Publications** produced under FIERCE serve as durable contributions to academic literature. They will continue to provide a foundation for other scholars to build upon in their own work. The **FIERCE Communication Materials** will retain value as long as they remain accessible, offering tools for disseminating feminist knowledge to wider audiences. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** will continue to be impactful as long as it is publicly available and its recommendations remain relevant within the shifting

political context of gender debates. It highlights key challenges and gaps in gender equality policymaking and proposes actionable solutions. Its value could be amplified if policymakers and stakeholders use these recommendations in practice, bridging research and policy implementation.

5. Replication / Transferability

For KU, the **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** is highly adaptable and can be applied in diverse contexts and projects beyond Europe. Given the global relevance of gender and its politics, it has potential for application in all regions of the world, though adjustments may be needed to reflect different political regimes and the role of gender in shaping socio-political grievances. The **Transnational Feminist Network** approach could also be replicated in other projects and settings, with actors and participants tailored to the specific topics and contexts involved. Similarly, the **FIERCE Training Material** lends itself to adaptation, with lesson plans and topics revised as needed for different regional and cultural realities. The **FIERCE Actions**, such as the mini film and policy brief, offer replicable formats that can incorporate activist perspectives from other countries or focus on new national case studies. The **FIERCE Labs** methodology is equally transferable; it could bring together similar or new groups in other locations or regions to explore feminist themes collaboratively. For **Scientific Publications**, KU highlights that research-oriented projects should explicitly include the production of academic outputs within their infrastructure, ideally through dedicated work packages. Lastly, the **FIERCE Communication Materials** could be replicated across projects, with content adjusted to reflect the themes and regions addressed.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the KU FIERCE Team

“FIERCE has been an ambitious project in terms of producing high quality scientific research outputs with policy impact. Its productiveness draws from various types of collaboration planned between universities and NGOs; partners from different countries; scholars, activists, and policymakers; different academic disciplines; scholars with different methodological expertise; and senior and junior scholars. Achieving a smooth collaboration across all these diversities requires labor, time as well as commitment to produce high quality work. To make collaboration across these diversities effective, extra attention to the planning of the division of labor has been required. We have gained rich experience in working through these diversities. We will benefit from these experiences in future collaborative projects.”

3.4.1.6. Individual Exploitation Plan – Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)

Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS) is a university based in Italy. The Centre on Social Movement Studies (COSMOS), housed within the Faculty of Political and Social Sciences in Florence, is a network of researchers with extensive experience in social movement research. COSMOS focuses on social movements as part of broader contentious politics, exploring their interactions with civil society organisations and institutional political actors. Within the FIERCE project, COSMOS was responsible for deepening knowledge on the claims, debates, and actions of feminist movements, examining if and how they contribute to democratic innovations. Through FIERCE, COSMOS applied its expertise on social movements and contentious politics to produce new insights that envision inclusive democratic opportunities and advance gender equality across Europe.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how SNS intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

FIERCE's **conceptual framework** will be integrated into both research and teaching activities at SNS, strengthening the focus on feminist democratic innovations and providing a structured approach to analyzing the interplay between feminism and anti-feminism in contemporary Europe. It will guide future research projects and academic publications and inform the development of seminars and advanced courses on feminist theory, social movements, and democratic backsliding. The **Transnational Feminist Network** aligns with SNS's ongoing work on feminist movements, intersectionality, and democratic innovation, serving as a platform for continuing dialogue with activists and scholars across Europe. It creates opportunities for cross-border collaboration on both research and public engagement activities, particularly on issues of gender-based violence, anti-gender backlash, and feminist strategies of resistance, while also supporting future co-teaching initiatives and guest lectures. The **FIERCE Course** will be integrated into existing academic curricula at SNS, particularly in modules on feminist movements, intersectionality, and democratic backsliding. It will also serve as supplementary material for seminars and workshops targeting both students and civil society actors. The format, which combines academic insight with activist voices, is particularly valuable for bridging theory and practice and will be highlighted in participatory teaching strategies and public engagement events. The course has already been shared with colleagues at SNS interested in gender and politics and in participatory methodologies. SNS is particularly interested in the **FIERCE Actions** focused on workshops for self-empowerment, the exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia, and the awareness-raising materials targeting LGBTQIA+ communities, such as the cartoons and the policy-related film. Since SNS contributed to the writing process of the Italian self-defense manual, there is also specific interest in that action, which was found to be extremely relevant and helpful for that constituency (in public schools) and beyond. These actions will inspire future participatory initiatives within and beyond academia, especially those targeting feminist and LGBTQIA+ mobilizations under threat. The methodologies and formats used—such as exhibitions, workshops, and creative materials—will inform co-designed educational events, public engagement activities, and activist-academic collaborations on gender-based violence, reproductive rights, and anti-gender backlash. The co-creation methodology developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** is highly relevant to SNS's work on participatory research and feminist democratic innovations. This approach will be applied to future research projects, particularly those exploring the interplay between activism, knowledge production, and policy influence. It will also inform methodologies taught in graduate-level courses and be used in the design of interactive workshops with civil society actors. Key people for collaboration might include Daniela Chironi, Emanuela Lombardo, Giulia Selmi, Vincenza Pellegrino, and Beatrice Busi. The **scientific publications** emerging from FIERCE form a key part of SNS's research dissemination strategy. They will be referenced in teaching, cited in future work, and used to strengthen theoretical and empirical foundations in ongoing research on feminist movements, anti-gender politics, and democratic backsliding. These publications also provide essential material for the development of future courses and collective publications. FIERCE's **communication material**, such as videos, podcasts, and campaign materials, will complement both academic and activist outreach activities at SNS. These materials provide accessible and engaging content that can support teaching, conference presentations, and public events, and they are valuable tools for reaching broader audiences beyond academia, especially when addressing

complex issues like democratic backsliding and anti-gender movements. The **Policy Toolkit** will serve as a reference and resource in both academic and policy-oriented work at SNS. It will be used in teaching (particularly in courses on gender, democracy, and public policy), cited in research outputs, and shared in policy dialogues. It will also inform trainings and advisory activities with institutions and civil society actors seeking practical tools to defend and advance gender and LGBTQ+ rights.

2. Exploitation

FIERCE's **conceptual framework** has already helped SNS identify gaps in existing literature and inspired new research outputs in areas such as the conflictual engagement between feminist movements and institutions, feminist democratic innovations, and intersectionality in public policy. It also enriches pedagogical approaches by offering an updated, intersectional, and politically grounded tool to analyze current developments. The framework will be incorporated into syllabi, graduate supervision, and may inspire new participatory projects or training sessions for activists and institutions. It has already inspired the writing of a new project proposal for the Fondo Italiano per la Scienza (FIS) call, focusing on feminist democratic innovations in the field of gender-based violence. The **Transnational Feminist Network** strengthens SNS's ability to co-design research with activists and practitioners, ensuring that outputs are grounded in real-world needs and perspectives. It contributes to professional development through knowledge exchange, peer feedback, and the potential to build interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral methodologies. The network also supports the translation of research into practice by facilitating connections with feminist organizations engaged in advocacy and policy work. The **FIERCE Course** supports innovation in pedagogy at SNS by modeling a horizontal, inclusive learning structure. It enhances teaching methods through multimedia content grounded in current feminist struggles and allows for more interactive and reflective learning experiences. The course also addresses content gaps by focusing on emerging forms of anti-gender backlash, feminist resistance, and transnational solidarity—topics often underrepresented in traditional academic materials. **FIERCE Actions** offer concrete models for integrating cultural production, advocacy, and political education. These examples expand SNS's methodological toolbox for both research and teaching, enabling more inclusive, affective, and community-oriented forms of knowledge production. They can be replicated in other projects and serve as best practices in capacity-building efforts with activists and students. The co-creation methodology developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** has strengthened SNS's capacity to design inclusive, action-oriented processes that bring together diverse actors, including academics, activists, and practitioners. It provides a concrete model for engaging in "academic activism" in a structured and reflective way. The Lab format enhances the impact and relevance of research by embedding it in collective discussion and political action, especially on the theme of education, which is currently under severe threat from anti-gender and far-right attacks. The **scientific publications** emerging from FIERCE contribute to positioning SNS's work within cutting-edge feminist and political science debates. They serve as both academic resources and advocacy tools, offering rigorously researched arguments that can be mobilized in teaching, activism, and policymaking. Co-authorship and joint dissemination further strengthen collaborative research capacity. FIERCE's **communication materials** provide a model for translating research into clear, visual, and emotionally resonant messages. These tools enhance SNS's ability to disseminate findings across multiple platforms and strengthen skills in public scholarship. They also serve as inspiration for future multimedia content to accompany academic publications and activist

collaborations. The **Policy Toolkit** enhances the usability of research by offering actionable strategies and recommendations. It strengthens SNS's capacity to engage in knowledge transfer and policy advocacy and fills a gap by connecting theoretical frameworks to applied democratic innovation practices. The toolkit can also support the development of consulting or training offers on participatory democracy and intersectional policymaking.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

FIERCE's **conceptual framework** fosters collaborations between SNS and both academic and non-academic actors interested in gender and democracy. It provides a common language and methodological foundation for future joint projects, particularly within European consortia. The framework also creates opportunities to connect with policy actors and civil society groups working to counter anti-gender mobilization. This was exemplified in the co-creation lab in Italy, which led to the writing of the manual of self-defense for teachers against attacks from anti-gender groups. The **Transnational Feminist Network** consolidates relationships initiated through FIERCE and opens new doors for collaborations on European research projects, particularly Horizon Europe proposals. It provides a structure for maintaining contact with feminist actors across different national contexts and thematic areas and supports the creation of long-term interinstitutional partnerships. Particular attention is given to practitioners and direct actors involved in feminist actions, who are often under-financed and seeking material resources that can be accessed through this type of grant. The **FIERCE Course** provides a common foundation for joint teaching initiatives, co-organized public events, and collaborative training activities with civil society groups. It also creates opportunities for exchanges with activists who contributed to the course, facilitating new project ideas or co-designed research. The use of the course material in diverse settings—such as universities, NGOs, and policy workshops—enhances SNS's capacity to engage with a broad range of partners. **FIERCE Actions** create opportunities to engage with artists, activists, and policy actors beyond traditional academic spaces. Collaborating on similar initiatives, such as exhibitions or workshops, will strengthen ties with feminist organizations, community groups, and institutions committed to gender justice. These formats also provide compelling outputs for future research proposals and outreach strategies. The co-creation model developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** supports the development of horizontal partnerships with feminist organizations, community groups, and policymakers. It offers a replicable format for future collaborations, both in research and public engagement. The Labs can also serve as a core component of new Horizon Europe proposals or transnational feminist alliances seeking to connect research and activism. Joint **scientific publications** developed during FIERCE have deepened existing collaborations and opened opportunities for new ones, especially across disciplines and national contexts. These efforts increase SNS's visibility in international academic networks and create possibilities for future co-authored articles, special issues, and Horizon project consortia. SNS intends to continue reflecting and writing with collaborators such as Susi Meret, Roman Kuhar, Rok Smerdelj, Leja Markelj, Mojka Panik, and Lise Rolandsen Augustin. FIERCE's **communication materials** help SNS engage a wide array of stakeholders, students, civil society groups, journalists, and policymakers, facilitating new partnerships and increasing the visibility of feminist research. They are also valuable tools for cross-border dialogues, where subtitled videos or social media campaigns can spark connections and collaborative work. The **Policy Toolkit** offers a useful conversation starter with institutions, NGOs, and intergovernmental organizations interested in gender equality and

democratic innovation. Its format lends itself to collaboration across sectors, and the toolkit can serve as a foundation for co-creating context-specific policy guidance with partners in future projects.

4. Sustainability

FIERCE's **conceptual framework** will continue to be used in future publications, conference presentations, and research proposals at SNS. It will remain a foundational element in teaching, especially in modules on gender, democracy, and social movements. Thanks to its adaptability, the framework can be applied across projects and collaborations over time. While major resources would further support its maintenance, its dissemination will be sustained through academic and activist networks that will help secure its longevity. Additionally, the **Transnational Feminist Network** has the potential to be self-sustaining through mutual interest, regular exchanges, and integration into ongoing academic, activist, and policy-related work. SNS plans to remain actively engaged with the network as part of upcoming projects and will continue contributing through research dissemination, teaching exchanges, and collaborative publications. This includes initiatives within the FIRE working group (Feminism, Intersectionality, and Gender) at COSMOS, SNS's research centre on social movement studies. The **FIERCE Course** will also continue to be used in classroom settings and training programs at SNS. With minor updates and contextual adaptations, it can remain a relevant and inspiring resource for years to come. Moreover, course is expected to inform new academic offerings and contribute to the co-development of future activist-academic training modules. If hosted online, it could serve as a reference point for feminist education accessible to diverse audiences. The knowledge and methods generated through **FIERCE Actions** will inform future teaching, project design, and public events. Materials such as the cartoons and exhibition concepts could be adapted and reused, particularly in awareness campaigns or activist training. Importantly, these resources require no major investment beyond coordination and context-specific adaptation to remain impactful. Furthermore, the co-creation methodology developed in the **National Labs** will be adapted and reused in future EU-funded projects and academic-practice collaborations led by SNS. It will also be incorporated into research proposals, methodological trainings, and public seminars. The structure is inherently sustainable and requires only facilitation and coordination. Its added value lies in its capacity to generate politically relevant outputs through participatory dialogue. The **scientific publications** emerging from FIERCE will continue to circulate in academic and policy spaces, shaping teaching, informing future research, and contributing to debates on feminist strategies and democratic resilience. Their relevance is long-term, particularly in the face of ongoing attacks on gender rights across Europe. Some may even serve as groundwork for edited volumes or follow-up projects. Finally, FIERCE's **communication materials** will remain highly valuable in teaching and outreach initiatives at SNS. These tools provide ready-made content for workshops, classroom discussions, and awareness-raising activities. If kept online and openly accessible, they could serve as a lasting public archive of feminist knowledge and resistance strategies. The **Policy Toolkit** will also be treated as a living document, capable of being updated and adapted for use in new project proposals and capacity-building activities. It will be integrated into policy engagement strategies, academic teaching, and may even serve as a reference in civil society campaigns or institutional gender equality plans.

5. Replication / Transferability

FIERCE's **conceptual framework** is highly adaptable and can be transferred to other national or regional contexts facing gender backlash, such as Hungary, the UK, Germany, Portugal, Serbia, and beyond. It is also relevant across sectors, including civil society capacity-building, education, and advocacy. With slight modifications, the framework could support projects focusing on LGBTQ+ rights, democratic innovation, or intersectional policy development, making it a versatile tool for future initiatives. Moreover, the **Transnational Feminist Network** demonstrates significant transferability. Its model could be applied to other thematic areas, such as anti-racism, reproductive justice, and LGBTQ+ rights, or scaled to different regional levels, including Southern Europe, the Mediterranean, or Global South alliances. It could also inspire similar structures in projects involving co-creation and cross-sector engagement, fostering collaboration between researchers, activists, and policymakers in new contexts. The **FIERCE Course** provides a solid prototype for participatory curriculum development that can easily be adapted to national and local settings. In particular, it can address specific thematic issues such as migration, reproductive rights, or anti-LGBTQ+ legislation and be repurposed into train-the-trainer programs, summer schools, or civic education campaigns. This flexible format ensures relevance for future EU-funded projects and collaborations with both academic and activist partners. Similarly, **FIERCE Actions** offer creative and flexible formats that can be replicated in diverse contexts. They can be translated into other languages or redesigned to reflect local struggles, including those around abortion rights, anti-LGBTQ+ legislation, or gender-based violence. These actions are suitable for a wide range of settings, from universities and museums to festivals and activist spaces, ensuring their broad applicability. The co-creation methodology developed in the **National Labs** is also particularly transferable. It can be applied to other themes, such as racial justice, climate justice, and reproductive rights, and adapted for use by local grassroots groups as well as international networks. Additionally, this approach is relevant for institutions—such as municipalities, universities, and NGOs—that seek to enhance participatory and inclusive practices. Importantly, the **scientific publications** emerging from FIERCE have broad transferability. The analyses and theoretical frameworks developed can inform studies in other regions, including Hungary and Portugal, and be mobilized in training and advocacy contexts. Furthermore, the methodological approaches—particularly those combining critical frame analysis and participatory research—can be adapted to address other pressing societal challenges. Finally, FIERCE's **communication materials**, especially the podcasts and short videos, offer highly transferable formats. They can be adapted to new research topics or campaigns and co-produced with local activists, students, or policy actors. These materials provide a participatory model for future science communication efforts in EU-funded projects and feminist media initiatives.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the SNS FIERCE Team

“Participating in the FIERCE project has reinforced the importance of creating spaces where academic research, feminist activism, and policy engagement intersect in meaningful and transformative ways. We have learned how essential co-creation and mutual learning are when working across disciplines, countries, and positionalities, especially in the face of growing anti-gender backlash. The project has expanded our methodological repertoire, sharpened our thinking around democratic innovation, and strengthened our commitment to building long-term transnational alliances. These lessons will inform not only our future research and teaching but also how we collaborate with feminist movements and institutions seeking to defend and deepen democracy.”

3.4.1.7. Individual Exploitation Plan - Complutense University of Madrid (UCM)

Complutense University of Madrid (UCM), based in Spain, maintains strong connections with civil society actors through its active participation and research in social movements, including feminist movements. The team also has established links with political parties (e.g., Ahora Madrid, Más Madrid, Podemos) and key institutions (e.g., Ministry of Equality), which have been instrumental in advancing the FIERCE Project. UCM has been deeply involved in every stage of the project — from producing up-to-date knowledge on European anti-gender, anti-feminist, and feminist movements to organizing co-creation labs with feminist activists, NGOs, and political representatives.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how UCM intends to sustain and build upon FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

At the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM), the interdisciplinary, multidimensional, and multi-level **conceptual framework** developed through FIERCE – grounded in a bottom-up approach to feminism and democracy – will be integrated into both research and teaching practices. This framework will inform academic publications and the activities of research groups such as Gender and Politics (GEYPO) and Social Movements (MOVICON) within the Faculty of Political Science and Sociology. By publishing materials in Spanish, UCM aims to ensure broader accessibility for students and academic audiences. Moreover, the framework will guide the development of new research agendas and support the creation of emerging networks at both national and international levels. The Transnational Feminist Network established within FIERCE provides a lasting infrastructure for collaboration, mobilization, and mutual learning. UCM plans to leverage this network to foster partnerships with feminist organizations across countries, co-organize public forums, awareness campaigns, and training programs, and involve students and early-career researchers in ongoing dialogue and activism. This will be a key element of UCM's strategy to connect academic research with feminist praxis. **FIERCE training materials** will also be actively incorporated into teaching and supervision activities. Selected content will be integrated into master's-level courses on *Gender, Family, and Work* and undergraduate courses such as *Sociology of the Family*. The complete FIERCE course will be shared with students as an open-access resource, supporting both formal education and self-directed learning. This hybrid format – combining scholarly perspectives with activist knowledge - will enrich classroom discussions and promote an intersectional, politically engaged feminist curriculum. **The FIERCE Actions**, notably the self-defence manual, represent tangible contributions that address safety and empowerment from a feminist perspective. UCM intends to use these resources in courses on social movements, feminism, and activist research. Campaign materials and other co-produced content will also be incorporated into seminar discussions and readings, providing students with valuable insights into how activism and academia intersect. The **co-creation methodology** developed through the FIERCE National Labs will be applied to future participatory research and training strategies within the Faculty of Political Science and Sociology. UCM plans to use this approach to structure multi-stakeholder dialogues and dissemination activities on gender equality and feminist political engagement, engaging feminist activists, organizations, faculty members from gender studies research groups (DIVISAR, GEYPO, MOVICON), and PhD students working on gender-related topics. **Scientific research outputs** from FIERCE, including published and forthcoming articles and

book chapters, will be actively disseminated within UCM through presentations in research groups, academic seminars, and postgraduate forums. These contributions are expected to strengthen UCM's feminist and sociopolitical research agendas, inspire future projects, and support international academic collaboration beyond the project's lifecycle. In teaching, these publications will enrich lecture content, guide classroom discussions, and serve as key references in both undergraduate and postgraduate curricula. Finally, FIERCE's communication materials – including the website, visual identity, graphics, stickers, and campaign visuals – will continue to support public presentations and outreach efforts, making feminist research more accessible to wider audiences. The **Policy Toolkit** will serve as both a pedagogical and strategic resource to enhance democratic engagement and feminist policy literacy. It will be disseminated across various teaching and research settings, particularly within the Faculty of Political Science and Sociology. The Toolkit's accessible, action-oriented structure will be used in student workshops, master's-level courses on gender and public policy, and seminars with civil society organizations and participants.

2. Exploitation

The **FIERCE conceptual framework** has significantly enhanced UCM's capacity to teach gender-related courses by providing a rigorous and contextually grounded model that bridges academic research and social movements. It has informed the development of new student-centered courses and will serve as a foundation for future research proposals. Notably, the FIERCE experience has introduced co-creation as a core methodological innovation – an approach that UCM plans to replicate in upcoming research and teaching initiatives focused on participatory knowledge production. **The Transnational Feminist Network** has offered valuable insights into building and sustaining cross-border feminist collaboration, strengthening UCM's capacity for facilitation, coordination, and transnational dialogue. It has become a reference point in teaching and project design, enriching course content with real-world examples of feminist mobilization. This experience contributes directly to the generation of new research ideas and the conceptualization of international, action-oriented projects grounded in feminist values. The **FIERCE training materials** provide a model for enhancing teaching methods and course design through the integration of diverse forms of feminist knowledge. By identifying conceptual and practical gaps from both academic and activist perspectives, they support a more holistic and intersectional pedagogical approach. These materials will also inform the design of new teaching units and public engagement activities. **FIERCE Actions**, such as the co-created self-defence manual and campaign resources, offer concrete models for engaging with feminist knowledge production in practice. In future projects, these actions will inspire participatory and collaborative methodologies, improving the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of UCM's work while enriching individual learning experiences. The co-creation methodology developed through FIERCE **National Labs** has influenced UCM's approach to qualitative fieldwork and participatory research. This methodology will be embedded in future Horizon Europe project proposals and national research calls. Additionally, it will inform the creation of new postgraduate courses on feminist methodologies, participatory research, and academic activism. By fostering student engagement through research-based learning activities, this approach helps bridge the gap between theoretical training and real-world societal challenges. The **scientific publications** emerging from FIERCE have significantly contributed to professional development by offering rigorous, empirically grounded, and theoretically innovative outputs. These publications will enrich course

materials, inform new syllabi, and support UCM's feminist and sociopolitical research agendas. Furthermore, they will contribute to the professional advancement of the FIERCE team by facilitating accreditation processes (e.g., through Spain's National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation, ANECA). The emphasis on co-authorship and interdisciplinary collaboration has also built capacity for collaborative writing and publishing across institutions and countries, strengthening UCM's international academic networks. FIERCE's **communication materials** – including podcasts, blog posts, videos, and campaign visuals – have proven to be valuable tools for integrating activist voices and contemporary feminist struggles into university classrooms. These materials enhance public outreach and demonstrate how feminist knowledge can be disseminated beyond traditional academic publications. Their visibility contributes to UCM's institutional credibility and supports future project development. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** developed within FIERCE provides research-informed strategies to counter anti-gender backlash and promote inclusive policies. Its modular structure and comparative insights across European contexts make it a valuable resource for replicating methodologies in future national and international projects. At a professional level, it will support the creation of training materials for public officials and educators, while enriching academic teaching with concrete examples of democratic innovation. By bridging theory and action, the Toolkit will inform new project ideas focused on participatory democracy, anti-discrimination strategies, and feminist policy development.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The collaborative work fostered through FIERCE has already contributed to expanding UCM's network of international partners, including academics, civil society organizations, consulting firms, and feminist researchers in Spain. The project's **conceptual framework** has facilitated the creation of future Horizon Europe proposals and multidisciplinary cooperation across borders. It has also provided valuable opportunities for internships and research training for master's students, strengthening ties with potential PhD candidates and fostering lasting academic relationships. Furthermore, UCM has built synergies with related international and national initiatives such as CCINDLE and DIVISAR, deepening its engagement within feminist research and activism networks. The **Transnational Feminist Network** established under FIERCE has significantly broadened UCM's transnational and cross-sectoral connections. It has linked feminist activists in Spain with counterparts across Europe, creating a dynamic ecosystem of exchange and solidarity. These relationships open new opportunities for co-authorship, future Horizon project calls, and sustained collaboration between universities and civil society. The network also facilitates cross-thematic and interdisciplinary cooperation by connecting diverse struggles within a shared feminist framework. FIERCE's **training materials** have supported ongoing collaboration with researchers, activists, and feminist organizations involved in the project, particularly those engaged in the co-creation processes in Spain. These resources also offer opportunities to establish new connections with educators—including university lecturers, secondary school teachers, and civil society organizations. By circulating and implementing the course in these contexts, UCM aims to expand interdisciplinary networks and deepen intersectoral cooperation. The **FIERCE Actions** have helped cultivate new connections and strengthen UCM's understanding of feminist networks. These relationships provide a foundation for future collaboration with grassroots organizations and other partners. Through joint activities and co-creation processes, trust and shared understanding have been established, laying the groundwork for future projects and sustained partnerships beyond the project's

duration. The **FIERCE National Labs** have further broadened UCM's transnational connections within feminist academic and activist circles. Their dialogical framework has proven to be a fertile ground for initiating collaborative relationships across disciplines and sectors. These Labs are envisioned as a foundation for future joint proposals under Horizon Europe and other international calls, particularly those focusing on gender equality, democracy, and civic engagement. FIERCE's **scientific publications** reflect and reinforce transnational collaboration, with co-authored outputs serving as a platform for sustained academic cooperation. These publications are expected to lead to further joint projects, including proposals under new Horizon Europe calls. The research findings also open possibilities for dialogue and exchange with feminist organizations, policymakers, advocacy groups, and researchers, offering academically validated materials to support public debate and policy engagement. In this way, the publications act as bridges between academia and civil society, enhancing the visibility of feminist scholarship and fostering multidisciplinary partnerships.

Finally, FIERCE's **communication materials** – through their emphasis on joint actions and co-created content – have played an important role in strengthening networks and inspiring new partnerships. The **Policy Toolkit** developed within the project serves as a concrete basis for fostering continued transnational collaboration with feminist academics, civil society organizations, and policy practitioners. It also acts as a catalyst for engaging new institutional partners – such as gender equality councils, youth platforms, and local authorities – through policy dialogue initiatives grounded in the Toolkit's recommendations.

4. Sustainability

The data and analytical tools developed within FIERCE, anchored in its **conceptual framework**, provide a strong foundation for sustained research activity at the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM). These resources will be leveraged to pursue new funding opportunities and collaborative projects, ensuring the continuation of research on feminist movements and democratic innovation. The experience and methodologies gained through FIERCE are now embedded within UCM's institutional practices, supporting long-term engagement with feminist research, teaching innovation, and broader social transformation. The **Transnational Feminist Network** and its co-creation methods have fostered collective learning processes that will inform future research, teaching practices, and collaborative outputs. This network has already inspired new academic content and will continue to serve as a foundation for publications and institutional initiatives. The relationships forged during FIERCE are expected to evolve further through new projects and joint campaigns, ensuring the continuity and deepening of the network's impact over time. FIERCE's **training materials**, designed to be high-quality, openly accessible, and reusable, ensure their continued relevance and value beyond the project's duration. They will be integrated into the development of new academic courses, extracurricular training sessions, and the supervision of student research. By embedding these resources within institutional pedagogical tools, UCM will sustain FIERCE's impact across both academic and activist learning environments. The **FIERCE Actions** provide valuable inspiration for academic-activist collaborations, demonstrating how knowledge can be co-produced through concrete and practical initiatives. These actions illustrate effective ways of communicating feminist ideas to diverse audiences, extending beyond academia to engage grassroots actors and the broader public. UCM intends to build on the methodologies and formats used in FIERCE Actions for future participatory research, fostering

inclusive knowledge production and strengthening connections between academia and social movements. These initiatives will also serve as models for co-creation in future teaching, research, and engagement activities. The co-creation model established through FIERCE **National Labs** will remain a key methodological and pedagogical reference for UCM's research and teaching activities. The university plans to seek additional funding to support lab-based knowledge production on feminist topics. This model will also inform academic seminars, doctoral workshops, and applied policy dialogues. By providing a reflective space for academics and activists to reconsider their roles in knowledge production, the Labs have laid the groundwork for future collaborative endeavors. UCM also intends to document and publish these experiences to further disseminate the value of this approach. The **scientific publications** initiated during FIERCE will continue to generate academic value through peer-reviewed articles and edited volumes, several of which are still in progress. These outputs are expected to have long-term relevance in feminist scholarship and will remain central to UCM's research and teaching strategies. They will inform thesis supervision, curricular development, and the shaping of future research agendas. Ongoing collaborations with FIERCE partners will ensure continuity, while the project's data and insights will support future publications and conference presentations. Institutional support for research dissemination and open-access publishing at UCM will help maintain the visibility and accessibility of these contributions. FIERCE's **communication materials** constitute a living archive of the project's activities, outcomes, and collaborations. These resources will continue to support visibility, outreach, and the sharing of results even after the project's formal conclusion. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** developed within FIERCE offers a practical and adaptable resource for addressing current democratic and gender-related challenges. UCM plans to continue using the Toolkit in training sessions and future participatory labs. Its modular design and relevance across academic, policy, and activist contexts ensure its long-term applicability and value as a living resource for fostering inclusive and democratic innovation.

5. Replication / Transferability

The FIERCE **conceptual framework** is flexible and adaptable to other disciplinary and geographical contexts. It is particularly well-suited for developing further case studies in Spain or for conducting comparative research across regions. Translating the framework into Spanish and making contextual adjustments will facilitate its application in diverse institutional settings, including regional gender policy evaluations and civic engagement initiatives. The **co-creation methodology** underpinning the Transnational Feminist Network is highly versatile and can be tailored to different scales—national, regional, or local. It offers a valuable approach for supporting the formation of feminist networks in new thematic areas or institutional contexts and for building coalitions that respond to local priorities while maintaining a transnational perspective. FIERCE's **training materials** are designed for broad applicability and can be directly integrated into a wide range of educational settings, including undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs. They can also serve as resources during doctoral supervision processes or as inspiration for designing new modules and workshops on feminist theory, activism, and democratic innovation. Their flexibility and open-access format make them easily transferable across diverse institutional and cultural contexts. Several **FIERCE Actions** are highly transferable, provided they are thoughtfully adapted to local languages, contexts, and needs. For example, the self-defence manual could be translated and adjusted for use in Spanish contexts. Other Actions – such as public campaigns,

workshops, cultural events, and educational materials – offer models for similar initiatives elsewhere, as long as they are grounded in the specific realities of the communities they seek to engage. The **FIERCE National Lab** methodology is equally adaptable and can be implemented across various thematic areas, institutional settings, and geographical contexts. At UCM, it can be applied to projects in other departments focusing on social justice, political participation, and human rights. With minor contextual adjustments, it could also be transferred to other universities or civic institutions, both within Spain and across Europe. Its inherent flexibility allows it to be tailored to different participant profiles and political realities while preserving its core principles of co-creation, dialogue, and action-oriented outcomes. The **scientific publications** produced within FIERCE address transnational gender dynamics that are relevant across multiple academic and geographical contexts. Their analytical frameworks and empirical findings can inform research in other countries, support comparative studies, and serve as foundational literature in thematically related projects on democracy, rights, and gender-based mobilizations. Beyond academia, these outputs provide valuable insights for NGOs, think tanks, and institutions working on gender equality and feminist policy. Finally, FIERCE's **communication materials** demonstrate how academic and activist work can be effectively integrated and disseminated. The project's strong visual identity, accessible content, and co-produced knowledge offer a transferable model for future initiatives aiming to enhance the visibility and impact of research and activism.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the UCM FIERCE Team

"The work carried out within the FIERCE project has significantly deepened our understanding of feminist movements across Europe—their frames, strategies, claims, and forms of everyday activism. A key part of this learning has been exploring how these movements engage, in diverse ways, with the growing influence of anti-democratic and anti-gender forces. Collaborating toward shared objectives within a large European consortium of universities and non-governmental organisations has been a learning process in itself. We have benefitted greatly from the ongoing exchange of ideas, methodologies, and interdisciplinary perspectives. The co-creation process and participatory action research significantly contributed to building professional capacity. This included expanding knowledge of feminist networks, acquiring new co-creation methods, and developing a deeper understanding of the opportunities and challenges involved in academic–activist collaboration."

3.4.2. Civil Society Organisations Partners

3.4.2.1. Individual Exploitation Plan - Mirovni Institute (MI)

Mirovni inštitut (The Peace Institute) - MI is an independent non-profit research institute with expertise in human rights, minorities, politics, media, gender and cultural policies based in Ljubljana-Slovenia. At the FIERCE Project, MI provided a better understanding of when, how and why feminist and anti-feminist movements draw on frames, actors and alliances from local, national, regional and transnational levels in their strategies for policy change. MI has developed regular contacts with various civil society organizations and has included them as resources for research and as partners in research and advocacy activities. They also invite experts from civil society as lecturers at seminars, conferences, study courses.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how MI intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will serve as a valuable reference point for future academic publications and potential new projects addressing similar themes. Methodologies developed within WP1 and WP2 – such as critical frame analysis, interview protocols, and discourse network analysis guidelines – offer strong potential for application in upcoming research initiatives. This conceptual and methodological knowledge will also be shared internally through joint meetings at the Institute, fostering capacity building among colleagues and ensuring its integration into broader research and advocacy activities. As an active member of the **Transnational Feminist Network**, the Institute plans to sustain its collaborations with feminist activists across the EU, leveraging these relationships in both research and advocacy work. The **FIERCE Training Material** will support ongoing capacity-building efforts and will be promoted among feminist groups, networks, and stakeholders at the national level - including policymakers - to raise awareness on gender equality. Some researchers at MI involved in university teaching may integrate the course into their curricula, and the Institute will promote it at feminist and academic events. The **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the online Exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia, align closely with the Institute's mission to disseminate feminist knowledge and encourage public engagement. It will be actively shared with policymakers, researchers, and networks to foster dialogue on reproductive justice. Similarly, the **FIERCE Labs** co-creation methodology has proven effective in bringing together diverse actors and will be potentially applied in future projects, even beyond gender-focused themes. The **Scientific Publications** will follow open-access principles to ensure broad dissemination, supporting MI's commitment to knowledge sharing and public engagement. Featured regularly on the Institute's website and social media channels, these publications will also be presented at national and international conferences to promote academic exchange. Lastly, the **FIERCE Communication Materials** will inspire future strategies within the Institute and be distributed online and at feminist and academic events, while the **Policy Toolkit** will be disseminated to Slovenian decision-makers in the campaigns ahead of the 2026 parliamentary elections, aligning with the institute's broader mission of promoting gender equality and democratic participation. Also, it will be shared with partner NGOs on gender-related issues to amplify advocacy efforts.

2. Exploitation

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** has significantly enhanced the Institute's research capacity by offering a comprehensive theoretical and methodological basis that deepens understanding of anti-gender mobilizations in Slovenia. As the first thorough study of contemporary feminist responses to rising anti-gender discourse in the country, it fills a critical research gap and strengthens academic advancement while providing a solid foundation for future project proposals. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has further contributed to MI's advocacy and activist work by fostering stronger connections between feminist activists across Europe and bridging the gap between civil society efforts and academic research. This network creates a platform for mutual learning, exchange of strategies, and co-creation of knowledge, ensuring research findings have real-world impact. The **FIERCE Training Material** supports MI's mission to disseminate gender equality knowledge, combining theoretical and practical feminist approaches that enhance teaching methods and inspire future research and advocacy initiatives. The **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia, strengthened the Institute's integration of academic research and activist practice, building partnerships

with private sector actors and generating media coverage that raised public awareness and elevated the issue on a national level. Similarly, the **FIERCE Labs** provided a unique space for interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration, addressing sensitive issues like violence in reproductive health care through dialogue and mutual learning. The **Scientific Publications** have reinforced the Institute's academic excellence, contributing to gender studies and supporting the career development of early-career researchers involved in the project. The **FIERCE Communication Materials** serve as a strong model for future projects, demonstrating how strategic dissemination can amplify reach and impact, while the **Policy Toolkit** equips the Institute with concrete tools and recommendations to engage in political debates effectively and support feminist activists in influencing public policy and legislative processes.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** has created opportunities for long-term collaboration with feminist organizations, researchers, and activists by laying the groundwork for sustained partnerships for upcoming EU-funded projects and fostering cooperation across academic and activist spheres. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has already contributed substantially to the Institute's advocacy and activism by bridging civil society efforts with academic research and establishing a platform for mutual learning, strategy exchange, and co-creation of knowledge. Sharing the **FIERCE Training Material** with feminist organizations, networks, and stakeholders is expected to generate new collaborations, as it serves as a common reference point for dialogue and joint initiatives, potentially leading to stronger alliances and future projects. The course offers a flexible, replicable educational resource that can enhance teaching methods, be included in future project methodologies, and stimulate new ideas for research and advocacy initiatives. The development of the **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the exhibition, facilitated deeper collaboration between the Institute and feminist activists, reinforcing engagement with the broader feminist community. The collaborative nature of the exhibition, particularly the inclusion of activists from various generations and ideological backgrounds, helped overcome internal divisions within the movement. This action strengthened regional and transnational networks by building relationships with groups like the Feminist Anti-Fascist Network (FAMA) and feminist organizations across the former Yugoslavia. Similarly, the **FIERCE Labs** deepened connections with feminist organizations, expanded the Institute's reach beyond academic and policy circles, and integrated civil society actors into its strategic network. Co-authoring **Scientific Publications** with researchers from other countries has supported the internationalization of academic work and embedded the Slovenian context within global feminist discussions, opening doors to new partnerships and future Horizon project proposals and EU-funded initiatives. The dissemination of **FIERCE Communication Materials** boosted the Institute's visibility nationally and internationally, resulting in invitations to present at various events and laying the foundation for future collaborations. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** has strengthened ties with both political decision-makers and civil society organizations, positioning the Institute as a key actor in policy-engaged advocacy efforts.

4. Sustainability

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** will continue to inform academic and policy discourse beyond the project's lifespan, with knowledge disseminated through the Institute's website, scientific publications, conference presentations, and feminist and academic events. The **Transnational Feminist Network** will

remain a key space for mutual learning, enabling the exchange of country-specific experiences and strengthening strategic responses to gender backlash. The Institute plans to stay actively engaged in the network, sustaining and expanding collaborations formed during FIERCE and integrating them into future research and advocacy initiatives. The **FIERCE Training Course**, freely accessible online in English, will continue to be promoted through the Institute's website, partnerships, and training activities, serving as a valuable resource in academic and advocacy contexts. To ensure ongoing impact, the **Exhibition on reproductive rights** has been digitized and made freely available online in Slovenian and English, allowing for continued use in educational, activist, and public awareness initiatives. The **FIERCE Labs** have left a legacy of strengthened relationships among participants, with the co-creation methodology remaining central to the Institute's participatory research and activism-oriented projects. The **Scientific Publications**, released in open access, will remain available to scholars, students, and activists and will be promoted via the Institute's online platforms to ensure sustained visibility. The **FIERCE Communication Materials**, especially digital formats like podcasts and videos, will continue to support academic presentations, advocacy campaigns, and training sessions. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** will be potentially translated into Slovenian to increase accessibility for local stakeholders, particularly in the context of the 2026 parliamentary elections.

5. Replication / Transferability

The theoretical and methodological contributions of FIERCE's **Conceptual Framework** are highly adaptable to various national and institutional contexts. Methodological guidelines developed within different work packages can support research on social movements across the EU and, with minor contextual adjustments, be applied in other regions to explore feminist and anti-gender mobilizations. The **Transnational Feminist Network's** structure enables easy expansion to include new partners, particularly from underrepresented regions, fostering cross-border knowledge exchange and comparative learning. Insights and strategies developed in specific national contexts can inform feminist activism globally, strengthening responses to anti-gender movements and building solidarity at local and international levels. The **training material** can be updated with feminist knowledge and experiences from additional EU countries, translated into other languages, and adapted to diverse contexts to enhance its relevance and accessibility. The **FIERCE Action** developed under FIERCE offers a scalable model for replication in national and transnational settings. At the national level, similar exhibitions can be tailored to reflect specific regional reproductive rights issues, while a transnational version could be co-created by feminist organizations from multiple countries, addressing shared challenges. A digital platform could support cross-border engagement and solidarity among movements facing common threats to reproductive freedom. The co-creation methodology developed in the **FIERCE Labs** is flexible and transferable across sectors, disciplines, and thematic areas, offering a powerful tool for inclusive dialogue and collective action. **Scientific publications** can be translated into additional languages to broaden their reach and integrated into workshops, policy briefs, or educational materials for diverse audiences. The project's **communication materials** can be localized, adapted, and translated to engage specific communities or address regional issues effectively. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** can also be translated into Slovenian to enhance its accessibility for local stakeholders, particularly in the context of the upcoming 2026 parliamentary elections and serve as a practical resource for advocacy and policy engagement.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the MI FIERCE Team

“The project provided valuable insights and lessons that will significantly inform our future work. Most notably, it introduced us to new conceptual, theoretical, and methodological approaches, particularly participatory research methods, which we plan to incorporate more systematically into our projects. The collaboration between academia, NGOs, and SMEs proved particularly enriching, demonstrating the value of cross-sectoral engagement for both research and advocacy. Regular exchanges with other project leaders fostered mutual learning and offered fresh perspectives on project management and strategic planning. The experience also deepened our understanding of the dynamics of democratic backlash and strengthened our ability to respond to these challenges both academically and through activism.”

3.4.2.2. Individual Exploitation Plan - European Alternatives (EA)

European Alternatives (EA) is a transnational organization dedicated to promoting democracy, equality, and culture beyond the nation-state, while envisioning alternatives for a more viable and inclusive future for Europe. EA has built an extensive network of civil society organizations across Europe, actively engaging in areas such as civil and democratic rights, women's rights, gender equality, LGBTQ+ rights, and the rights of migrants and minorities. The organization maintains regular dialogue with members of the European Commission on issues of civil and fundamental rights and democratic engagement, as well as with Members of the European Parliament and other EU institutions. EA plays a key role in connecting and channeling innovative transnational feminist movements into tangible democratic change and advancing gender equality. Within the FIERCE project, the EA team led Work Package 5 *Innovative Strategies and Solution Pathways*, establishing a transnational network that brought together feminist movements and public actors through community meetings. They co-organized the Feminist Winter School and contributed significantly by delivering Policy Briefs and Toolkits.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how EA intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

The elements developed through FIERCE's **Conceptual Framework** have strengthened European Alternatives' understanding of contemporary feminist movements and anti-gender mobilisations across Europe. This framework will inform advocacy work with institutions, including French parliamentary delegations on women's rights, health, labour, and finance, as well as relevant European bodies such as the FEMM Committee and the Human Rights Sub-Committee. The data collected will also support awareness-raising campaigns targeting the general public and collaborations with associations, helping to build a robust case for structural and long-term support for feminist and LGBTQIA+ organisations. The **Transnational Feminist Network** aligns directly with European Alternatives' mission to strengthen democracy in Europe through inclusive, transnational cooperation. It will be integrated into advocacy and mobilisation activities, promoting exchanges of experience among European partners and providing a collective platform to support local and national initiatives while sharing practices and resources. The **FIERCE Actions**, including the self-defence manual for teachers, the Gender Debunking Guerilla project, the Slovenian platform monitoring anti-gender attacks, and the Tant que je serai noire community training, will directly inspire future campaigns and training activities, equipping activists and serving as

models to be shared with other partners. The **FIERCE Labs** reinforced the understanding that responses to anti-gender backlash require collective strategies engaging allies beyond feminist spaces. They highlighted the coherence of backlash as an organised strategy and inspired the development of anticipatory tools for shared protection. The Labs also exposed blind spots in current practices, particularly regarding the inclusion of racialised people, trans people, and those in precarious situations. The **Scientific Publications** will be used by EA strategically in communication and advocacy activities to strengthen arguments and support outreach efforts. The **FIERCE Communication Materials**, including videos, podcasts, and visual aids, will remain essential resources for training workshops, public speeches, and communication campaigns. The French National Lab's web page will continue as a hub for information, awareness-raising, and networking among feminists, journalists, elected representatives, researchers, and allies facing anti-gender attacks in France. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** will support continuity in advocacy efforts, enabling coordination with FIERCE partners to develop common positions at key political moments such as European elections, EU presidencies, and institutional campaigns. Joint advocacy events will also be organised with policymakers at both national and European levels to sustain momentum beyond the project.

2. Exploitation

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** represents an interdisciplinary, multidimensional approach grounded in a bottom-up methodology that European Alternatives will re-use in future European projects. It enriches analyses through an intersectional reading of power relations and strengthens methodologies for documenting anti-feminist discourses and policies. This framework also acts as a lever for enhancing educational tools, internal training programmes, and awareness-raising resources, while generating new content aimed at young people, allies, and political decision-makers. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has facilitated collective learning by exposing European Alternatives to feminist contexts, practices, and tools developed across different countries. It enriches the organisation's approaches, elevates shared struggles to the European level, enables pooling of resources, strengthens solidarity among organisations, and amplifies the impact of actions in advocacy and mobilisation. The **FIERCE Training Material** has proved to be a valuable resource that will support various activities. It will be used to train internal teams, including new staff and volunteers, on intersectional feminist mobilisations and anti-gender discourses. Beyond internal use, it will serve as a support tool in training workshops for young people and French feminist collectives. The material's accessible, self-paced, and hybrid format facilitates distribution and inspires the creation of new participatory, cross-disciplinary educational models. The **FIERCE Actions** have provided concrete methodologies adaptable to a variety of mobilisation contexts. The pedagogical self-defence manual equips the organisation to better support educators facing gender-related controversies. The Gender Debunking Guerilla offers an innovative, targeted strategy for disseminating information on sexual and reproductive health and rights to vulnerable groups. The Slovenian monitoring platform serves as an inspiration for developing a similar tool in France. Additionally, the approach of Tant que je serai noire informs the development of training rooted in the lived experiences of racialised women. Together, these initiatives address gaps in existing tools, particularly around documenting attacks and safeguarding activists. Through the **FIERCE National Labs**, European Alternatives forged connections with grassroots groups, universities, researchers, and feminist organisations that were previously

outside its network. These exchanges have laid the foundation for future collaborations and created alliances that strengthen the organisation's ability to operate across multiple fronts - community engagement, education, media, and institutional advocacy - making its actions more relevant, visible, and resilient to backlash. Finally, the **FIERCE Policy Toolkit** will be an integral resource for advocacy efforts with French institutions, including the Women's Rights, Finance, Health, and Labour delegations of the National Assembly and Senate, as well as European bodies such as the FEMM Committee and the Human Rights and Democracy Intergroup. It strengthens arguments for structural support to feminist organisations, reinforces vigilance against anti-gender offensives, and advocates for public policies grounded in equality and intersectionality. The toolkit's factsheets and policy briefs translate key research findings into actionable recommendations, equipping the organisation to engage more effectively with decision-makers and enhance the relevance of its advocacy. It also provides inspiration for developing future advocacy materials tailored to the French context.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** has enabled European Alternatives to establish meaningful links with feminist, LGBTQIA+, and anti-racist researchers, universities, and activist organisations across diverse European contexts. These connections, built on a shared understanding of anti-gender threats, are already inspiring ideas for joint projects, political events, and coordinated advocacy campaigns. This KER has become a common language for structuring sustainable, interdisciplinary partnerships and serves as a foundation for fostering collaboration across borders. The **Transnational Feminist Network** offers a vital space for ongoing engagement with a broad range of intersectional feminist and LGBTQIA+ actors, organisations, researchers, and public figures. There is a strong intention to expand the network further by including more anti-racist, anti-fascist, and civil society organisations. This expanded network will support the development of new collaborations, joint campaigns, and collective responses to anti-gender attacks. It also provides a framework for co-creating future European projects (Horizon Europe, CERV) and nurturing inter-institutional and cross-sectoral cooperation. The **FIERCE Training Material** strengthens collaborations by serving as a shared resource for feminist organisations, youth groups, and partner universities. It provides a common basis for discussion, analysis, and training, making it easier to develop lasting partnerships. The course also opens the door for designing joint training modules in collaboration with diverse stakeholders, particularly within Erasmus+ or Horizon Europe initiatives. The **FIERCE Actions** offer practical examples that facilitate engagement with new organisations confronting similar struggles across Europe. These actions support the creation of new transnational projects and encourage pooling resources and expertise. They also act as levers for building partnerships across sectors - including education, health, media, and law - and fostering broader cooperation between feminists, LGBTQIA+, anti-racist, and civil rights defenders. Through the **FIERCE National Labs**, European Alternatives has created ongoing communication channels, such as an email loop for sharing information and resources among participants. These connections are now well established, and there are plans to maintain regular exchanges and organise public events, particularly to promote the collaborative platform developed during the Labs. Finally, the **FIERCE Policy Toolkit** strengthens outreach to new partners working in civil rights, public policy, and gender equality. By disseminating this KER throughout existing and emerging networks, it facilitates inter-institutional dialogue and provides a

shared foundation of knowledge and proposals. This, in turn, supports the creation of new collaborations, campaigns, and European projects.

4. Sustainability

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework**, including reports, analyses, and typologies, will continue to inform European Alternatives' future work. It will be integrated into training, publications, and advocacy efforts, offering a structured lens to analyse anti-gender mobilisations and strengthening long-term strategic actions. The **Transnational Feminist Network** established through FIERCE is seen as a key legacy. European Alternatives plans to maintain and expand it by continuing regular online exchanges, organising in-person meetings, and publishing co-created resources. The aim is to develop it into a stable coordination space for intersectional feminist organisations across Europe, enabling collective responses to anti-gender movements. The **FIERCE Training Material**, as an online resource, remains an essential tool for ongoing education and advocacy, addressing structural political issues that will remain relevant well beyond the project's duration. The **FIERCE Actions**, including initiatives like the self-defence manual and the monitoring platform, will continue to be disseminated through European Alternatives' channels and events. Some will be translated for broader activist and institutional use, and, depending on available funding, adapted or replicated to support future campaigns and programmes. The collaborative platform developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** will be kept alive through regular exchanges among participants and public events to raise awareness. Finally, the **FIERCE Policy Toolkit** is a critical resource for advocacy, with potential for adaptation and translation to national contexts. It will support European Alternatives' efforts in training, new project development, and influencing European policymaking on issues such as reproductive rights, education, and combating online hate speech.

5. Replication / Transferability

The **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** is fully transferable to other national or regional contexts, provided it is adapted to local socio-political specificities. It can also be applied across sectors to inform diagnoses and intervention strategies grounded in intersectional analyses. The **Transnational Feminist Network** is equally adaptable to related sectors such as human rights, anti-racism efforts, or migrant rights, and could be deployed at regional or municipal levels by incorporating local languages, legal frameworks, and activist realities. The **FIERCE Training Material** offers flexibility for replication in diverse linguistic, cultural, or activist contexts. This could involve translating modules, tailoring examples to local settings, or adjusting complexity for different audiences - activists, students, or policymakers. It also has potential for integration into university curricula or civic education programmes on equality, human rights, and democracy. The **FIERCE Actions** can similarly be adapted to various settings, accounting for local realities such as language, political climate, risk levels, and access to technology. For instance, the Gender Debunking Guerilla could be applied in working-class neighbourhoods in France with context-specific adjustments, while the self-defence manual could incorporate examples drawn from French education. Finally, the collaborative platform and relationships forged in the **FIERCE National Labs** will continue to provide a foundation for sharing information, maintaining regular exchanges, and organising public events that promote the platform and inspire further initiatives.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the EA FIERCE Team

“One of the major lessons learned from FIERCE is the importance of mobilising an interdisciplinary, multidimensional and multi-level analytical framework to tackle the issues linked to feminist mobilisations and the rise of anti-gender movements. This framework allows us to think in terms of a continuum between discourse, public policy and structural violence, to better understand the interweaving of oppressions and anti-gender strategies, linking local attacks to broader transnational dynamics. It has also enabled us to identify the innovative strategies deployed by feminists to tackle these issues, with a view to replicating and multiplying them. It has also strengthened the relevance of our advocacy actions, basing them on rigorous, contextualised analyses. The project has also shown us the richness of sharing expertise between academics and activists, and the need to create sustainable spaces for such dialogue. The co-creation of knowledge between research and activism, as experimented with in the FIERCE laboratories, has been a particularly fruitful method, which we hope to replicate in other initiatives in the future. Finally, FIERCE has confirmed the need to strengthen feminist alliances at European level, particularly in the face of coordinated and transnational offensives against the rights of women, LGBTQIA+ people and minorities. This observation encourages us to invest more in cross-border cooperation, and to anchor our actions in an intersectional, inclusive and anti-fascist logic. This learning will feed into our institutional strategy, our future collaborations and our long-term actions.”

3.4.3. Private Sector Partners

3.4.3.1. Individual Exploitation Plan - Smart Venice (SV)

Smart Venice (SV) is an independent research, training and consultancy unit supporting the full integration of gender, societal and inclusiveness dimensions in research, innovation and governance. At FIERCE, the SV team is leading on the creation of the “FIERCE Labs”, spaces for dialogue between feminist movements and their institutional allies. Furthermore, SV oversaw the FIERCE Winter School and the preparation of the FIERCE online course. Smart Venice has a wide network of partners at the EU level, mostly universities and research organizations active on promoting gender in research and innovation, and cities/local authorities working on gender sensitive urban policies. Contacts and collaborations are active with a variety of feminist think tanks and NGOs.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how SV intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE’s results beyond the project’s completion.

1. Strategic Interest

The knowledge generated through the **FIERCE Conceptual Framework** on feminist, antifeminist, and anti-gender movements will inform several areas of Smart Venice’s expertise, including the preparation of new project proposals and the design of capacity-building and training initiatives that strengthen democracy in Europe. This knowledge is particularly relevant to Smart Venice’s ongoing work in studying feminist movements, far-right ideologies, and broader gender equality and intersectionality topics. It has already played a key role in shaping the proposal for the Horizon Europe project *YOU DARE (GA N° 101178147)* which examines gender constructions within far-right youth groups and their normalization across eight countries. The **transnational feminist network** developed through FIERCE offers valuable connections that Smart Venice could involve in co-design, co-creation, and participatory processes, as well as in capacity-building and training programmes. The **FIERCE training materials** will be integrated into Smart Venice’s e-learning platform and can form part of future training activities. For Smart Venice,

of particular significance is the self-defence manual for activists, co-created in the Italian Lab, which was jointly facilitated with partners from the Scuola Normale Superiore, and a group of teachers and academic activists participated, alongside feminist networks and organizations working on education for differences. These efforts align with comprehensive sex education and inclusive, intersectional practices in schools. Smart Venice will collaborate with feminist networks involved in the Italian Lab to disseminate the manual, potentially presenting it in the annual meeting of one of the networks in September. Some networks who have not participated in the co-creation process have communicated with partners involved about the diffusion of the manual to invite them to dedicated events. The **co-creation methodology** developed by SV for the FIERCE Labs provides a valuable foundation for future co-creation initiatives, while **communication materials** from the project will play a crucial role in promoting the self-defence manual and related outputs. A publication based on the State of the Art analysis developed in WP2 is also planned, and the FIERCE **Policy Toolkit** will serve as a resource for shaping future project proposals.

2. Exploitation

The knowledge created in the FIERCE project has already been valorized in the development of the Horizon Europe project YOU DARE (GA N° 101178147), which examines gender constructions of far-right youth groups and their normalization in mainstream discourse across eight countries. Participation in FIERCE was fundamental to shaping that proposal and will continue to inform future project applications and training courses. The **transnational feminist network** established through FIERCE has been particularly valuable in bringing together the expertise and perspectives of activists and researchers from diverse contexts, organizations, countries, and positions within feminism. This diversity was embraced through several transnational collaborations, such as the transnational Lab, the FIERCE campaign, and the Winter School, which provided a rich learning experience and strengthened Smart Venice's collaborative approach. The innovative methodology of the **FIERCE online course**, which integrates academic and activist forms of knowledge while challenging traditional hierarchies that privilege academia, serves as a model for future initiatives and could be replicated in upcoming training activities. The self-defence manual for activists, co-created within the Italian National Lab **FIERCE Action**, will be disseminated in collaboration with participating feminist networks, with one of the networks planning to present the manual at their annual meeting in September. Additionally, the co-creation methodology developed through the **FIERCE Labs** has expanded Smart Venice's expertise by exploring theoretical strands such as participatory and deliberative democracy, co-creation processes, and feminist pedagogies, enriching their existing knowledge base and offering a framework for future applications.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The network established with FIERCE researchers and sister projects such as CCINDLE and Push*Back*Lash has created a rich foundation for potential collaborations under new Horizon Europe calls, as evidenced by Aalborg University's inclusion in the consortium of the YOU DARE project. The **transnational feminist network** has also expanded Smart Venice's pool of contacts, providing valuable connections for participatory processes, co-creation activities, and training programmes. These stakeholders may be involved in future collaborations, including project proposals, the formation of new

networks, and the organization of conferences, roundtables, and other events. Academics and activists who contributed to the **FIERCE online course** represent a potential resource for upcoming training initiatives and collaborative ventures. The **Italian National Lab** enabled Smart Venice to establish a network of activists and organizations working in education for differences across multiple Italian cities, creating lasting ties that can support future initiatives. The networks developed through the FIERCE Labs have been instrumental in implementing the project's participatory components and could serve as a springboard for new collaborative activities. An academic **publication** based on the State of the Art report on transnational feminist organizations prepared for WP2 is planned and will be presented at the 5th ISA Forum of Sociology in 2025. Finally, networks created through the Italian Lab will play a central role in disseminating the self-defence manual published on the **FIERCE website**, while social media campaigns and press coverage are expected to amplify its reach. In past project activities such as the FIERCE campaign, social media has already proven to be a vital tool for building networks and fostering engagement.

4. Sustainability

In the YOU DARE project, Smart Venice is coordinating an open policy lab that serves as a platform for policy designers, implementers, practitioners, and activists committed to preventing and countering far-right radicalisation while promoting youth policies to foster civic engagement and democratic participation. Knowledge created in FIERCE, particularly on anti-gender movements and democratic innovations in WP3, will provide a key input for shaping the conceptualization and thematic focus of this lab. The **transnational feminist network** established through FIERCE has expanded Smart Venice's pool of contacts for participatory, co-creation, and training activities, creating opportunities for future collaborations such as joint project proposals, new networks, and events like conferences, roundtables, and workshops. With the outcome of the Italian National Lab, the self-defence manual published on the FIERCE website, Smart Venice will promote it in collaboration with the feminist organizations involved in the Italian lab. All contributing organizations have agreed to disseminate the manual through their networks, ensuring its reach to teachers and educators working to promote diversity in schools - often in the face of hostility from colleagues, school staff, parents, and media. The networks created during the **FIERCE Labs** were central to the project's participatory components and will remain a foundation for future initiatives. Outcomes of the labs and the co-created methodology are also highly relevant for establishing the Open Policy Lab in YOU DARE. Additionally, the **Italian lab** networks will help disseminate the self-defence manual widely, supported by social media campaigns and press coverage, which have already proven effective during previous FIERCE activities like the campaign. An academic **publication** based on the State of the Art analysis of transnational feminist organizations developed for WP2 is planned and will be presented at the 5th ISA Forum of Sociology in 2025. The project's **communication materials** are part of its enduring legacy and will continue to serve as references in future initiatives, while the **Policy Toolkit** provides valuable insights for shaping new project proposals and advocacy efforts.

5. Replication / Transferability

The **knowledge** developed in FIERCE can be adapted to meet the specific requirements of future projects and funding calls. The **transnational feminist network** established through the project has

significant potential to continue beyond FIERCE as a valuable space for grassroots, horizontal feminist initiatives - a structure that is currently not usual at the European level, with E.A.S.T. identified in our State of the Art as one of the few similar examples. To ensure its sustainability, it would be beneficial for the project, in coordination with participating feminist organizations, to explore whether there is sufficient interest and commitment to organize future meetings or initiatives. While a dedicated budget would be helpful, the primary challenge lies in identifying a core team to coordinate and sustain the network. The **online feminist course** also holds strong replication potential for projects or initiatives focusing on feminism, social movements, and democracy in Europe. For successful transferability, it is essential to contextualize the course content to reflect specific political and activist landscapes, given its focus on mobilizations and European political dynamics. The **self-defence manual** developed in the Italian lab could also be replicated in other countries, as many of the situations and hostilities faced by teachers are common across Europe. Translation of the manual would facilitate its transferability; however, since its first section reflects the Italian context, adaptation in collaboration with national activist networks would be necessary to ensure relevance. Similarly, the co-creation methodology developed for the **FIERCE Labs** offers a versatile model that can be applied in other projects and thematic areas. The knowledge and experience gained through this approach will directly inform Smart Venice's co-creation work in the YOU DARE project. Finally, the **Policy Toolkit** provides actionable insights that could inspire and strengthen future project proposals and advocacy initiatives.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the SV FIERCE Team

"The FIERCE project demonstrated the potential of feminist methodologies in knowledge creation, blending academic perspectives with activists' practical knowledge from diverse countries and sectors. This synergy fosters experience-sharing and supports the development of new strategies to counter the anti-gender backlash. The establishment of networks between civil society organizations, universities, and NGOs through the Labs has also shown great potential for cultivating future initiatives. Moreover, innovative participatory research methodologies explored during the project highlight their capacity to strengthen democratic practices and promote inclusive dialogue."

3.4.3.2. Individual Exploitation Plan - ViLabs (VIL)

ViLabs (VIL) is a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) based in Thessaloniki, Greece, with extensive experience in project coordination as well as the dissemination and exploitation of research results. ViLabs provides a wide range of research, development, and consulting services to national and international enterprises and organisations. As the coordinator of **FIERCE**, ViLabs has brought its expertise in managing Horizon Europe projects in the field of gender and research to ensure the successful implementation of the initiative. The team has been actively involved in all aspects of FIERCE, from financial and administrative oversight to scientific management, ensuring the effective delivery of the project's overall goals. In addition, ViLabs leads the dissemination and communication activities, ensuring that FIERCE's results are widely shared to raise awareness, influence policy actions, and contribute to the vision of a more democratic and gender-equal Europe.

This Individual Exploitation Plan outlines how VIL intends to sustain and further develop FIERCE's results beyond the project's completion.

1. Strategic Interest

The Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement analysis, developed within FIERCE, has significantly enhanced ViLabs' expertise and understanding of the contemporary dynamics of feminist movements in Greece and across Europe, as well as anti-gender strategies, rhetoric and mobilisations. This knowledge can be directly applied in the design and development of new Horizon Europe and other EU-funded project proposals, particularly those focusing on gender equality, democratic innovation, and social inclusion. As consultants to public sector institutions, ViLabs can also integrate this scientific foundation into its services, offering informed consulting, training, and facilitation activities. The framework provides a strong base for supporting stakeholders such as public authorities, research organisations, and civil society actors in addressing socio-political challenges and designing inclusive, evidence-based policies and initiatives. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has expanded ViLabs' pool of stakeholders and partners across Europe, creating valuable opportunities for future collaborations in Horizon Europe and other EU and national-funded projects. The strong ties built between feminist organisations and collectives at national and European levels and the ViLabs team members provide fertile ground for developing new project ideas that integrate co-creation activities and democratic innovations. This network enhances ViLabs' role as a connector between grassroots feminist movements and institutional actors, strengthening the organisation's capacity to facilitate dialogues, co-design processes, and multi-stakeholder engagement activities. It also positions ViLabs to support inclusive policymaking and innovation by bridging diverse perspectives from civil society and institutional frameworks. The **FIERCE training material** represents an innovative resource for capacity building and provides valuable knowledge that bridges academic expertise with intersectional practice. It can be integrated as an added component into ViLabs' training and mentoring services for organisations seeking to strengthen gender equality competencies, particularly in research, innovation, and governance settings. This resource also serves as an excellent internal training tool for the ViLabs team and for partners involved in Horizon Europe and other EU-funded projects focusing on gender and democracy. Additionally, ViLabs could explore ways to incorporate these materials into workshops with local authorities and private sector partners working on diversity and inclusion initiatives. The **FIERCE Actions** provide excellent examples of feminist mobilisation, bridging academic knowledge with grassroots practices, and offering tools for professionals to counter anti-gender backlash. They raise awareness on gender equality, LGBTQIA+ rights, reproductive rights, body autonomy, and reclaiming public spaces. Among these, ViLabs can highlight the Greek FIERCE Action developed by the *Boat Collective* as a case study to inspire new participatory and grassroots initiatives in Greece and beyond. This action's focus on community empowerment and creative mobilisation aligns closely with ViLabs' expertise in supporting democratic innovation processes. The action involved organising a three-day workshop for women, transgender people, migrants, and other marginalised groups, culminating in the writing and public performance of a play on themes of the body, borders, and remembrance. The intersectional approach of this action is particularly relevant in Greece, a country with significant migrant populations, and can serve as a reference for future projects and proposals engaging marginalised communities. In addition, the Italian FIERCE Action- the self-defence manual for teachers facing attacks on education on differences - stands out as an excellent result of co-creation and could also inform ViLabs' work in fostering inclusive and resilient educational practices. The co-creation methodology developed in the **FIERCE National Labs** will be a key reference for ViLabs' future projects, particularly in designing participatory workshops and multi-actor dialogues for fostering social change. It offers tested tools and practices that can enhance ViLabs' facilitation of co-design processes with stakeholders in complex socio-political environments. The **scientific publications, communication**

materials, and the **Policy Toolkit** have significantly enhanced ViLabs' team capacity and expertise in gender equality, democratic innovation, and feminist mobilisation. This enriched knowledge base is valuable not only for external collaborations but also for internal capacity building, as it can be distributed and embedded within the company to strengthen the skills of team members across departments. These outputs will also be referenced in ViLabs' advocacy, dissemination, and exploitation activities, bridging research findings with practical, impactful solutions for clients and partners. In operational terms, the core ViLabs team - including the project management, dissemination, and exploitation units - will lead the integration of these KERs into the company's strategic roadmap. Together, these results provide a foundation of expertise gained through the FIERCE project and offer a competitive advantage for proposal development, capacity building, and implementation of future initiatives.

2. Exploitation

The **Conceptual Framework** has strengthened ViLabs' organisational capacity by deepening the team's understanding of feminist and anti-gender mobilisation dynamics in Greece and across Europe. This enhanced expertise will be highly valuable for designing methodologies for new Horizon Europe and other EU-funded project proposals, especially those focusing on gender equality and democracy. The research framework can also be adapted and integrated into ViLabs' consulting, training, and facilitation services and it provides a scientific and intersectional foundation for advising clients on strategies to counter gender backlash and advance diversity and inclusion policies. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has expanded ViLabs' stakeholder pool across Europe, enabling the organisation to establish new collaborations and partnerships for co-creation activities and participatory processes. This network provides direct access to grassroots knowledge and innovative feminist practices, which can be applied in the design of inclusive and democratic governance models in future projects. The **FIERCE training material**, including the online course can inspire the development of tailored training modules and capacity-building activities for ViLabs' clients and partners and in other EU funded projects or in proposal writing. It also serves as a valuable internal learning resource to strengthen the team's expertise on gender, democracy, and intersectionality, which can enhance the quality of ViLabs' facilitation and mentoring services. The **FIERCE Actions**, particularly the Greek action by the Boat Collective and the Italian self-defence manual for teachers, provide replicable models for community empowerment and creative mobilisation. These actions inspire ViLabs to design and deliver impactful initiatives within diverse cultural and political contexts, with a focus on engaging marginalised groups and promoting intersectional approaches in other projects. Finally, the **scientific publications, communication materials, and Policy Toolkit** produced under FIERCE collectively enrich ViLabs' knowledge base and methodologies. They provide evidence-based insights and practical tools that can be integrated into ViLabs' project development, policy consulting, and stakeholder engagement activities. These KERs strengthen ViLabs' competitive edge in proposal writing and contribute to the creation of innovative solutions tailored to clients' and partners' needs.

3. Networking and Future Collaborations

The **Conceptual Framework** developed in FIERCE opens opportunities for ViLabs to engage in new Horizon Europe calls focusing on gender equality and democracy. It provides a shared language and analytical approach that can facilitate collaborations with research organisations, feminist networks and

other civil society organisations, and also public authorities in Greece and across Europe. This foundation strengthens ViLabs' capacity to design interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder projects that connect academic insights with applied methodologies in consultancy and innovation projects. The **Transnational Feminist Network** has expanded ViLabs' connections to a wide spectrum of feminist organisations, grassroots movements, and institutional actors. These links can create pathways for building new project consortia, co-creation processes, and joint advocacy campaigns in new projects. The network also positions ViLabs as a key facilitator for fostering dialogue and partnerships between grassroots activists, research institutions and policymakers. The **FIERCE training material** can serve as a bridge for initiating collaborations with universities, civil society organisations, and private sector actors interested in capacity-building programmes on gender equality, human rights and democracy. By sharing and adapting these resources, ViLabs can strengthen ties with current partners and attract new ones for future projects or consultancy assignments. Drawing inspiration from the **FIERCE Actions** ViLabs is well-placed to design participatory activities and campaigns that bring together diverse stakeholders. This reinforces its role as a connector in multidisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaborations aimed at promoting inclusive innovation. Finally, the **scientific publications, communication materials, and Policy Toolkit** enhance ViLabs' visibility and credibility in the European research and innovation ecosystem. They can be leveraged in building partnerships with academic institutions, NGOs, and public bodies, ensuring ViLabs remains an active participant in shaping future feminist and democratic agendas.

4. Sustainability

The FIERCE KERs will continue creating value for ViLabs beyond the project by serving as a foundation for new project proposals, capacity-building services, and consulting activities on gender equality and democratic innovation. The **conceptual and methodological** insights gained will be embedded in ViLabs' internal knowledge base, strengthening the expertise of its teams and informing future Horizon Europe and national initiatives. The **Transnational Feminist Network** and the participatory methodologies developed offer ready-to-use models for engaging diverse stakeholders in co-creation processes. Digital resources like the **training material, communication outputs, and the Policy Toolkit** can be reused in workshops and shared with ViLabs' public and private sector clients. These outcomes require no additional infrastructure but rely on continued engagement with partners and collaborators to ensure their relevance and evolution over time.

5. Replication / Transferability

FIERCE's interdisciplinary, multidimensional, multi-level **framework** built on a bottom-up approach to feminism and democracy is highly adaptable to other contexts, sectors, and regions. It can be integrated into future Horizon Europe and other EU-funded projects addressing gender, democracy, and social innovation. Minor adjustments would be needed to tailor the framework to specific socio-political environments, but its flexibility makes it a strong foundation for new methodologies in co-creation and participatory governance initiatives. The **Transnational Feminist Network** structure can be replicated in other thematic areas beyond gender equality, such as human rights, migration or environmental and climate justice. Its collaborative model provides a blueprint for building intersectional and intersectoral alliances at local, national, and transnational levels. **FIERCE's Training Material**, the self-paced course can be adapted for diverse audiences and sectors, including local authorities, universities, and civil

society organisations working on inclusion and diversity. Its concept serves also as a replicable element for other Horizon projects that involve stakeholder capacity building. The innovative approaches of **FIERCE Actions** provide transferable models for participatory initiatives and grassroots mobilisations in other countries. For example, the Greek Action by Boat Collective could inspire similar creative workshops engaging marginalised communities in public spaces. Adjustments to cultural and political contexts would enhance relevance and impact. The co-creation methodology of the **FIERCE Labs** is inherently flexible and can be also applied to a wide range of thematic areas and sectors. It offers a scalable model for participatory action research and dialogue-building, adaptable to varying group sizes, stakeholders, and institutional settings. The **Scientific Publications** serve as transferable resources for scholars and practitioners across disciplines. They can also inform curricula, training modules, and advocacy materials in other regions, supporting knowledge transfer and capacity building. **FIERCE's Communication Material**, the campaigns, podcasts, and rich project website developed during FIERCE provide a wealth of transferable ideas for communication and dissemination strategies in other gender-oriented projects. These materials showcase effective ways of bridging academic and activist voices, engaging diverse audiences, and countering anti-gender narratives. They can inspire similar formats in future EU-funded initiatives, offering a tested model for creating impactful, inclusive communication content.

6. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt by the VIL FIERCE Team

"In today's socio-political context, marked by the rise of far-right populism and anti-gender rhetoric, practices and politics, FIERCE has been a beacon of hope and a testament to the power of collective action. As a private company, ViLabs is deeply aware that organisations are not faceless entities - they are made up of people who want to be inspired and take pride in contributing to meaningful democratic change in Europe. This project has confirmed the urgent need to strengthen feminist and intersectional alliances at the European level to defend justice and advance the rights of women, LGBTQIA+ communities, and other marginalised groups. FIERCE has motivated ViLabs to invest further in transnational collaborations and to centre its work in an intersectional, inclusive and feminist perspective. Building an "engendered" democracy requires research and academia, the private sector, civil society, and policymaking institutions to come together in a shared effort to imagine and realise new possibilities for Europe. The lessons learned through FIERCE reaffirm our commitment to deepening transnational cooperation and building intersectoral alliances that share a common language and vision for a democratic Europe. Because there is no innovation without justice - and no democracy without solidarity".

3.5. FIERCE Replication / Transferability Guidebook - Feminist Democratic Innovation in Action: A Guide to Replication and Sustainability

3.5.1. Introduction

The *Replication and Transferability Guidebook: Feminist Democratic Innovation in Action* is a key component of the FIERCE Sustainability Strategy. Developed in the context of escalating transnational anti-gender movements, the rise of far-right populism, and the erosion of democratic norms, this guidebook responds to the pressing need for evidence-based, transferable strategies that can reinforce feminist democratic practices. It aims to equip stakeholders with adaptable tools to counteract these challenges and promote inclusive, participatory governance beyond the duration of the FIERCE project.

This Transferability Guidebook provides concrete pathways for adapting and replicating feminist innovative actions across diverse national and local contexts. It aims to foster cross-border solidarity, strengthen democratic participation and support feminist movements in navigating different political, cultural, and institutional settings. By combining practical insights, lived experience examples, and guiding principles, the guidebook serves as both a roadmap and a toolkit for advancing feminist democratic participation in Europe and beyond. Rooted in intersectional and cross-movement collaboration - core pillars of the FIERCE approach - the FIERCE Transferability Guidebook draws on co-participatory processes carried out in close partnership between all project partners and feminist activists, combining theoretical insights and practical experiences. Specifically, it focuses on the feminist Democratic Innovation Actions designed and implemented within *Work package WP4 – “Participatory research co-creation Labs”* and *Work package WP5 – “Innovative strategies and solution pathways”*, building on the conceptual framework laid out in *Work package WP3 – “Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy”* and *WP2 – “Feminist movements and democracies”*.

It also includes a curated mapping of grants and funding mechanisms - from public institutions to feminist foundations and international agencies - that align with the values of feminism, democracy, intersectionality, care, and community empowerment. This resource is intended to support grassroots actors, organisations, and activists in sustaining and expanding their work, while also inspiring new feminist democratic innovations beyond the lifespan of the FIERCE project.

Intended Audience & Use

This guidebook is primarily designed for feminist grassroots organisations, activists, civil society actors, municipal and regional authorities, and other stakeholders interested in implementing participatory, inclusive democratic processes. It can also serve as a resource for researchers, educators, and policymakers aiming to understand and apply principles of feminist democratic innovation.

What to Expect in This Guidebook

The FIERCE Transferability Guidebook provides a practical roadmap for replicating and adapting feminist democratic innovations, featuring tools, strategies, and reflections from FIERCE’s pilot actions. Readers will find:

- Key insights and lessons learned from feminist actors who led FIERCE Actions, based on a structured post-action questionnaire;
- A synthesis of foundational feminist principles developed through the project, including intersectionality, inclusion, co-creation, and horizontal governance;
- Adaptable approaches and illustrative examples of democratic innovations;
- A FIERCE Replication Canvas
- A curated map of funding opportunities to support the sustainability and scaling of feminist initiatives.

3.5.2. The FIERCE Actions

Within the framework of FIERCE's participatory action-research methodology, **18 FIERCE Actions** were implemented across the FIERCE countries. The FIERCE Actions emerged through two complementary pathways:

National Labs: Seven (7) Actions were developed through collaborative work within the FIERCE National Labs - groups of feminist organisations, collectives, and networks that engaged in regular meetings coordinated by FIERCE partners in each country. These Labs, part of the project's research-action methodology, provided space for collective reflection and co-creation on the themes of FIERCE. As defined in Deliverable D4.1, the FIERCE Labs were conceived as hybrid, action-oriented spaces of dialogue aimed at generating concrete, politically relevant outcomes.

Open Call: In parallel, to ensure openness and engagement with a wider spectrum of feminist actors, FIERCE launched an Open Call for proposals. This initiative allowed grassroots organisations and collectives outside the National Labs to conceptualise and implement Actions aligned with FIERCE's values and objectives. In total, **eleven (11) Actions** were selected as the result of this Open Call - advertised through the FIERCE communication channels between 31 July 2025 and 15 September 2025. The FIERCE Actions were expected to be political, cultural and/or artistic projects related to FIERCE's 5 intervention themes (Labour Market, Health and Reproductive Rights, LGBTQIA+ Rights, Migration, Gender-Based Violence) and to happen in one of the eight countries of the project (Greece, Denmark, Italy, Spain, France, Poland, Slovenia, Turkey).

The table below illustrates the complete list of the FIERCE Actions implemented featuring the country, the organisations, the thematic area covered by each action, the tile and a small description of the action.

Country	Organisation	Thematic Area	Title of Action	Summary
Denmark	Everyday Sexism Project	Fighting discrimination & sexism in marginalized group	Intersectional Bystander Workshop & Card Game at the Youth Democracy festival 2024	Dialogue card game and scenario-based workshop teaching youth to combat intersectional sexism & become an active bystander to marginalized groups.
Denmark	Center for Violence Prevention	GBV	Orange Days in Aalborg	Public events and art exhibition & theater, discussions & workshops with organisations & distribution of practical informational resources to raise awareness about GBV.
France	Tant que je serai noire	Black women political representation & rights	Savoir Pouvoir. Réapproprions nos droits démocratiques	Empowering initiative for black women and gender minorities to understand their democratic rights in France. Workshops, interactive seminars & a public event.
France	European Alternatives	Fighting Anti-Gender Mobilizations	Online Resources: How to fight Anti-Gender	Platform offering digital tools & documents by feminist NGOs for anti-gender resistance & a public event.
Greece	The Boat Collective	Migration	Musafir	3-day workshop on re-memory, bodies, borders, to conceive a theatre play with migrants
Greece	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	GBV, fighting anti-gender	FIERCE	Roundtables in 3 different Greek cities bringing together researchers & activists to share findings on anti-gender backlash. Thematic areas: legislative backlash & anti-sexist movements, feminist networks & fight against GBV. Based on horizontal methodology these meetings enriched research with local experiences.
Italy	Smart Venice	Education to Difference (schools & high schools)	Self-defense Manual for teachers	Self-defense manual with practical strategies for teachers addressing gender violence & anti-gender discourse
Italy	Tourbillon ETS	GBV, Housing, Care	Arti Feministe a Santa Chiara. Transformare, sentire, formarsi	Feminist urban space creation, feminist kitchen, and exploring care practices intersecting with gender, race & labor. A network of feminist practices & build a feminist community that use alternative ways of doing politics.
Poland	University of Gdańsk	Labour Rights	Women's Labour Rights	Campaign on women's labor rights, workshops on gender-specific labor and workplace rights & information to combat soft forms of gender-based discrimination at the workplace.
Poland	Fundacja Kocham Dębniaki	GBV, LGBTQIA+ rights, Migration	Gender Debunking Guerilla	QR code sticker campaign to combat gender stereotypes in public spaces (Warsaw – Krakow) & providing knowledge about gender-related issues.
Poland	Fundacja	Abortion	Akcja Aborcja	Workshops and information access about reproductive rights in rural

Country	Organisation	Thematic Area	Title of Action	Summary
	Widzialne			areas in Poland.
Slovenia	Mirovni Institut	Reproductive Rights	Reproductive Rights: On health, sexuality and equality of women	Exhibition presenting key milestones in history of reproductive rights and bodily autonomy in Slovenia: contraception, abortion, sexual education, artificial insemination & parenting rights, violence in reproductive health.
Slovenia	Transfeminist TransAkcija	LGBTQIA+ and trans Rights	LGBTQIA+ Radar	Public awareness Campaign and database on anti-LGBTQIA+ violence in media, public events, discriminatory laws
Spain	Mujeres Supervivientes	Fight Anti-Gender Movements	Feminist Day: Theory & Action in the face of anti-feminism	Roundtable & raise awareness campaign on anti-feminism in Spain
Spain	Parcela de Tierra	Intersectionality & Decoloniality	La Cenicera	Public event aiming at creating links between intersectional feminists, decolonial & queer organisations, migrant & artistic organisations to promote gender equality and combat extreme right-wing discourse in Spain in the public space. Round tables, dinner and cultural event open to collectives & general public.
Turkey	Koç University	Feminism and Democracy	Feminist co-creation: strengthening voice & increasing visibility	The action produced a policy brief on existing participatory democratic processes combining activist lens & scholarly knowledge. Production of a mini film that captured activists' ideas about democracy & the feminist movement and their imaginations about the future of both.
Turkey	Kadın İşçi	Labor market	Internal training and forum	A two-day internal training program on feminist methodology and politics with Kadın İşçi reporters and volunteers. A workshop where feminist solidarity strategies for women workers' resistance and strikes were discussed. Feminist activists attended this meeting to deliberate on the ways that feminists can better contribute to women's struggles & how women can overcome the boundaries drawn by male-dominated unions.
Turkey	Özgür Renkler	LGBTQIA+ rights	Queer-Trans Feminist Cartoon School	A 2-day workshop, where queer and feminist illustrators met with LGBTI+ participants, learned cartoon techniques & created artistic production against anti-LGBTI+ ideologies. The artists were allowed to express their stories, experiences, and social struggles.

Table 10: Complete list of the FIERCE Actions

Formats - Approaches and outputs of the FIERCE Actions

As analysed in Deliverable 4.2 "*Report on democratic innovative practices*", the FIERCE Actions were designed to empower feminist initiatives in addressing local and national challenges, without imposing rigid deliverable requirements. While not all actions resulted in materials intended for broad dissemination, most generated meaningful outcomes, ranging from capacity-building and political mobilisation to the strengthening of local and transnational networks. Examples include:

- 1 set of cartoons on LGBTQIA+ rights in Turkey
- 1 set of dialogue cards games on fighting sexism from Denmark
- 1 set of exhibition panels produced in Slovenian and English and [available online](#)
- 1 film in Turkish and one policy brief in Turkish and English
- 1 [online platform](#) on fighting anti-gender in French
- 1 database and online platform about LGBTQI+ rights in Slovenian
- 1 manual for teachers on facing violence notably when teaching about sexual and reproductive rights in Italian.
- 1 Booklet about abortion in Polish
- Campaign stickers on rights of women in Polish and Ukrainian

These outputs serve as practical illustrations of feminist democratic innovation in action. They offer valuable materials for adaptation and replication by feminist actors working in diverse contexts.

3.5.3. Methodology of the Transferability Guidebook

The development of this Replication and Transferability Guidebook is grounded in a dual methodological approach that combines **1. theoretical and political grounding of feminist democratic innovation and 2. practical insights from FIERCE Action carriers.**

1. Theoretical Grounding: Core Feminist Principles

The theoretical principles presented are grounded in the findings of FIERCE's D 2.1 "*Report of field work results*" which explored the structural and contextual conditions enabling or constraining feminist mobilisation at national and transnational levels. Through extensive fieldwork in eight different country contexts over the period 2010-23, the project examined feminist movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain. This period has been characterised both by the growing momentum of transnational feminist activism and by the intensification of radical right and neoconservative attacks on gender rights.

The analysis conducted by the FIERCE team sought to understand how feminist movements respond to and resist these challenges while fostering democratic innovation. The research focused on how gender narratives are framed and communicated, how movements engage with or confront other political actors, and how internal tensions and conflicts are navigated. In doing so, it revealed the transformative role feminist activism plays in reshaping political imaginaries and practices.

2. Practice-Based Insights: Post-Action Questionnaire

Practical Insights were drawn from the responses of FIERCE Action carriers to a structured post-action questionnaire conducted by European Alternatives. The questions focused on the various dimensions of democratic innovation identified within FIERCE. The questionnaire was developed by European Alternatives and reviewed by FIERCE consortium members, notably the scientific team from Aalborg University and ViLabs as project coordinator.

The post-action questionnaire, titled *“Questionnaire on the Democratic Innovation of Your FIERCE Action”* received 18 responses from all FIERCE Action carriers across Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey. As highlighted in Deliverable 4.2, it is important to note that one-third of the FIERCE Actions (7 out of 18) were coordinated by FIERCE project partners. The analysis thus incorporates both the perspectives of the NGOs and collectives that led the Actions, and the input of FIERCE partners, offering a holistic and well-rounded consultation of the FIERCE stakeholder community.

This tool explored the experiences and interests of FIERCE Action carriers, assessing the effectiveness and impact of their activities while identifying key elements suitable for replication. A dedicated section of the questionnaire focused on the benefits Action carriers gained from implementing their initiatives. Their ideas, reflections and feedback, form a valuable foundation for this Guidebook and are considered a core element in assessing the transferability and replication potential of the FIERCE Actions.

The synthesis of these two dimensions - practical feedback and theoretical grounding - shapes the content and recommendations of this guidebook.

3.5.4. Core Feminist Principles

The core feminist principles included in this section are directly informed by the body of work of *D2.1 “Report of field work results”*. They emerge from the lived experiences, strategic choices, and political visions of feminist movements across Europe and serve as a foundation for developing inclusive, resilient, and context-sensitive approaches in the Transferability Guidebook.

1. Intersectionality as a Core Framework: Recognizing overlapping forms of discrimination (race, class, gender, etc.) as central to understanding power and oppression.

2. Care as a Political and Organizational Principle: Positioning care (emotional, relational, reproductive labor) not as private/domestic, but as a radical political practice.

3. Democratic Innovation: Feminist movements foster new forms of participation, inclusion, and decision-making that go beyond conventional representative democracy.

4. Resistance to Patriarchy, Neoliberalism, and the Far-Right: Feminist movements respond actively to systemic inequalities, austerity policies, and anti-gender backlash.

5. Transnational Solidarity and Networking: Cross-border alliances and strategy sharing (e.g., #MeToo, Ni Una Menos) create a sense of global feminist community.

6. Innovative Repertoires of Action: Feminist activism uses creative, embodied, symbolic, and emotional responses / actions to challenge norms (e.g., mourning as protest, street performance).

7. Digital Feminist Activism: Online platforms are used for awareness, mobilization, education, and community building.

8. Internal Reflexivity and Debate: Feminist movements continuously interrogate their own practices (e.g., debates on universalism vs. intersectionality).

3.5.5. Practice-Based Insights and replication elements

“The seed we planted is producing a spread of our practices, and this is absolutely innovative!”

— FIERCE Action carrier, Tourbillon – ITALY

Drawing from the responses to the post-action questionnaire (see *Methodology*), this section identifies recurring benefits experienced by FIERCE Action carriers. These benefits have been grouped into a set of replicable elements - concrete outcomes and enabling factors that contributed to the success and sustainability of the feminist actions implemented through the project.

While each action was deeply context-specific, these shared elements reflect underlying conditions, practices, and impacts that can be adapted and transferred to other feminist initiatives. They offer inspiration and guidance for those seeking to develop similar approaches in diverse political, cultural, and institutional environments. The findings complement and expand on those presented in Deliverable 4.2 (Section 4.1.4 – *Replicability*).

Respondents highlighted a series of features and strategies that enabled impactful outcomes and can serve as replicable components in other settings:

1. Open and Collaborative Frameworks

Horizontal, participatory structures were crucial in ensuring meaningful engagement and ownership among participants. All of the FIERCE actions thrived through volunteer-led co-organisation, which fostered trust, accountability, and a sense of shared purpose.

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [All](#)

- ✓ **Replication efforts should aim to embed inclusive co-creation as a foundation for sustainable action.**

2. Embedding Intersectionality

Successful actions actively included under-represented groups and created time and space for them to shape agendas. Feminist, queer, and anti-racist perspectives were often integrated through creative methods - such as theatre, music, and poetry, cartoons - making complex topics more accessible and emotionally resonant.

- ✓ **These inclusive, artistic approaches offer adaptable formats for replication.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Turkey](#), [Greece](#), [Denmark](#)

3. Dialogue-Based Educational Tools

Interactive formats - including role-play, visual materials, and card games - proved highly effective, especially with younger audiences. These tools sparked critical discussions and made learning experiential.

- ✓ **They can be readily tailored and deployed in a wide range of socio-political contexts.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Denmark](#), [Italy](#)

4. Reclaiming Public Spaces through Community-Based Feminist Interventions

FIERCE actions showed how public space can be reimagined and re-signified through feminist interventions—ranging from street performances and visual installations to neighbourhood-based events. These activities not only raised awareness and offered high visibility but also fostered cultural resonance and new forms of community-making, especially when grounded in local contexts and co-created with residents. By reclaiming public spaces, these interventions gave visibility to marginalised groups, challenged dominant narratives, and built stronger local ties.

- ✓ **Replication initiatives should explore the transformative potential of public space interventions that are rooted in community engagement and feminist values.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Italy](#), [Slovenia](#)

5. Bridging Activism, Academia, and Institutional Engagement

FIERCE actions highlighted the powerful impact of connecting grassroots activism, academic knowledge, and institutional processes. Several initiatives demonstrated how community-driven knowledge can enrich policy dialogue, while others showed how creating spaces where theoretical insights meet lived experiences can co-create new knowledge and strengthen feminist ecosystems. This bridging role supports more grounded, inclusive, and transformative decision-making—rooted in the realities of those most affected by inequalities. Strengthening alliances between academics, feminist activists, and policymakers proved essential in amplifying voices, deepening impact, and fostering long-term feminist change.

- ✓ **Replication initiatives should prioritise creating and maintaining intersectional, cross-sectoral spaces for dialogue and co-creation.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Turkey](#), [Spain](#), [Greece](#)

6. Giving Access to Practical Resources

Distributing information materials - such as booklets, flyers, manuals or advocacy tools with direct and accessible content (including contact information for support services) proved empowering for participants, especially those from marginalized communities.

- ✓ **This practical element enhances autonomy and awareness and can be integrated across a wide range of action formats.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Italy](#), [Poland](#), [France](#), [Denmark](#)

7. **Strong Communication Networks**

Well-developed communication strategies helped actions gain visibility, engage wider audiences, and create lasting ties with stakeholders.

- ✓ **Investing in networks of dissemination and collaboration lays the groundwork for future projects and can serve as a replicable good practice for feminist initiatives.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Turkey](#), [Spain](#), [Poland](#)

8. **Interactive Campaigns Bridging Awareness and Action**

Campaigns using QR codes, stickers, digital platforms, and multimedia content were especially effective in restrictive or conservative environments where in-person activism carried risks. These tools helped spread feminist and LGBTQIA+ knowledge while inviting participation. Interactive content - such as quizzes or videos - encouraged users to test assumptions and deepen engagement.

- ✓ **Replicating this approach can enhance reach and impact, particularly among younger or digitally engaged audiences.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Poland](#)

9. **Using Arts, Comics, Theatre, and Poetry to Transcend Borders**

Creative expression provided a safe, resonant space for voices often excluded from mainstream discourse. Art became a democratic tool - a form of knowledge production, activism, and connection.

- ✓ **Replicating this method supports storytelling that resists erasure and fosters empathy and solidarity across differences.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [Greece](#), [Turkey](#), [Denmark](#)

10. **Giving Access to Knowledge to Marginalised People**

Feminist actions created accessible spaces - often in city centres and rural areas - that welcomed those excluded from traditional political education. These became hubs for learning, exchange, and empowerment. Providing safe, visible venues for dialogue about power, race, gender, and reproductive rights helps individuals gain confidence, develop advocacy skills, and shape their futures.

- ✓ **This model can be adapted in cities and rural areas alike, depending on local needs.**

Examples of FIERCE Actions: [France](#), [Poland](#), [Greece](#) These reflections confirm that many of the democratic innovations piloted within FIERCE are not only contextually impactful but also transferable, so long as the core values of inclusivity, intersectionality, and co-creation remain at their heart.

Summary: 10 Replicable Elements of the FIERCE Actions

1. **Inclusive co-creation frameworks** – Horizontal, participatory structures fostering ownership and trust.
2. **Embedding intersectionality** – Addressing multiple forms of discrimination through creative methods.
3. **Dialogue-based educational tools** – Engaging formats like role-play, card games, and visual materials.
4. **Community-based public space interventions & strategic local engagement** – Feminist actions reclaiming public visibility and resonance in community-led design and shared cultural contexts.
5. **Bridging activism, academia, and policy** – Cross-sector collaboration that deepens impact.
6. **Distribution of practical resources** – Materials that empower communities and increase access to support.
7. **Strong communication networks** – Visibility and reach through thoughtful dissemination strategies.
8. **Interactive campaigns** – Using tech and media tools to engage and mobilise audiences.
9. **Creative expression** – Art, theatre, and poetry as tools for resistance, memory, and dialogue.
10. **Access to political education** – Welcoming spaces for marginalised groups to learn, reflect, and lead.

3.5.6. From Principles to Practice: A Feminist Methodology for Replication

The Replication and Transferability Guidebook is shaped by a dual foundation: the feminist values that have emerged through years of movement-based activism and reflection, and **the lived experiences of FIERCE Action carriers who operationalised these values in diverse local contexts**. The ten replicable elements identified through the post-action questionnaire provide concrete, adaptable models of feminist democratic innovation - models that put intersectionality, care, co-creation, and resistance into action. In parallel, the feminist principles drawn from FIERCE's fieldwork (Deliverable 2.1) offer a conceptual and political compass that gives deeper meaning to these practices.

The interplay between principles and practice is central: for example, the use of public space interventions and street performances resonates with feminist strategies of reclaiming visibility and resisting marginalisation, while horizontal, participatory structures reflect a commitment to internal reflexivity and democratic innovation. Many of the FIERCE Actions also bridged local activism with institutional engagement - a form of transnational networking and strategic resistance that feminist movements have long practiced.

Rather than treating these as separate layers, the FIERCE Transferability Guidebook sees the theoretical and practical dimensions as mutually reinforcing. Together, they offer a roadmap for designing, implementing, and sustaining feminist actions in varied contexts - rooted in shared values but responsive to local specificities. This synthesis is what enables FIERCE's contributions to be both context-aware and transferable.

3.5.7 FIERCE Replication Canvas

To support the replication of feminist democratic innovations piloted in FIERCE, this Transferability Guidebook includes a **Replication Canvas** - a practical planning tool designed to help activists, educators, and organisations adapt core principles and successful elements of the Actions to their local contexts. It can be used in workshops, strategic planning sessions, or self-assessment processes to guide the design of new feminist initiatives.

 FIERCE Replication Canvas <i>Template for planning the adaptation and replication of a feminist democratic innovation</i>		
Section	Guiding Question	Your Notes
Title / Name of the Planned Action	What will your initiative be called?	
Objective	What is the main goal of your action? What change do you hope to make?	
Target Audience / Communities	Who are the people most impacted by or involved in this action?	
FIERCE Inspiration(s)	Which FIERCE action(s) or replicable element(s) are you building on? (e.g., co-creation, public space interventions, artistic tools)	
Core Feminist Principles Applied	Which principles are at the heart of your approach? (e.g., intersectionality, care, transnational solidarity)	
Local Context Considerations	What are the political, social, or cultural specifics of your setting? What challenges or enablers do you anticipate?	
Methods and Tools	What tools or formats will you use (e.g., theatre, booklets, dialogue-based education, digital campaigns)?	
Alliances and Partners	Who will you work with (e.g., activists, local authorities, artists, educators)?	
Accessibility and Inclusion	How will you ensure the action is accessible, safe, and inclusive for all, especially marginalised communities?	
Evaluation and Reflection	How will you assess impact and integrate learning throughout the process?	

Figure 71: FIERCE Replication Canvas – A planning tool to support the adaptation and scaling of feminist democratic innovations.

3.5.7. Access to Finance: Funding Opportunities for Feminist Democratic Innovation

Feminist grassroots initiatives often face systemic challenges in accessing sustainable funding, including eligibility barriers, administrative constraints, and limited institutional support. This section of the FIERCE Transferability Guidebook offers a curated mapping of grants and funding mechanisms, from public institutions to feminist foundations and international agencies, that align with the values of intersectionality, care, and community empowerment. It is designed to help grassroots actors, organisations and feminist activists, sustain and expand their work and to inspire new feminist democratic innovations beyond the lifespan of the FIERCE project.

Key Considerations Before Applying:

- ✓ Is the funder aligned with your feminist values and political goals?
- ✓ Do they support informal groups or non-registered collectives?
- ✓ What reporting and monitoring obligations will you need to meet?
- ✓ Can you apply through a fiscal sponsor or intermediary?
- ✓ Does your proposed work align with the funder's geographic or thematic priorities?

Tips for Grassroots Feminist Fundraising:

- ✓ Consider partnering with an established organisation for fiscal eligibility.
- ✓ Emphasise lived experience and community impact rather than simply formal KPIs.
- ✓ Seek small or micro-grants with low administrative burdens.
- ✓ Cultivate long-term relationships with funders who value trust and narrative.
- ✓ Use storytelling, art, and emotion as legitimate forms of project framing.

Funding Opportunities

The following table maps relevant funding opportunities accessible to feminist organisations in Europe and internationally. Each entry includes a link, thematic focus, and recent funding activity where available.

This funding map is not exhaustive but offers a solid starting point for feminist actors seeking to sustain and expand their work. For lasting impact, we encourage continued engagement with local and transnational networks, strategic collaborations, and creative advocacy that centre care, inclusion, and collective power.

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
Denmark	The Danish Youth Council	DUF - Danish Youth Council	Umbrella organisation	Broadly NGOs in Denmark and therefore also many of the feminist organizations	They distribute around 5-6m. euro per year. Here is one of their official reports on their economyà https://duf.dk/fileadmin/user_upload/Editor/document/s/Om_DUF/Delegeretmoede/2021/12_11_12_regnskab.pdf
Denmark	Fundamental Rights Initiative (FRI) collaboration between Global Focus and Nyt Europa	Globalt Fokus - The FRI grant - Fundamental Rights Initiative	NGOs (but co-founded by the EU)	NGOs (particularly those who focus on migration and LGBTQ+ rights - e.g. LGBT+ Denmark, Danish Refugee Council Youth) - also a clearly feminist one: An activist group called Men against patriarchy	1,5 m. euro over the last couple of years
Poland	FEM FUND	https://femfund.pl/en/	Grassroots Fund	Small grants available for feminist projects and organizations (also informal) with very easy reporting	Yes, several thousands of Euro's in the last year
Poland	Fundacja Batorego	https://www.batory.org.pl/	Foundation	Polish Soros partner, numerous calls for grants, also for feminist projects and initiatives, but subjected to peer review	Few hundred thousand Euros per year
EU level	WAVE - WOMEN AGAINST VIOLENCE EUROPE	https://wave-network.org/	European feminist organisation	Feminist civil society organisations (CSOs) which are part of their network. They launch yearly regranting activities among their	2025 call for regranting activities: https://wave-network.org/wave-regranting/#call-for-proposals-2025

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
				members from the funds they receive from the European Commission, European Education and Culture Executive Agency, under the CERV Programme.	
EU level	ILGA Europe	https://www.ilga-europe.org/about-us/	European feminist organisation	European LGBTI organisations.	call for 2025 project proposals on Socio-economic justice: https://www.ilga-europe.org/the-movement/our-current-programmes/socio-economic-justice/
France	The Support Fund for Feminist Organizations (FSOF)	https://www.afd.fr/en/support-fund-feminist-organizations	Public/National Fund	Feminist Organizations, local civil society organizations working to promote gender equality and the rights of women and girls	€120 million over three years (2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023) to fund the activities of feminist movements around the world. Call for projects 2024 -2025à https://www.afd.fr/en/calls-projects
France	Mediterranean Women's Fund	https://www.medwomensfund.org	Multilateral Foundation	Women's movements in all of the countries of the Mediterranean region that demonstrate a strong commitment to equal rights for women and men and to human rights principles Associations or groups led by women: the majority of the	There are currently no open call for proposals in 2024. But their budget in 2023 was: 2.168.316 euros https://www.medwomensfund.org/docs/ffmed-lettre-appel-dons-2023.pdf

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
				top management must be women.	
France	Fondation de France	https://www.fondationdefrance.org/fr/	Foundation	Environment, education, health, culture, assistance to vulnerable people. They provide concrete and sustainable solutions in all areas of public interest, in France and internationally.	Latest call on Digital freedoms and democracy, combatting cyber violence (€50k - €150k) https://www.fondationdefrance.org/fr/appels-a-projets/libertes-et-democratie-numeriques
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Fund for Women (BFW)	https://bgfundforwomen.org/en/	National feminist fund	Bulgarian Fund for Women is the only indigenous donor in Bulgaria that raises funds and gives grants to local NGOs working to advance women's and girls' rights, eliminate gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and discrimination, achieve gender equality in all spheres of life and make a social change.	BFW will distributed over € 1 million to 25 Civil Society Organizations in 2024. Funding Opportunities for 2025 à https://bgfundforwomen.org/2025/04/10/novo-izdanie-na-programa-misia-vuzmoznina/
Spain	Calala Fondo de Mujeres	https://calala.org/	The only women's fund present in Spain. Part of 'Prospera', a network of more than 40 women's funds around the world.	Groups, networks and organizations of women and feminists who organise themselves in Spain and Central America to defend human rights and social justice, promoting real changes in their lives and in their communities. Organisations and groups that	Their last call for 2024 here: https://calala.org/abrimos-tercera-convocatoria-de-fondo-dalia/

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
				play a key role in advancing women's rights	
Croatia	Ecumenical Women's Initiative	https://eiz.hr/en/mission/	Croatian non-profit organisation and women's fund	Women-led organisations and women theologians in Croatia and in Bosnia & Herzegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia for creative and innovative approaches to address issues which impact on their lives and those of their communities	Their last call for 2025 here: https://eiz.hr/en/grant/organisational-support-grants/
Germany	Filia.die frauenstiftung	https://www.filia-frauenstiftung.de/en/	German Foundation	Supports projects by and for women, girls and LGBTIQ+ that aim to bring about structural change – in Central and Eastern Europe, in the Global South and in Germany. Supports grassroots groups and networks that stand up for women's rights and want to encourage structural changes. Supports projects and initiatives that work for freedom from violence, demand social participation and strengthen democratic structures.	There are currently no open call for proposals in 2024. But filia has so far enabled over 340 self-determined activities and projects of women, girls and LGBTIQ+ in 40 countries in different parts of the world (as of 2020). Approximately 80 per cent of the funds flow to projects worldwide.
Serbia	Reconstruction Women's Fund	https://www.rwfund.org/eng/	Local women's foundation in Serbia Multilateral agency	Support autonomy of women's groups, whose programs affect the public and lead to strategic changes.	No open calls for 2025 but their support until 2024 à https://www.rwfund.org/eng/programs/womens-

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
				Stimulate communication and exchange of women's activist, academic, artistic and pacifist experience and knowledge	initiatives/general-support/
Ukraine	Ukrainian Women's Fund	https://uwf.org.ua/en/	Foundation	Support women's/feminist organizations, make for their participation in the development of a powerful, effective and mass women's/feminist movement capable of protecting women's rights and promoting gender equality in all areas. Activists and representatives of women's/feminist organizations	Open call for travel grants opportunity for activists and representatives of women's/feminist organizations as part of the Women's Voice and Leadership - Ukraine Project https://uwf.org.ua/en/travel-grants-for-activists-and-representatives-of-womens-feminist-organizations/
Armenia	Women's Fund Armenia	https://womenfundarmenia.org/	Local grant-making organization	supports women and girls in Armenia through capacity building, providing financial support and development of feminist movement	https://womenfundarmenia.org/call-for-cross-regional-cooperation-projects/
Georgia	Women's Fund in Georgia	https://www.womenfundgeorgia.org/en/WhatWeDo/Grantmaking/3677	Local funding organization dedicated to sustaining the women's rights' movement in Georgia	Awards grants to women organizations, initiative groups or individuals, that work on the improvement of women's lives	https://www.womenfundgeorgia.org/en/WhatWeDo/Grantmaking/3677
United Kingdom	Rosa	https://rosauk.org/	Funding organisation in UK	Rosa was formed to address the acute lack of funding for the women and girls sector.	Rosa's Rise Fund provides organisational development funding for Black and

Country	Donor's name	Link	Type of donor	Eligible Entities	Recent Activity / Notes
				Over the years, they have adapted and grown to respond to the pressing issues affecting women and girls' safety and equity across the UK.	racially minoritised-led women's and girls' organisations across the UK. Through this fund, we offer two-year grants of up to £40,000 to organisations with an income of between £30,000 and £300,000. https://rosauk.org/our-programmes/rise-fund/
International	Cartier Women's Initiative	https://www.cartierwomensinitiative.com/	Annual International entrepreneurship program	Empowering women and impact entrepreneurs. Founded by Cartier in 2006, the program is open to women-run and women-owned businesses from any country and sector that aim to have a strong and sustainable social and/or environmental impact.	Call for 2025 for Women-owned, women-run businesses focused on positive social or environmental change. €100k + additional leadership and strategy support https://www.cwi-portal.com/submit

Table 11: Access to finance for civil society - feminist organisations and collectives

3.5.8. The FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network: A Legacy for Sustainability and Collaboration

One of the most significant assets created within FIERCE for ensuring the sustainability of its outcomes is the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network. Developed and coordinated by European Alternatives (EA), the Network provides a transnational platform for sharing ideas, strategies, and solidarity among feminist activists, researchers and organisations resisting anti-gender movements across Europe and beyond.

The Transnational Feminist Network was launched in person during **the FIERCE Week in Venice (4–7 November 2024)**, which brought together more than 50 participants from eight European countries, including feminist activists, researchers, Advisory Board members, and representatives from sister projects. The event served as both the formal launch and an initial space for members to outline shared objectives:

- Creating a safe and supportive environment for knowledge exchange and peer learning.
- Building coordinated actions to counter anti-gender backlash.
- Strengthening alliances between civil society, academia, and policy actors.

Following the launch, the Transnational Feminist Network held a series of three online meetings and a final in-person gathering in Brussels, ensuring continuity of dialogue and joint action:

- **1st Online Meeting (19 February 2025)** – Focused on the role of feminist activists in local struggles and coordination against anti-gender movements. Included a presentation of FIERCE’s research findings on the influence of well-funded conservative forces in shaping public discourse and policy, followed by discussion on feminist mobilisations for International Women’s Day.
- **2nd Online Meeting (18 April 2025)** – Featured speakers from Turkey, Serbia, and Greece sharing insights on current protests, feminist student movements, and responses to political repression, as well as a workshop on Resisting Cyberviolence by *Feministes contre le cyberharcèlement*.
- **3rd Online Meeting (27 May 2025)** – Gathered voices from Georgia, Hungary, Romania, and the ACT (Against Conversion Therapy) initiative, addressing threats to democracy, restrictions on NGOs, and successful civil society campaigns. Participants also discussed the future format of the network, with a preference for regular hybrid meetings.

The final in-person meeting took place on **19 June 2025 in Brussels**, as part of the pre-conference programme of the FIERCE Final Conference. Hosted at the *RoSa Library*, it combined a book launch of two major **FIERCE publications** with strategic discussions on the Network’s future. The event gathered 40 participants (32% from academia and 68% from feminist organisations, NGOs, and political institutions) and reinforced the momentum for ongoing collaboration.

Participants and Reach

The Transnational Feminist Network mailing list grew to over 300 registered members, with online meetings attracting an average of 35 - 40 participants from diverse backgrounds. The majority represented feminist organisations and collectives, with a significant proportion from academia, including early-career researchers.

Sustainability Potential

The Transnational Feminist Network is envisioned as a living legacy of FIERCE beyond the project’s funding period. By connecting a diverse community of feminist actors, it creates a foundation for:

- Disseminating FIERCE's research findings and methodologies in the long term.
- Replicating co-creation and advocacy practices in new contexts.
- Serving as a mobilisation hub for joint advocacy campaigns, future research projects, and EU funding opportunities.

As such, the Transnational Feminist Network represents a concrete vehicle for sustaining and expanding the impact of FIERCE's work, ensuring that the project's feminist and intersectional approach to democratic innovation continues to inform activism, policy, and scholarship across Europe.

4. Conclusion

Over its three-year implementation, the FIERCE project has built a strong and lasting foundation for feminist democratic innovation across Europe. Through strategic communication, targeted dissemination, and meaningful engagement with diverse stakeholders, the consortium has ensured that the project's results are not only visible but also accessible, usable, and impactful well beyond the funding period.

From establishing a strong visual identity and dynamic online presence to facilitating high-impact events, transnational networks, and co-creation processes, FIERCE has created spaces where activists, researchers, and policymakers can connect, exchange, and collaborate. The project's dissemination activities have reached thousands across Europe, sparking dialogue, informing policy debates, and strengthening alliances against anti-gender backlash.

As the project formally concludes in August 2025, its mission continues through the sustained use and promotion of its tools, scientific publications, research outcomes and networks. These will serve as living platforms for knowledge exchange, mutual learning, and coordinated action, ensuring that the spirit and vision of FIERCE endure.

The consortium's collective efforts have laid out not just a roadmap, but a call to action: to carry forward the momentum, to integrate feminist perspectives into democratic processes, and to build a more inclusive, equitable and engendered democracy in Europe.

Annex 1: KPIs Monitoring

Status of the Communication KPIs (M36)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements <u>by M36</u>
[C1] Project Identity and Branding	Templates for project documents, reports and presentations	YES
[C2] Dissemination Materials	1 brochure, 1 poster (eng. & national languages)	ALL materials in English and national languages
[C3] Project Website	Y1: 250, Y2: 500, Y3: 750+ (monthly visits) // 1 blog post per month	8 K visitors (now called users), 35 K views 34 blogs (M36)
[C4] Social Media Strategy	Y1: 1 post/week (Twitter: 500 followers, Facebook: 300 Likes and LinkedIn:100 followers) Y2: 2 posts/week (Twitter: 700 followers, Facebook:500 Likes and LinkedIn:300 followers) Y3: 2 posts/week (Twitter: 1000 followers, Facebook:700 Likes and LinkedIn: 500 followers)	Facebook: 269 posts, 332 likes, 440 followers Instagram: 129 posts, 443 followers LinkedIn: 300 posts, 731 followers X (former Twitter): 444 posts, 231 followers
[C5] Videos/Podcasts	>3 project videos / >8 podcasts (1 x country on pilot actions) >300 views per YouTube video 500 >actual listens to each podcast episode	23 videos available (15 on YouTube, 8 on social media) 528 YouTube channel views 8 Podcasts (1 x country on pilot actions) > 500 listeners reached YouTube and Spotify
[C6] Networking Events	>30 networking activities are foreseen during the project's lifetime	65 networking activities
[C7] Generating positive media coverage	>12 press releases, >6 E-Newsletters, 10 publications, 1 book >30 articles; >15 interviews	12 Press Releases, 17 E-Newsletters, 29 Publications, 1 co-edited volume book, 10 interviews – articles

Table 12: Status of Communication KPIs (M36)

Status of the Dissemination KPIs (M36)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements by M36
[D1] Scientific Publications, Conferences & Workshops // Participation in events	>10 Open Access scientific papers published 1 Open Access co-edited volume >65 participants involved in the final conference	29 scientific papers published 1 open access book Final Conference: 195 onsite and online participants
[D2] Other Open access publications policy briefs	1 toolkit and 3 policy briefs in 8 languages	3 Policy Briefs 1 Policy Toolkit
[D3] FIERCE Labs & Democratic innovations pilot actions; Feminist Summer School	> 150 participants in the 3 cycles of Co-creation Labs in 8 countries > 80 participants to each Transnational Labs online session 65 participants involved in the Transnational Network > 16 grassroots organizations partnering the innovation actions in 8 countries > 25 participants to the Feminist Summer School > 500 users of the online course created disseminate the feminist Summer School	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Total participants to national lab meetings: first co-creation cycle (149), second co-creation cycle (137), third co-creation cycle (129) 2. Total participants to the transnational lab meetings: 26 to each session. In both meetings participants were distributed 21 from national labs and 5 from European feminist organisations (some of the participants changed between the two meetings). Total participants of the third transnational lab meetings: 31 (3 participants from the FIERCE Actions, 13 from the FIERCE National Labs, 15 FIERCE partners) 3. Participants to the first FIERCE online roundtable (registered people 116 and between 65-60 attendees). <p>Total participants FIERCE Week in Venice: 50 from eight European countries – feminist activists, researchers, Advisory Board members, and representatives from sister projects. Over four days, the programme combined three major components: the Third Transnational Lab, the FIERCE Winter School, and the launch of the FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. FIERCE Course online users: 47 (ongoing)
[D4] Synergies/ Clustering	15 project synergies	15 synergies

Table 13: Status of Dissemination KPIs (M36)

Status of the Exploitation KPIs (M36)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements by M36
[E1] Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement Analysis	Develop a framework to analyse social movements >8 case studies analysis Develop bottom-up participatory events >Organisation of 24 national-level events, 6 Transnational level ones (3 online and 3 face to-face)	8 case studies analysis completed 24 national-level events 6 Transnational level (3 online and 3 F2F)
[E2] Transnational Network (T5.1)	Develop an active community of stakeholders >Involvement of 65 organisations/individuals	The FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network counts 300 registered members from feminist organisations, collectives, academia, including early-career researchers and Individuals.
[E3] Policy Toolkit (D5.3)	Develop a framework for effective engendered policies	3 Policy Briefs, 1 Policy Toolkit
[E4] FIERCE's training material	Recorded modules from the Feminist Summer School exploit in other trainings and capacity building >3 trainings organised	YES
[E5] FIERCE's Lessons Learnt	Expanding the outcomes beyond the end of the project	FIERCE Partners' Individual Exploitation Plans completed Transferability and Replication Guidebook of the FIERCE Actions completed FIERCE Transnational Feminist Network created

Table 14: Status of Exploitation KPIs (M36)

Annex 2: Guidelines and podcast procedure for partners

Guidelines and podcast procedure

Fierce Dialogues

These podcasts will serve as a dynamic platform that addresses contemporary feminist issues at the national level in each FIERCE country.

At least 8 podcasts must be conducted (8 podcasts – 8 national cases).

Podcasts could be conducted in English or in partner's national language.

Our objectives

- To provide insights into the most pressing feminist challenges and achievements specific to each FIERCE country or the broader EU context.
- To offer listeners knowledge and understanding of the ongoing efforts in achieving gender-equal and inclusive democracies.

Format and Duration

- ✓ All podcasts can be conducted via Zoom.
- ✓ The “meeting” link will be provided by VIL and will be recorded and exported as audio and video. VIL will also participate in these “meetings” to facilitate smooth progress.
- ✓ All participants should be briefed on the podcast's theme and objectives.
- ✓ The podcasts should be kept within a maximum duration of **30 minutes** to ensure engaging content.

You will need

- ✓ Your laptop.
- ✓ Headphones for better voice recording.
- ✓ A quiet room. To minimize the noise, doors and windows should be closed. It is also important not to be in an empty room but in one full of objects.
- ✓ Good internet connection.

Type of podcasts

Interviews with Gender Experts/Feminist Activists/Political Actors:

For this option, we will have one person from the consortium conducting an interview with an external guest (outside of the consortium), who could be a gender expert, feminist activist, political actor, or another researcher from our “sister” projects.

- ✓ key points/questions should be prepared.
- ✓ allow spontaneous discussions.
- ✓ guest selection should align with the podcast's overall theme.

Informative Podcasts:

This format will feature one or two experts from the consortium speaking about a specific topic related to gender equality or feminist activism.

- ✓ Prepare an outline or script to ensure a well-structured and coherent presentation or discussion.
- ✓ If the topic is presented as a monologue-style ensure providing valuable insights, research findings, and practical recommendations.

- ✓ In the case of two experts, the format will be a discussion-style podcast, where they can share different perspectives on the same topic, offering a comprehensive view of the subject matter.

Podcast Topics

The podcast episodes could focus on topics related to:

- ✓ feminist movements,
- ✓ gender equality,
- ✓ women's and LGBTQ+ rights,
- ✓ political challenges and solutions in each FIERCE country or at the EU level.

Examples:

- Policy changes and their implications on women and other marginalized groups.
- Intersectionality and its role in shaping feminist discourse and activism in Europe.
- Critical challenges faced by feminists.
- Other topics that each partner finds useful to focus on. Please suggest topics

Suggested questions for the interviews

Here are some basic questions that can be applied to all interviewees. These questions can serve as a starting point to understand their perspectives and experiences, and you can then tailor follow-up questions based on their specific expertise and insights:

- Can you please introduce yourself and your background in feminist activism or your work related to gender equality?
- From your perspective, what are the most pressing feminist issues in [specific country/EU context] today?
- What advice or guidance would you give to individuals who want to become more involved in feminist activism or support gender equality in their communities?
- How can we bridge the gap between local/national feminist movements and broader EU-level initiatives to create a more unified approach to gender equality?
- Looking ahead, what do you envision as the most important priorities for feminist activism in [specific country/EU], and how can we work towards achieving them?

Podcast structure (30 minutes)

Intro music and information about FIERCE (standard by VIL): 1-2 minutes

- ✓ Show intro (who you are, what you're going to talk about): 30-60 seconds
- ✓ Introduction: A brief introduction about the country (or EU context) being discussed, setting the tone for the episode.
- ✓ Closing remarks: Summarize the main points discussed, thank guests, thank audience and invite them to visit our webpage and social media channels to be updated on our activities): 4-5 minutes
- ✓ Closing music and outro (standard by VIL)

Annex 3: Five FIERCE Feminist Claims campaign posters for organic and paid social media posts

Figure 72: Campaign posters of the FIERCE campaign for organic and paid social media posts

Annex 4: Final Conference Communication (promo designs, posters, banners merchandise and selected examples of social media posts)

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

FINAL CONFERENCE
“Feminist futures for revitalising democracy across Europe”

PRE-CONFERENCE FEMINIST EVENT
“Feminist Movements in Time and Space & Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe”

19-20 JUNE
2025

#WeAreFIERCE

BRUSSELS - BELGIUM

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

#WeAreFIERCE

FINAL CONFERENCE

FRIDAY - 20.06.2025 | 9:15 - 9:40

Welcome Speeches

José Antonio MORENO DÍAZ
Member European Economic and Social Committee

Rosa Pérez Monclús
Policy Assistant
Directorate - General for Research and Innovation, European Commission

BRUSSELS
BELGIUM

European Economic and Social Committee
Rue Van Maerlant 2, 1040 Brussels, Belgium

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

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FINAL CONFERENCE

FRIDAY - 20.06.2025 | 9:40 - 10:00

FIERCE main results

BRUSSELS
BELGIUM

Kyriaki Karydou
Project coordinator
ViLabs

Susi Meret
Scientific co-coordinator
Aalborg University

Lise Rolandsen Agustin
Scientific co-coordinator
Aalborg University

Funded by the European Union

European Economic and Social Committee
Rue Van Maerlant 2, 1040 Brussels, Belgium

European Economic and Social Committee

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

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FINAL CONFERENCE

FRIDAY | 20.06.2025

BRUSSELS - BELGIUM

PANEL 1
10:00 - 11:30

How anti-gender and anti-feminist actors and campaigns undermine democracy

MODERATOR

Roman Kuhar
FIERCE project partner
University of Ljubljana

Neil Datta
Executive Director and Founder,
European Parliamentary Forum
for Sexual and Reproductive Rights

David Paternotte
Professor of Sociology
& Gender Studies
Université libre de Bruxelles

Andreas Beyer Gregersen
FIERCE project partner
Aalborg University

Grzegorz Piotrowski
FIERCE project partner
University of Gdansk

Anna Lavizzari
FIERCE project partner
Complutense University
of Madrid

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European Economic and Social Committee
Rue Van Maerlant 2, 1040 Brussels, Belgium

European Economic and Social Committee

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PANEL 2
11:45 - 13:15

FINAL CONFERENCE
FRIDAY | 20.06.2025
BRUSSELS - BELGIUM

MODERATOR

Giada Bonu Rosenkranz
FIERCE project partner
Scuola Normale Superiore

Feminist approaches and responses to democratic crises in the context of rising challenges to gender and equality across Europe (and beyond)

Sylvia Walby
Professor at Royal Holloway
University of London

Christina Grammatikopoulou
FIERCE project partner
Aristotle University
of Thessaloniki

Inés Campillo
FIERCE project partner
Complutense University
of Madrid

Leja Markelj
FIERCE project partner
The Peace Institute

Bertil Emrah Oder
FIERCE project partner
Koç University

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PANEL 3
14:15 - 15:45

FINAL CONFERENCE
FRIDAY | 20.06.2025
BRUSSELS - BELGIUM

MODERATOR

Maria Sangiuliano
FIERCE project partner
Smart Venice

**Feminist futures for revitalising democracy across Europe.
Taking stock of the project results for democratic innovation and policy implications**

Mélissa Camara
Member of the European Parliament,
Member of the FEMM and LIBE
Committees

Tsippora Sidibé
Founder of Tant que je serai noire
(TQJSN)

Segolene Pruvot
FIERCE project partner
European Alternatives

Gea Meijers
General Coordinator, Women in
Development Europe+ (WIDE+)

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Feminist movements
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**PRE-CONFERENCE
BOOK LAUNCH**

THURSDAY - 19.06.2025 | 17:30 - 20:30

**Rosa Feminist
LIBRARY**

**Feminist Movements in Time and Space
and Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe**

Giada Bonu Rosenkranz
FIERCE project partner
Scuola Normale Superiore

Rok Srdelj
FIERCE project partner
University of Ljubljana

Dr. Victoria Showunmi
University College London
(UK)

Prof. Birgit Sauer
University of Vienna
Austria

Funded by the European Union

RoSa Feminist Library
Rue de la Senne 40, 1000 Bruxelles, Belgium

European Economic and Social Committee

Figure 73: Final Conference panel discussions posters

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

Project Final Conference
“Feminist futures for revitalising
democracy across Europe”

REGISTRATIONS OPENED!

20 JUNE
2025

Brussels, Belgium
Hybrid

#WeAreFIERCE

Funded by the European Union

European Economic and Social Committee

fierceprouct_eu

Registrations are now OPEN for the FIERCE Final Conference: “Feminist Futures for Revitalising Democracy Across Europe”

20 June 2025 | Brussels & Online
09:00–16:00 CEST
European Economic and Social Committee - Rue Van Maerlant 2, 1040 Brussels, Belgium
Meeting room: VMA23
Registration Deadline: 12 June 2025

The conference programme features three insightful panel discussions:

- How anti-gender and anti-feminist actors and campaigns undermine democracy
- Feminist approaches and responses to democratic crises in the context of rising challenges to gender and equality across Europe (and beyond)
- Feminist futures for revitalising democracy across Europe: Taking stock of the project results for democratic innovation and policy implications

Προβολή στατιστικών

Πρωτοθση δημοσίευσης

Αρέσει στο χρήστη karydak1 και 24 ακόμη

5 Μαΐου

Προσθέστε ένα σχόλιο...

Δημοσίευση

Figure 74: Selected social media posts promoting the Final Conference

Figure 75: Merchandise (coasters and bookmarks) for the Final Conference

Figure 76: Name Tags for speakers and participants

Figure 77: Selected examples of social media posts during the Final Conference

Annex 5: Questionnaire and guidelines for Partner's Individual Exploitation Plans co-creation

Guidelines

In the table below, you'll find the **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** of the FIERCE project.

For each KER, you are invited to answer the set of questions that follow, selecting those that are relevant to your organisation or the sector you represent within the project.

Objective

This questionnaire aims to reflect your **Individual Exploitation Plan that will be included in D6.3**, aligning FIERCE's KERs with your organisation's **strategic goals** and potential future impact. Remember that the exploitation of FIERCE results beyond the project lifetime falls under our **contractual obligations**.

To complete the questionnaire:

 Pro Tip: Be FIERCE, ambitious but realistic! Think about what's achievable within your organization's capacity and what might scale up with the right partners or resources.

 Remember: Your insights will feed into the Individual Exploitation Plans, shaping how FIERCE's results live on after the project ends. So, be bold and specific!

 In addition to the guiding questions, you'll find a few examples to help you formulate your answers. For further reference and convenience, you can also draw inspiration from the team responses gathered during the Sustainability and Exploitation Workshop in Gdańsk (attached to this email).

Please complete the questionnaire per organization and return it to areti.provata@vilabs.eu by the 6th of June. We envisage that each organization will be able to utilize all FIERCE KERs however if you find that something is irrelevant to you please feel free to indicate it in the questionnaire and justify your answer.

<p>KER 1: Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement analysis. An Interdisciplinary, multidimensional, multi-level framework built on a bottom-up approach to feminism and democracy (WP1 & WP2).</p>
<p>How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization's mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)</p>
<p>In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)</p>
<p>How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)</p>
<p>How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)</p>
<p>Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)</p>

<p>KER 2: Transnational feminist Network</p> <p>The establishment of the Transnational feminist Network aims at a continued exchange of experiences, peer review and scaling up of the experimented democratic innovations at local/national levels, including the willingness to strengthen the capacity of the feminist actors and to mobilise against anti-gender movements.</p>
<p>How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization's mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)</p>
<p>In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)</p>
<p>How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)</p>
<p>How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)</p>
<p>Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)</p>
<p>KER 3: FIERCE's training material</p> <p>The FIERCE Course is a self-paced programme that explores non-hierarchical forms of feminist knowledge generation, bridging research and activism/practice to strengthen intersectional feminist alliances and counter the spread of anti-gender and anti-feminist discourses and politics. The course combines academic lectures by FIERCE researchers with presentations from activists, who share knowledge and lessons learned from their mobilisation practices. It invites participants to reflect on the current political scenario dominated by the far right, engage in discussions on future feminist strategies, and explore pathways for building intersectional alliances.</p>
<p>How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization's mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)</p>
<p>In what ways has this KER contributed (or can) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)</p>
<p>How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)</p>
<p>How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)</p>
<p>Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)</p>
<p>KER 4: FIERCE Actions</p> <p>FIERCE Actions are feminist-driven initiatives designed to promote democratic participation and</p>

innovation from an intersectional feminist perspective. 18 FIERCE ACTIONS were supported by the project (7 actions were proposed as the result of collaborative work elaborated within the FIERCE National Labs and 11 Actions were selected as the result of an open call). FIERCE Actions combined several forms of actions, notably when it comes to public events that combined round tables, cultural events, workshops and/or exhibitions.

Main forms of actions:

- The most used form of action was that of cultural events or activity, which were used in 7 of the FIERCE Actions
 - There were 2 exhibitions: 1 on Reproductive Rights in Slovenia, 1 on surviving sexual violence in Denmark.
 - 2 FIERCE actions focussed solely on workshops, notably some actions focussed on internal workshops within a given group or community, as a basis for self-empowerment and learning in a safe environment
- One film was produced, together with a policy brief as campaign support and material
Cartoons were produced as a way to raise awareness and to support self-consciousness within the LGBTQIA+ community
One self-defence manual

For reference see [D4.2](#)

In which FIERCE actions are you interested? Answer the following questions based on your reply here!

How will you use this/these FIERCE Action(s) within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization's mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)

In what ways can this/these FIERCE Action(s) contribute to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)

How can this/these FIERCE Action(s) help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)

How will this/these FIERCE Action(s) continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)

Can this/these FIERCE Action(s) be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)

KER 5: FIERCE National Labs – the co-creation methodology and analysis

FIERCE labs were conceived as hybrid spaces, mixing elements of different theoretical and methodological approaches, in which academic research meets with an empirical co-creation process. They can also be defined as action-oriented “dialogues”, implying that labs were spaces of encounter between a multiplicity of actors in which the discursive dimension was predominant while at the same time a concrete output was expected to be achieved by the groups.

FIERCE National Labs were indeed spaces of discussion about the most relevant current themes and challenges present in the European feminist movements (nationals and transnational) but also went beyond their discursive dimension: they intended to strengthen alliances between the participants and

oriented to action, aimed at developing concrete and specific “policy- politically oriented outcomes”. FIERCE Labs were spaces for mobilizing "academic activism," and they could be understood as places for self-reflection on the roles of different actors within the feminist movement.

For reference see [D4.1](#)

How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization’s mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)

In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)

How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)

How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE’s outcomes in your academic activities)

Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)

KER 6: Scientific publications

The publications that were created throughout the FIERCE project duration

How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization’s mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)

In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)

How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)

How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE’s outcomes in your academic activities)

Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)

KER 7: FIERCE’s communication material

The communication material for the project’s purposes: website, videos, podcasts, campaigns etc

How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization’s mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)

In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)

ideas)
How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)
How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)
Can this KER be adapted and applied to other contexts, projects, occasions? And if yes, how? (i.e: other departments, sectors, regions/countries, adjustments needed to make it work elsewhere beyond your organization)
KER 8: Policy Toolkit
Policy toolkit aims to present methods and practices - in a simple and easily usable manner - that provide innovation in democratic engagement, while also introducing policy recommendations to defend women and LGBTQ+ rights in the face of the identified 'backlash' against Gender Rights.
How will you use this KER within your organization or sector? (i.e: in your organization's mission or strategy, concrete steps to be taken to apply it, key people or departments involved)
In what ways has this KER contributed (or can contribute) to building your organizational or professional capacity and improving the quality or effectiveness of your work? (i.e: Replication in other projects, Inclusion in methodology in other projects, enhance teaching methods, building courses for students, cover identified gaps, new consulting/ training/facilitation services, generate new project ideas)
How can this KER help you strengthen or expand your existing networks? (i.e: Build a network with partners/customers, new & continued research collaborations, building new Horizon projects calls, interinstitutional and multidisciplinary cooperation)
How will this KER continue creating value after FIERCE ends? (i.e: resources funding, personnel, infrastructure needed to maintain it, ways to ensure ongoing engagement or support, evolution or expansion over time, already utilized FIERCE's outcomes in your academic activities)
KER 9: FIERCE's Lessons Learnt
The overall project experience and lessons learnt by the partners throughout the project's lifetime
Based on your overall experience with the FIERCE project, what key lessons have you learned, and how do you plan to apply them within your organisation to enhance your professional capacity, improve the quality or effectiveness of your work, and strengthen your existing networks? <i>(Please write freely in one paragraph, maximum 200 words.)</i>